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Reflector Optimization for Low Concentration Photovoltaic-Thermal Solar Collectors

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Cover illustration: CPC-PVT solar collector prototype under real field measurements at Högskolan i Gävle Solar laboratory (Source: Diogo Cabral).

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*There is no plan B
because there is no planet B*

Unknown

Abstract

The alarming new global warming and increasing awareness related to climate change due to the high emissions of carbon dioxide in recent decades linked all nations into a common cause, which requires ambitious efforts to combat climate change by adapting energy systems to its effects.

The knowledge gain presented in this dissertation establishes the foundations for the development of a more efficient concentrating photovoltaic-thermal (PVT) solar collector. The presented work provides decision-makers with a broader, more detailed performance assessment of concentrating PVT solar collectors.

A critical issue for concentrating PVT solar collectors lies in the respective reflector shape, which will determine, to some extent, the overall performance of the CPVT collector. Therefore, several symmetrical reflector design concepts were designed and optimized through a Monte Carlo ray-tracing software. With the support of a MATLAB script, a simulation test methodology has been developed and optimized, allowing a more thorough analysis of the results regarding the viability of the different reflector shapes, which established the compound parabolic collector (CPC) to be the most appropriate reflector geometry for PVT solar collectors.

Moreover, CPC-PVT solar collectors, based on the findings described above, were designed, built and outdoor tested under steady-state method guidelines for their thermal and electrical peak efficiencies, heat losses and incidence angle modifier (IAM) coefficients.

The developments achieved in this dissertation significantly enhanced the annual performance of CPC-CPVT solar collectors, which closes the efficiency/performance gap between mature technologies such as PV modules or ST collectors.

Keywords: Photovoltaic-thermal collector, experimental assessment, collector performance assessment, optical efficiency, concentrating PVT solar collector, ray tracing.

Sammanfattning

Den alarmerande globala uppvärmningen och den ökande medvetenheten i samband med klimatförändringar på grund av de höga utsläppen av koldioxid har samlat alla nationer till den gemensama uppgiften, att bekämpa klimatförändringarna och effekterna av dem genom anpassning av energisystemen.

Den kunskapsökning som presenteras i denna avhandling utgör grunden för utvecklingen av effektivare koncentrerande solcellsmoduler. Det presenterade arbetet möjliggör en bredare och mer detaljerad analys av prestandan hos koncentrerande PVT-moduler.

En kritisk fråga för den koncentrerande PVT solfångarens prestanda är reflektorns geometri, som i hög grad påverkar verkningsgraden. Därför designades och optimerades flera symmetriska reflektorgeometrier. Med hjälp av en Monte Carlo ray-tracing programvara. Med stöd av ett MATLAB-skript har en simuleringstestmetodik utvecklats vilken möjliggör en mer ingående analys av funktionen hos de olika reflektorformerna. Den visade att compound parabolic collector (CPC) är den mest lämpliga reflektorgeometrin för ej solföljande koncentrerande PVT-solfångare.

Dessutom konstruerades, byggdes och testades CPC-PVT-solfångare, baserat på de resultat som beskrivs ovan, enligt steady-state-metoden, för att få termiska och elektriska verkningsgrader värmeförluster och infallsvinkelberoende.

Den utveckling som uppnåts i denna avhandling förbättrar den årliga prestanda hos CPVT-solfångare avsevärt, vilket minskar effektivitetsgapet till mognare tekniker som solcellsmoduler och termiska solfångare.

Nyckelord: Fotovoltaisk-termisk kollektor, experimentell utvärdering, prestandautvärdering, optisk effektivitet, koncentrerande PVT-solfångare, strålgångsanalys.

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“Actions are more valuable than words”

...

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List of Papers

This thesis is based on the following papers, which are referred to in the text by Roman numerals.

Paper I

Cabral, D., Karlsson, B., 2018. Electrical and thermal performance evaluation of symmetric truncated C-PVT trough solar collectors with vertical bifacial receivers. *Sol. Energy* 174, 683-690.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2018.09.045>.

Paper II

Cabral, D., Gomes, J., Karlsson, B., 2019. Performance evaluation of non-uniform illumination on a transverse bifacial PVT receiver in combination with a CPC geometry. *Sol. Energy* 194, 696-708.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2019.10.069>.

Paper III

Cabral, D., Gomes, J., Hayati, A., Karlsson, B., 2021. Experimental Investigation of a CPVT Collector coupled with a Wedge PVT Receiver. *Sol. Energy* 215, 335-345.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2020.12.038>.

Paper IV (Currently under review at Solar Energy Journal)

Cabral, D., 2022. Development of a glazed CPC-PVT solar collector with a Bifacial PVT Receiver.

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During this thesis work, the author has contributed to a total of 13 papers, six published in conferences and seven in journals (two under review). These papers were, as a whole, very important in shaping this thesis and its research direction.

Additional Journal Papers:

Paper 5

Gorouh H., Salmanzadeh M., Nasserian P., Hayati A., Cabral D., Gomes J., Karlsson, B., 2022. Thermal modelling and experimental evaluation of a novel concentrating photovoltaic thermal collector (CPVT) with parabolic concentrator, *Renew. Energy* 181C, 535-553.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2021.09.042>

Key Message: Validation of thermal modelling for CPC-CPVT solar collector.

Paper 6 (Currently under review at Energy Journal)

Cabral D., Gomes J., Hayati A., Gorouh H., Nasseriyan P., Salmanzadeh M., 2022. Experimental Investigation of a Parabolic Trough Solar Collector prototype coupled with a vertical n-PERT half-size Bifacial Solar Cells.

Key Message: Evaluation of a bifacial CPV (collector testing).

Paper 7

Nasseriyan, P., Gorouh, H., Gomes, J., Cabral, D., Salmanzadeh, M., Lehmann, T., Hayati A., 2020. Numerical and Experimental Study of an Asymmetric CPC-PVT Solar Collector. *Energies* 13(7), 1669.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/en13071669>

Key Message: Study on heat conduction through silicone encapsulation.

Additional Conference Papers:

Paper 8

Housoli, S., Cabral, D., Gomes, J., 2021. Performance assessment of concentrated photovoltaic thermal (CPVT) solar collector at various locations. Accepted at the Solar World Congress 2021.

Key Message: Summary of the solar collector testing carried out in Greece and Sweden for RES4BUILD H2020 project.

Paper 9

Furbo, S., Perers, B., Dragsted, J., Gomes, J., Gomes, M., Coelho, P., Yildizhan, H., Cabral, D., Housoli, S., Hayati, A., Kaziukonytė, J., Sapeliaskas, E., Kaliasas, R., 2021. Best practices for PVT technology. Accepted at the Solar World Congress 2021.

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Paper 10

Chacin, L., Rangel, S., Cabral, D., Gomes, J., 2019. Impact study of operating temperatures and cell layout under different concentration factors in a CPC-PV solar collector in combination with a vertical glass receiver composed by bifacial cells. Accepted at Solar World Congress 2019.

Key Message: Construction and testing of a CPV collector.

Paper 11

Panchal, R., Gomes, J., Cabral, D., Eleyele, A., Lança, M., 2019. Evaluation of Symmetric CPVT Solar Collector Designs with Vertical Bifacial Receivers. Accepted at the Solar World Congress 2019.

Key Message: Construction and testing of a CPVT collector with a novel reflector geometry.

Paper 12

Cabral, D., Costeira, J., Gomes, J., 2018. Electrical and Thermal Performance Evaluation of a District Heating System Composed of Asymmetric low concentration PVT Solar Collector Prototypes. Accepted at Eurosun 2018.

Key Message: Evaluation of wall mounted system of a CPVT system composed by 20 Solarus PowerCollectors, at the University of Gävle.

Paper 13

Cabral, D., Dostie-Guindon, P., Gomes J., Karlsson, B., 2017. Ray Tracing Simulations of a Novel Low Concentrator PVT Solar Collector for Low Latitudes. Accepted at the Solar World Congress 2017.

Key Message: Comparison between different reflector geometries for a low concentrating PVT using Tonatiuh ray tracing.

Nomenclature and Subscripts

<i>Symbol</i>	<i>Description [Unit]</i>
θ_c	Acceptance half-angle [°]
t_a	Ambient temperature [°C]
$A_{aperture}$	Aperture area [m ²]
G_b	Beam irradiance [W/m ²]
$t_{cell,PVT}$	Cell temperature [°C]
A_{cell}	Cell area [m ²]
A_c	Collector area [m ²]
T_{in}	Collector inlet temperature [°C]
$T_{col.}$	Collector mean temperature [(T _{out} -T _{in})/2, °C]
T_{out}	Collector outlet temperature [°C]
β	Collector tilt angle [°]
C_i	Concentration factor [-]
b_0	Constant for incident angle modifier
I_{mpp}	Current maximum power point [A]
U_1	Day heat loss coefficient [W/m ² .K]
<i>dark</i> U_1	Dark heat loss coefficient [W/m ² .K]
G_d	Diffuse irradiance [W/m ²]
c_s	Effective thermal capacity [J/m ² .K]
K_s	Effective thermal conductivity [W/m.K]
η_{el}	Electrical efficiency [%]
$\eta_{el,STC}$	Electrical efficiency at standard testing conditions [%]
f	Focal length [mm]
F	Focus [-]
x	Half aperture [mm]
c_1	First-order heat loss coefficient at ($t_m - t_a$) = 0 [W/m ² .K]
U_1	Heat loss coefficient [W/m ² .K]
θ	Incidence angle [°]
$K_{\theta b}(\theta_L, \theta_T)$	Incidence angle modifier for beam radiation [-]
$K_{\theta d}$	Incidence angle modifier for diffuse radiation [-]
t_{in}	Inlet temperature [°C]
t_r	Light transmission [-]
E_l	Long wave irradiance ($\lambda > 3\mu\text{m}$) [W/m ²]
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate [kg/s.m ²]
η_{max}	Maximum efficiency [%]
P_{mpp}	Maximum power point [W]
t_m	Mean fluid temperature [°C]
n	Normal to the surface [-]
V_{oc}	Open circuit voltage [V]
η_{opt}	Optical efficiency [%]

<i>Symbol</i>	<i>Description [Unit]</i>
t_{out}	Outlet temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]
r_{\parallel}	Parallel component of unpolarized radiation [-]
η_0	Peak collector efficiency at $\Delta T = 0 \text{ K}$ [-]
r_{\perp}	Perpendicular component of unpolarised radiation [-]
ΔP	Pressure interval [Bar]
c_8	Radiation losses [$\text{W}/\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K}^4$]
h	Receiver height [mm]
r	Receiver thickness [mm]
ρ	Reflectivity [%]
z	Reflector depth [mm]
$A_{reflector}$	Reflector area [m^2]
n	Refraction index [-]
I_{sc}	Short circuit current [A]
$I_{sc, measured}$	Short circuit current (measured) [A]
$I_{sc, standard module}$	Short circuit current (standard module) [A]
c_4	Sky temperature dependence of heat loss coefficient [-]
γ_s	Solar azimuth angle [$^{\circ}$]
G	Solar irradiance (global) [W/m^2]
G_{beam}	Solar irradiance (beam) [W/m^2]
$G_{diffuse}$	Solar irradiance (diffuse) [W/m^2]
G_{STC}	Solar irradiance (standard testing conditions at $25 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) [W/m^2]
τ	Solar glass transmittance [-]
ρ	Solar reflector reflectance [-]
θ_z	Solar zenith angle [$^{\circ}$]
θ_{NS}	South projection angle [$^{\circ}$]
P_{el}	Specific electrical power output [W/m^2]
c_p	Specific heat [J/K]
Q_{th}	Specific thermal power output [W/m^2]
u	Surrounding air speed [m/s]
β	Temperature coefficient of electrical power [%/K]
c_2	Temperature dependence of heat loss coefficient [$\text{W}/\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K}^2$]
$\eta_{opt,theo.}$	Theoretical optical efficiency [%]
η_{0_beam}	Thermal optical efficiency for beam radiation [%]
$\eta_{0_diff.}$	Thermal optical efficiency for diffuse radiation [%]
V_{mpp}	Voltage maximum power point [V]
c_7	Wind dependence of IR radiation exchange [$\text{W}/\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{K}^4$]
c_6	Wind dependence of the zero-loss efficiency [s/m]
c_3	Wind speed dependence of heat loss coefficient [$\text{J}/\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{K}$]

Subscripts

BIPV	Building Integrated PV
CdTe	Cadmium telluride
CPC	Compound Parabolic Collector
CPVT	Concentrating Photovoltaic-Thermal
CSP	Concentrating Solar Power
CIGS	Copper indium gallium selenide
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
c-Si	Crystalline silicon
DC	Direct Current
DNI	Direct Normal Irradiation
DHW	Domestic hot water
EVA	Ethylene-vinyl acetate
FIPV	Façade Integrated PV
HTF	Heat Transfer Cooling Fluid
IAM	Incidence angle modifier
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IEA	International Energy Agency
IRENA	International Renewable Energy Agency
ISES	International Solar Energy Society
IAM _{Long.}	Longitudinal Incidence Angle Modifier
IAM _{Transv.}	Transversal Incidence Angle Modifier
IV curve	Current-voltage curve
LCPVT	Low Concentrating Photovoltaic-Thermal
MaReCo	Maximum Reflector Concentration
MCRT	Monte Carlo ray-tracing method
PR	Performance ratio
PV	Photovoltaic
PVT	Photovoltaic-thermal
PV+ST	Photovoltaic and solar thermal system combination
PP	Pure parabola
PTC	Parabolic Trough Collector
QDT	Quasi Dynamic Testing
RE	Renewable energy
RES	Renewable energy systems
ROI	Return on investment
RQ	Research question
SFH	Single-family house
SDH	Solar district heating
SHIP	Solar heat for industrial processes
SHC	Solar heating and cooling
ST	Solar thermal
Solarus PC	Solarus PowerCollector
SST	Steady-state testing method
TES	Thermal energy storage

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background

The new climate global warming and its confirmation year after year in statistics/reports led the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) to characterise the 2020s as the “Decade of Action”, which means that policymakers have to address this topic urgently.

The increasing awareness correlated to the climate changes (mainly due to high emissions of carbon dioxide) in recent decades linked all nations in a common cause to undertake ambitious efforts to combat climate change and adapt its energy systems to its effects, such as the 21st global climate change conference treaty of 2015 Paris Climate Agreement. From this meeting, it has been agreed on “holding the increase in the global average temperature to well below 2 °C above pre-industrial levels... recognizing that this would significantly reduce the risks and impacts of climate change” (UNFCCC 2015). This agreement, as laid out in the Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) of each country, has been achieved as the atmospheric concentration of harmful greenhouse gases in the atmosphere increased drastically since the pre-industrial period.

Each country committed itself to reach a global peak of greenhouse gas emissions from the energy sector as early as 2050. On the other hand, the previously stipulated year for meeting the net-zero greenhouse emissions of 2050 in the 2017 IPCC Assessment has been revised and shortened almost 20 years down to 2030, as the specialists realised that the temperature growth rate is above what had been established. To achieve this, all nations, and in particular those that are currently the largest emitters of greenhouse gases, must accelerate their ambitions for reducing their carbon emissions, which gained new impetus by recent events that led the United States to re-join the 2015 Paris Climate Agreement.

The ongoing increase of greenhouse gas emissions leads to an overall global increase in surface temperatures, which creates an imbalance in the environment.

In January 2021, the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) revealed that 2020 (during the global Covid-19 pandemic outbreak) tied with the previous warmest year of 2016. Globally, 2020 was 0.6 °C warmer than the standard 1981–2010 reference period and around 1.25 °C above the 1850–1900 pre-industrial period, which represents just 0.25 °C below the level that the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) states as harmful to humans and cause of ecological damage due to climate change.

Le Quéré et al. (2020) presented the global CO₂ emissions during the Covid-19 forced confinement, which registered an annual average reduction of around -7% with a peak of -17% around April 2020 (after lockdown).

These numbers urge us to shift (progressively) our energy systems towards a cleaner and more sustainable way of producing energy and at the same time

preserve the way of life that we achieved at the expense of our planet. This way, renewable energy systems, which use a sustainable way of producing clean energy from the sun, oceans, rivers, ground heat, wind and others are vital for a prosperous future.

Therefore, more and more, renewable energy stakeholders are urging governments to take instant and aggressive actions, including those with pandemic-relief investments, and set much earlier net-zero carbon emission targets, ideally within this decade (e.g. by 2030). The urge for a sustainable and viable accelerated energy transformation must ensure that no groups are left behind by taking into account all of the appropriate social measures.

Moreover, IRENA and other key organizations such as the International Solar Energy Society (ISES), the global renewable energy community REN21 and various International Energy Agency (IEA) Technology Collaboration Agreements represent a joint voice for vital action to stem the climate crisis. Therefore, renewable energy systems (RES) are key to this action and it is crucial to be well-positioned to transmit the messages that need to be passed on to policymakers, so they can take precise and correct actions towards a greener and sustainable future.

1.2. Motivation for the Thesis

There is no more powerful and inexhaustible energy source than solar energy. The recent territorial expansion combined with the exponential growing energy consumption led to an increasing rise in the demand for installation sites comprising RES technologies.

Existing RES technologies such as solar thermal (ST) and photovoltaic (PV), combined with limited space availability led to the development of photovoltaic-thermal (PVT) solar collectors, which produce heat and electricity from the same gross area. The Solarus PowerCollector (PC), a CPVT solar collector coupled with an asymmetric reflector geometry, is not able to work efficiently at lower latitudes, where the availability of solar radiation is higher, therefore it is required that new developments at the reflector level are performed to increase the overall energy production of a CPVT solar collector.

The need for an improved reflector geometry was an incentive to provide a more efficient electrical and heat conversion to the Solarus PC, which has been the main motivation for this dissertation.

Moreover, the development of a new reflector geometry has the aim of providing not only a higher annual energy yield for the Solarus PC but also for any CPVT solar collector that uses bifacial PVT receivers.

1.3. Aims and Research Topic/Question

This work aims to develop a reflector geometry for photovoltaic-thermal solar collectors that can work efficiently in a wide range of latitudes (i.e., low and medium latitudes) where the amount of solar radiation is greater than at high latitudes like Sweden.

Therefore, several research questions (identified as RQ in this dissertation) were developed and presented below, which include both broader solar aspects and specific questions about CPC-CPVT solar collectors:

1. Can ray tracing be used for the reflector design of a CPVT?
2. Which reflector geometry is the most suitable for a stationary low concentration PVT solar collector?
3. Can the current stationary concentrating PVT solar collectors be improved?
4. Is it possible to increase the overall performance of PVT collectors through an improved reflector geometry (i.e., improve both electrical and thermal incidence angle modifier and overall efficiencies)?
5. Can a CPVT solar collector compete (i.e., performance comparison) with a system composed of an asymmetric concentrating PVT or a PV+ST system? If yes, is it location dependent?
6. Is a CPVT solar collector able to challenge the low prices of manufacturing production of both PV and ST collectors?

1.4. Research Methodology

The current study is based on both computational simulations and field measurements on low concentrating non-tracking PVT solar collectors.

A numerical ray-tracing model software and a multi-paradigm numerical computing environment were used to assess the performance of different reflector geometries and therefore select the ultimate reflector geometry for a future construction of a solar collector to validate the simulation results under real test conditions.

Outdoor field measurements such as incidence angle modifiers, electrical and thermal performance parameters, and daily electrical and thermal diagrams were performed at the solar laboratory that was specifically developed for the study of this assessment. The field measurements were performed by following international standards such as ISO 9806:2017 for thermal characterisation and IEC 61215:2016 for terrestrial PV module categorisation, as no shared standard that couples both electrical and thermal performance models is scientifically available. Weather parameters such as global and diffuse radiation at the collector plane are monitored, while HTF and ambient temperatures are measured to allow the assessment of both thermal and electrical performance parameters.

A new electrical and thermal test facility has been developed and employed, which complied with the specifications of both international standards ISO

9806:2017 and IEC 61215:2016. This dissertation work has been developed with financing from Eureka Eurostars (project number E10625), the Swedish Foundation for International Cooperation in Research and Higher Education (grant number ME 2018-7559) and mainly from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program RES4BUILD (grant agreement No. 814865).

1.5. Limitations

Field measurement materials are often costly and the measurement methods suffer from specific uncertainty. In addition, finding appropriate time-slots for the measurements regarding the sun's "availability" at the installation site facilities required the author to be fully aware and available at any time.

At the first stages of the presented dissertation work, and while the new solar laboratory facilities were under development and construction, the author had to perform measurements with less accurate materials that were later redone (for validation of the previous field measurements) when the solar laboratory was up and running.

Uncertainty in analytical models tends to magnify the differences between the testing and simulated data. The numerical ray-tracing model software uncertainties (i.e., no consideration regarding circumsolar radiation) and limitations affect their predictions, for instance, exact estimation of the shading profiles for a series of PV cell string layouts is not accounted for, which will lead to some deviations. This limitation tends to magnify the incidence angle modifiers as it is not able to account for the diode systems that the receiver PV cell string potentially has, which are accounted for in the outdoor field measurements.

Regarding the HTF temperature measurements, there is always some uncertainty in the amount of glycol that the solar collector system had, as in the establishment of the solar laboratory it had some leakages, which were promptly sealed.

Moreover, by measuring the efficiencies at several positions it became clear that it was practically impossible to ensure a perfect angle of incidence with the normal of the solar collector, as no mechanical tracking system is used.

1.6. Outline of the Appended Papers

1.6.1. Paper I

Symmetrical truncated non-tracking CPVT solar collectors based on parabolic and compound parabolic concentrator (CPC) reflector geometries have been developed and studied. The solar collector design concept has a central vertical bifacial (fin) receiver, which was optimized for lower and medium latitudes.

Moreover, the electrical and thermal performance of the CPVT solar collectors is assessed and analysed, through a numerical ray-tracing model software and a multi-paradigm numerical computing environment.

A thermal (quasi-dynamic testing method for liquid heating collectors described in the international standard for solar thermal collectors ISO 9806:2013) and an electrical performance model were implemented to evaluate the annual performance of the specific design concepts. The evaluation was made for heating domestic hot water (DHW) for a single-family house in Fayoum (Egypt), in which CPC reflector geometries with a concentration factor of 1.6 achieved $+9\%_{\text{rel}}$ up to $+15\%_{\text{rel}}$ higher annual energy yields (in kWh/m²/year) than the pure parabola reflector geometries.

1.6.2. Paper II

A comprehensive evaluation has been carried out on non-uniform solar irradiation profile distributions on four symmetric low concentration CPC-PVT solar collectors. The goal was to optimize the incoming solar radiation that can be collected without the need for tracking. This is possible due to the use of a symmetric reflector geometry with a low concentration factor and lower collector depth. The use of symmetric reflector geometries allows higher annual energy yields worldwide. Furthermore, a low concentration factor is necessary to avoid tracking and a lower collector depth to reduce the shading effect on the PV cell string, which is particularly important for the electrical share of these CPVT design concepts.

Additionally, an electrical and thermal performance evaluation of symmetric truncated LCPVT solar collectors based on a CPC reflector geometry with a central transverse bifacial PVT receiver has been carried out, through a numerical ray-tracing model software and a multi-paradigm numerical computing environment software.

A simplified thermal (quasi-dynamic testing method for liquid heating collectors described in the international standard for solar thermal collectors ISO 9806:2017) and an electrical performance model were employed to characterise the CPC-PVT design concepts. The evaluation was carried out for heating domestic hot water (DHW) for a single-family house (SFH) in Fayoum (Egypt), where annual energy yields between 420 and 452 kWh/m²/year have been achieved.

The non-uniform solar irradiation assessment showed that the PV cells are exposed to high levels of radiation due to the specific reflector geometry.

Furthermore, the study showed that the CPC geometries are very sensitive to the shading effect, as partial shadowing is substantial for high incidence angles.

1.6.3. Paper III

Electrical and thermal outdoor testing measurements have been performed on a low concentration PVT solar collector based on a parabolic reflector geometry with a wedge PVT receiver.

Several outdoor experiments have been carried out and presented, such as daily instantaneous electrical and thermal performance efficiency diagrams, as well as optical efficiency charts.

Moreover, an electrical incidence angle modifier (for both transversal and longitudinal directions) assessment has been performed and presented.

Furthermore, an overall heat loss coefficient of $4.1 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{°C}$ has been attained. A measured thermal and electrical efficiency of 59% and 8% have been achieved, respectively.

Additionally, the placement of the wedge receiver proved to be very sensitive to high incidence angles, as the electrical transversal incidence angle modifier factor decreases significantly after reaching its electrical peak efficiency at $\pm 10^\circ$.

1.6.4. Paper IV

Two innovative concentrating PVT solar trough collector geometry concepts based on CPC geometry concepts (based on CPC 2 and 4 from Paper II) were built and tested, and subsequently, a comparative analysis with the Solarus PC has been made.

As intended, the measurement results confirmed that both CPC 1 and 2 geometries are an improvement from the asymmetric MaReCo geometry of the Solarus PC. The results revealed that the updated version of the CPC geometry is the most suitable for CPVTs, where the electrical peak efficiency per gross area reached 10.6%, which are $+16.5\%_{\text{rel}}$ higher than the Solarus PC. Furthermore, the heat loss coefficients were measured, with $U_l = 5.0 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$ ($\eta_0 = 62.3\%$) and $U_l = 5.4 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$ ($\eta_0 = 61.8\%$) for CPC 1 and 2, respectively. Additionally, the overall optical efficiency of both design concepts outperformed by $+1.1\%_{\text{rel}}$ the optical efficiency measured for the Solarus PC.

Moreover, a PV module combined with a ST collector system to be able to deliver the same overall annual energy yield as the newly developed CPC-PVT solar collector requires on average $+0.02 \text{ m}^2$ (at 45°C), -0.06 m^2 (at 55°C) and -0.15 m^2 (at 65°C) of installed area, for a wide range of latitudes.

Despite the improved IAM and overall efficiencies of the CPC 1 solar collector, a CPVT system to increase its competitiveness requires a material cost reduction (e.g. particularly at the PVT receiver) and at the same time an increased thermal efficiency (that can be accomplished by adding a selective surface to the receiver core, filling the gaps between PV cells).

Nevertheless, the efficiency/performance gap between a system composed of PV+ST technologies and a CPVT decreased, mainly due to the improvements made at the CPC reflector geometry (e.g. by employing symmetrical reflector geometries).

1.7. Co-author Statement

1.7.1. Paper I

The study was organized and planned by the author, Diogo Cabral, together with the co-author. The simulation measurements and data collection were performed by the author. The author did the literature review, analyzed and interpreted the data, presented the modelling results, wrote and revised the paper with the supervision of the co-author. The main author is the corresponding author of the article.

1.7.2. Paper II

The study was organized and planned by the author, Diogo Cabral. The simulation measurements and data collection were performed by the author. The main author did the literature review, analyzed and interpreted the data, presented the modelling results, and wrote the paper. The paper has been revised with help from the co-authors. The main author is the corresponding author of the article.

1.7.3. Paper III

The study was organized and planned by the author, Diogo Cabral, together with the co-authors. The field measurements and data collection were performed by the authors. The main author did the literature review, analyzed and interpreted the data, presented the modelling results, and wrote the paper. A paper revision with help from the co-authors has been performed. The main author is the corresponding author of the article.

1.7.4. Paper IV

The study was organized and planned by the author, Diogo Cabral. The field measurements and data collection were performed by the author. The author did the literature review, analysed and interpreted the data, presented the modelling results, wrote and revised (with support from Prof. Dr. Björn Karlsson) the paper. The main author is the corresponding author of the article.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Energy Systems

In general, all technologies, especially renewable energy (RE) technologies, require further development in areas such as research (i.e., for improved efficiencies), design and field-testing to a greater or lesser degree (depending on the maturity) from one technology to another.

The majority of RE systems (RES) present a high potential for exploitation and development, which comprises technologies such as hydro and ocean power, wind power, solar power, geothermal power and heat, ocean thermal energy conversion and biofuel processes. On the other hand, the complexity of offshore wind and solar power requires further developments to reach expected and suitable system efficiencies.

In recent decades, significant growth has been registered related to the abovementioned RES technologies in terms of improved overall efficiencies and thus installed capacity.

2.2. Renewable Energy System Market Share¹

Since the Paris Agreement, several decision-makers have made significant investments to increase the overall RES market share, which led the renewable power sector to experience an increased record high in installed capacity for the fifth year in a row, surpassing the overall net installations of fossil fuel and nuclear power combined.

The annual report by REN 21 presented a growth of 200 GW in installed renewable power capacity, in 2019. This increase has been largely impacted by the largest increase in solar PV.

Globally, most countries are now able to cost-effectively produce electricity from wind and solar PV rather than generating it from new coal-fired power plants. The operation cost reduction and high reliability of these technologies led to record-low bids/auctions that reached the lowest value ever registered, for solar PV, of 0.0135 €/kWh (July 2020) in Abu Dhabi for 2 GW. Just one month after the record-low presented above, in August 2020, a second solar energy auction for 700 MW was launched in Portugal, which was able to secure the current world record for the lowest bid for PV power generation of 0.0112 €/kWh. Moreover, for wind power generation, Spain auctioned a total of 3 GW of renewable energy capacity in January 2021. The auction reached the lowest wind energy bid ever registered in Europe, which was awarded at 20 €/MWh.

Despite the consolidation of these mature technologies, it favored larger multinational energy companies (i.e., high investment capability) rather than smaller community-led groups.

¹ Referencing from REN 21 report (2019, 2020 and 2021) and Renewables (2020).

Overall, in 2019, the estimated installed renewable energy capacity provided around 27% of the global total electricity generation. The ongoing investment in fossil fuel (and nuclear) power capacity, especially in Asia (e.g. China), increases the challenges for renewable electricity in achieving a larger share of global electricity generation.

2.2.1. Bioenergy

In 2018, the total global final energy demand share for modern bioenergy has reached 5.1%, whereas the industrial heat supply has grown around 2%. Mainly in Europe and North America, the use for heating in buildings such as domestic hot water (DHW) and indoor climate control decreased to roughly 9% of the total industrial heat demand.

Biofuels provide around 3% of transport energy, primarily due to ethanol (grew around 2%) and biodiesel (production growth of around 13%). Globally, in 2019, biofuels production increased 5%, whereas in the electricity sector, bioenergy's contribution rose 9%, to around 501 TWh.

In 2020, global biofuel production fell 5%, with ethanol production down 8%. Biodiesel production rose slightly to meet the increased demand registered for Indonesia, the USA and Brazil. On the other hand, bioelectricity production grew 6%, with China being the major producer.

2.2.2. Geothermal Power and Heat

In 2019, geothermal electricity generation totalled around 95 TWh, while direct use of thermal production surpassed the barrier of 100 TWh to roughly 117 TWh. Experts estimated that, in 2019, new geothermal power generating capacity of 0.7 GW would come online, reaching a global total of 14 GW.

The direct use of geothermal energy for thermal applications has grown nearly 8% on average. The fastest-growing segment proved to be space heating with an annual growth of 13%, where China, Turkey, Iceland and Japan were the most represented countries with roughly 75% of all geothermal direct use.

An estimated 100 MW of new geothermal power generating capacity came online in 2020, which is significantly less than in 2019, with Turkey representing the bulk of new installations.

2.2.3. Hydropower

The annual global hydropower capacity installation registered a deceleration. A new installed capacity of 16 GW has been reported, which raised the global installed capacity to around 1.2 TW, representing a generation increment of 2.3%. Pumped storage capacity had a marginal growth of 0.2% from a single 300 MW system in China, which reached a total installed capacity of 158 GW.

In 2020, although the global hydropower market expanded, it did not recover from several years of deceleration. China added 13 GW, being the largest addition of the previous five years, which put them back in the lead from Brazil regarding commissioning new hydropower capacity.

2.2.4. Ocean Power

Ocean power net additions were of 3 MW, mainly in Europe, with an estimated 535 MW of operating capacity. Ocean power tidal stream devices generated around 15 GWh (which is +50% higher since 2018).

Ocean power generation continued to rise in 2020, surpassing 60 GWh. The industry is now moving from small-scale demonstration and pilot projects to towards semi-permanent installations and arrays of devices.

2.2.5. Wind Power

In 2019, the global offshore wind power market registered a record of new installation share of around 10%, which expanded 19% (i.e., the second largest annual rise with 60 GW). Nowadays, wind power is divided into onshore and offshore installations, which reached 621 and 29 GW, respectively.

Wind energy accounts for 57% of Denmark's electricity generation, with high shares also in Ireland (32%), Uruguay (30%) and Portugal (26%). The 650 GW of installed capacity were able to provide 6% of the total global generation, which shows that RES are a sustainable and viable solution to tackle climate change.

China and the USA led the wind power capacity installed in 2020, in which the world added a record 93 GW. Both countries broke national records for new installations, driven in part by pending policy changes. The rest of the world commissioned about the same amount as in 2019, but several additional countries had record-breaking years.

In 2020, wind power plants accounted for a substantial share of electricity generation in several countries in 2020, including Denmark (over 58%), Uruguay (40%), Ireland (38%) and the United Kingdom (24%).

2.2.6. Concentrating Solar Thermal Power

Global concentrating solar thermal power (CSP) capacity grew 11% in 2019 to around 6 GW, which was below the average annual increase of 24% registered for the past decade.

Tower and parabolic trough installation capacity reached the same number in 2019. 21 GWh of thermal energy storage (TES) was operating in parallel with CSP power plants which keeps the levelised costs of energy lower than in previous years. CSP has increasingly been built alongside both solar PV and wind power to further decrease the production costs and increase capacity value.

CSP markets grew slowly in 2020 as a result of increasing cost competition from solar PV, the expiry of CSP incentives and operational issues at existing facilities. More than 1 GW of new capacity was under construction in 2020 in the UAE, China, Chile and India, although construction did not begin on any new projects. China was the only country to add new capacity during 2020.

2.2.7. Solar Thermal (ST) Heating and Cooling

Solar thermal capacity reached 479 GW in 2019, mainly due to 69% of the total installed capacity being located in China. Solar district heating (SDH) in

Denmark, China and Germany accounts for 24 systems, with 196 MW newly commissioned.

A new record-high installation capacity of 251 MW for solar heat for industrial processes (SHIP) has been reached, with PTC technology dominating with 817 systems, of which 700 MW were supplied as process heat to industry.

An estimated 25 GW_{th} of new solar thermal capacity came online in 2020, with China, Turkey, India, Brazil and the USA leading in new installations. Residential, commercial and industrial clients in at least 134 countries operated 501 GW_{th}, enough to provide heat equivalent to the energy content of 239 million barrels of oil.

2.2.8. Solar Photovoltaics (PV)

Solar radiation is typically harvested through PV systems for electricity generation (efficiencies up to around $-8\%_{rel}$ than the Shockley-Queisser efficiency limit (Qasima et al., 2020) and ST systems for heat generation. PV cell efficiency has grown exponentially in recent decades, and currently, the lab record is around 27% for mono-crystalline and 22% for multi-crystalline silicon wafer-based technology (Gorouh et al., 2022).

Additionally, the highest lab efficiency for thin-film technologies, CIGS and CdTe, is 23% and 21%, respectively. The record lab cell efficiency for Perovskite is 22% (Fraunhofer, 2020).

These developments have a direct impact on the solar PV market as it increased 12% in 2019 (direct current, DC), for a total of 627 GW. The increased demand in Europe, USA and emerging markets led to a global market growth of around 44% (not including China).

Solar PV accounted for 11% of the total PV generation in Honduras and 8.1% in Chile, while in Europe, Italy with 8.6%, Greece with 8.3% and Germany with 8.2% registered the highest shares.

In 2020, solar PV had another record-breaking year with 139 GW_{DC} of new installations, which brought the global total to an estimated 760 GW_{DC}.

2.3. Solar Energy

Following the trend from past years, solar power installed capacity increased more than all fossil fuel and nuclear power generation capacities combined. Moreover, the installed capacity of solar power doubled the wind power capacity and 30% more than all RE combined. The global solar power generation share increased from 42% in 2018 to 48% in 2019, which is more than double the solar power generation registered in 2015.

Even with a small decrease in RE global capacity additions from 62% to 59% in 2016, it has recovered from 2017 until 2019. Overall, it can be seen that solar has been at the top of the global capacity additions in the past years.

2.3.1. Solar Photovoltaic (PV)² Modules

Despite the annual global power generation capacity in addition being held by solar power, this needs to be taken into perspective. In 2019, the solar cumulative share reached 117 GW of installed global capacity, which represents growth of +13%, setting a new solar record.

All solar PV systems combined generated 2.6% of the global power output, which is transversal to all renewables, representing one-third of total generation capacities, and 23% of the world's power output. It is expected that the exponential solar market potential and its constantly improving cost-competitiveness will enable all RE technologies to reach an increasingly larger share, especially solar power.

An increase in demand to 128 GW is expected, which was not met, as the annual market grew around +9%. This trend is due to China's restructuring plan replacing the former incentives which are based on uncapped and attractive feed-in tariffs into a framework based on auctions. Moreover, this restructuring plan also relies on subsidies to better control the cost and growth, reducing newly installed capacities.

The main key factor for the increasing solar power installed capacity share is its exponential cost decrease over the last decade, which has finally led solar to become the "lowest" cost leader.

In just two years, from 2009 to 2011, PV solar electricity generation cost decreased around 240% and in the last eight years, the drop was three times lower, reaching lower costs than unsubsidized fossil fuels and nuclear.

In 2020, the outbreak of Covid-19 led the solar market analysts to significantly decrease their 2020 predictions with one conservative prediction from the International Energy Agency (IEA). The IEA anticipates around 107 GW of new solar installations for 2020, mainly due to the political measures implemented around the world, such as supply chain disruptions, lockdowns and emerging financing challenges.

2.3.2. Solar Thermal (ST)³ Collectors

In 2018, a total installed capacity of 34 GW_{th} was installed worldwide, which corresponds to around 48.10⁶ m² of solar collectors. China with 28 GW_{th} and Europe with 3 GW_{th} were the main ST markets, which comprises 83% of the overall new collector installations. The remaining market shares were registered in Latin America (1.2 GW_{th}), Asia (1.4 GW_{th}), the USA and Canada (0.6 GW_{th}), the Middle East/North Africa or MENA countries (0.4 GW_{th}), Australia (0.4 GW_{th}), the Sub-Saharan African countries (0.1 GW_{th}), and remaining markets with 1.7 GW_{th}.

With a share of 71% of the newly installed capacity in 2018, evacuated tube collectors are the main employed ST collector technology worldwide, where the Chinese market accounted for 83% of all newly installed collectors.

In contrast, in 2019, the cumulated ST capacity in operation was 479 GW_{th}, which fell short from wind power by 170 GW_{el} and photovoltaics by 193 GW_{el}

² Referencing from SolarPower Europe (2020) and Renewables (2020).

³ Referencing from Weiss and Spörk-Dür (2020).

of installed capacity. CSP and geothermal energy registered low overall installed capacity with 7 GW_{el} and 14 GW_{el}, respectively.

Overall, a total energy of 389 TWh_{th} has been supplied by ST systems, while wind power plants and PV systems supplied 1567 TWh_{el} and 751 TWh_{el}, respectively.

2.4. Fundamentals of PVT Collectors

The quest to decarbonize electrical and thermal systems has never been more urgent. While this decarbonization of the electrical system is on track, the decarbonization of thermal systems has not been tackled. ST systems typically make up about 50% of the final energy demand and Hadorn et al. (2020) suggest that a large portion of the demand could potentially (i.e., while requiring significant technology developments) be supplied by renewable PVT solutions. PVT solutions address another important and increasingly emerging issue – spatial and network constraints, thus requiring less space than a PV or ST collector would.

Solar energy systems are progressively increasing their installed capacity due to subsidies and incentives as well as due to their increased efficiency. Higher efficiencies and economic competitiveness increase annually, which leads to more investment and a sustainable energy mix.

The active application of solar energy technologies relies mainly on the use of PV systems for electricity generation and ST systems for heat generation.

The electrical efficiency of PV cells typically corresponds to a fraction of the incident solar radiation with 22% for multi-crystalline and 27% for mono-crystalline silicon wafer-based technology (tested under laboratory conditions and presented by Fraunhofer, 2020), which leaves the remaining share to be converted into heat. Additionally, the highest lab efficiency for thin-film technologies, CIGS and CdTe, is 23% and 21%, respectively.

The low surface power and energy density of PV modules, combined with the relatively low exergy of the solar flat-plate thermal collectors, and the limited available roof/ground area can be overcome by higher combined electrical and thermal (per unit area) efficiencies of a solar photovoltaic thermal (PVT) system. This is particularly important if the available roof area is limited, but integrated solar energy concepts are needed to achieve a climate-neutral energy supply for consumers, such as in residential and commercial buildings.

By co-generating both heat and electricity from the same gross area, PVT collectors extract the excess thermal energy generated by the PV cells by employing a heat transfer cooling fluid (HTF), increasing electrical efficiencies due to lower PV cell temperatures.

For solar energy applications, the wavelengths of importance for solar energy applications are typically from around 0.3 to approximately 25 μm of the solar spectrum (i.e., ultraviolet, visible and infrared region). PV cells optimally operate at a very narrow range of the solar spectrum (i.e., from around 0.3 to approximately 11 μm), therefore the radiation that is not within this range merely warms the PV cells and can be used as thermal energy, thus limiting the maximum electrical efficiency.

Due to the co-generation of heat and electricity, PVT collectors utilize a broader solar irradiance spectrum, which makes them more attractive in terms of energy conversion effectiveness as can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Spectral distribution of solar irradiance, optical and heat losses, and heat and electricity gains.

As previously stated, PVT solar collectors are (in a simplified way) the combination between a PV module and a ST collector into a single unit. The PV elements convert the incoming solar energy into electricity, which is typically encapsulated with ethylene-vinyl acetate (EVA) or a solar silicone gel in case of low concentration PVT solar collectors (e.g. Solarus PowerCollector and the compound parabolic concentrator studied and developed in this thesis).

On the other hand, the thermal elements of the PVT collector convert the solar energy into heat gains typically by absorption. The absorption is done at the receiver level, in which the harvested heat from the PV cells (highest material share exposed to the solar radiation) and PVT absorber (e.g. thermally couples the PV cells to the HTF) is transferred into an HTF.

Figure 2. Schematic cross-section of an unglazed PVT collector with sheet-and-tube type heat exchanger and rear insulation: Anti-reflective cover glass; Front-encapsulant layer (e.g. EVA); PV cells; Back-encapsulant layer (e.g. EVA); Backsheet (e.g. PVF); Heat exchanger/thermal absorber (e.g. aluminum, copper or polymers); Thermal insulation (e.g. mineral wool, polyurethane) and Frame. Based on Aste et al. (2015).

2.4.1. Temperature Dependence Overview

For a solar collector to produce usable thermal energy, the HTF must be at lower temperatures than the absorber (i.e., in ST collectors) and PV cells (i.e., in PVT collector) as “heat can never pass from a colder to a warmer body without some other change” (statement by Clausius from 1854). Therefore, the thermal coupling between the PV cells (hottest element in a PVT collector) and the thermal absorber (and thus the HTF) is of most importance for the overall performance of a PVT collector.

Furthermore, silicon wafer-based PV technology is typically more efficient at lower module temperatures as their average temperature coefficient is around $0.4\%/^{\circ}\text{C}$, which leads to a lower open-circuit voltage and thus to a decreased electrical efficiency (Würfel and Würfel, 2008).

Just as PV modules reach higher efficiencies at lower module temperatures, the ST collectors do so too as the heat losses are proportional to the receiver’s surface temperature. It is important to note that the operating temperature is regulated by the overall system (i.e., temperature required at the heat storage) and not solely by the solar collector. According to Lämmle (2018), a ST collector mean operating temperature typically ranges between 30 and 90 °C. On the other hand, a PV cell typically operates at module temperature between 30 and 60 °C, which overlaps (to some extent) with a ST collector mean operating temperature. This overlap in operating module and mean temperature leads to different behaviors from the PV module and the ST collector, as the ST collector has a deeper decrease in efficiency than the PV module for increasing temperatures.

Moreover, the PVT collectors do not operate at optimum efficiency for either PV or ST operation mode, which leads to a compromise between both

elements. Therefore, PVT collectors either operate as *electricity* or *heat optimum operation*, which prioritize the operating agent needs for a specific application, either giving priority to the electricity or heat generation:

- *Electricity optimum operation* implies a low HTF mean temperature to lower the heat dissipation, thus enhancing the PV cell electrical efficiency.
- *Thermal optimum operation* implies higher HTF mean temperatures closer to the operation point of conventional ST collectors.

For an overall PVT collector optimum performance it is crucial to efficiently utilize the available solar resource, therefore, it is of greatest interest to install PVT solar collectors for a better use of space.

Amongst several solar specialists, Hadorn et al. (2020) consider PVT technology to be more complex than the available mature technologies such as PV or ST technologies. Nevertheless, PVT provides significant advantages such as the ones mentioned below.

- PVT uses the same area as a PV or ST module to provide electricity and heat, and in some cases cooling.
- The solar electricity production of an unglazed PVT module is not less than that of a PV-only module, which can be slightly higher if the collector is operated at temperatures below those of a PV-only module, due to the extraction of thermal energy.
- Depending on their type, PVT collectors can produce heat for a wide range of applications.
- The ST production can be used to preheat or heat DHW. In well-designed hybrid collectors, the production can be almost as high as that of just an ST collector, 10–20% less, a reduction mainly due to the part of the irradiation that is converted to electricity.
- The thermal energy converted from either solar radiation or ambient heat, can be used as a heat source for a heat pump. The PV electricity can directly supply the circulation pumps and partially the heat pumps. In some cases, for instance, a DHW heat pump in summer periods can completely supply the heat pump, thus leading to a fully solar solution.
- Solar generated thermal energy can be stored in many ways, such as on-site tanks, precinct-level tanks, aquifers, ground strata and pit storage systems. The current thermal storage options are much more cost-effective than electricity storage. This is especially true when PVT is used in combination with a heat pump that will make good use of the stored energy. The heat pump enables higher output temperatures enabling more compact storage solutions to be implemented. This is critical when space is limited. Larger thermal energy solutions can be accessed via DH networks and enable the produced summer excess heat to be stored seasonally for the winter.
- As the demand for cooling increases, PVT has the potential to address this demand through direct solutions using heat in absorption machines

or when at night-time the unglazed PVT collector, under clear sky conditions, is exposed to the night radiation phenomena. This effect sub-cools the HTF below ambient temperatures and can be used directly and/or stored. A compact storage example is ice storage. When coupled as a source of a heat pump, it can be recharged by an unglazed PVT collector with very high efficiencies even during the cold heating season.

- PVT collectors have a low social impact, as no noticeable noise is produced and when incorporated into a roof or façade they have no detrimental visual impact.
- Radiative and convective cooling also can be provided directly during the night using the thermal absorber or indirectly through a machine driven by PV electricity.

2.5. PVT Collector Classification

According to Zondag (2008), PVT collectors can be classified into four main categories according to their heat transfer medium, employed PV cell technology, collector design and their specific operating temperature.

Typically, PVT solar collectors either have air or liquid as an HTF, the latter being either water or a mixture between water and glycol (anti-freeze and anti-corrosion product) (Sathe and Dhoble, 2017). PVT air collectors are less sensitive to overheating as typically they are categorized as unglazed PVT collectors (i.e., glass cover, thus higher heat losses). On the other hand, PVT liquid collectors comprise the biggest installation share, however, they present overheating issues. Nevertheless, water (as a heating fluid) has a higher heat capacity and thermal conductivity than air (Zondag, 2008).

The exponential increment in efficiency of PV cells in recent decades tends to raise end users' expectations. Therefore, the system where this technology is employed is of most importance, since the specific suitability depends on electrical conversion efficiency, temperature and absorption coefficient (Lämmle, 2020). C-Si PV cells have the highest share for both PVT and PV collectors. Mono-crystalline cells have enhanced electrical efficiency and solar absorption than polycrystalline PV cells. Thin-film technologies, which comprise CIGS and CdTe technologies, are typically characterized by their lower temperature coefficient than c-Si cells, thus more suitable to work under higher HTF and module temperatures. In applications such as PVT collector, where cooling is needed at PV cell level, multi-junction (III-V cells) solar cells are generally used for systems where high concentration is required. Therefore, this technology (III-V cells) can be a contender for PVT solar collectors that require higher operating HTF temperatures.

Additionally, PVT collectors can be classified into two main clusters according to their design, such as flat plate and concentrating PVT collectors. Flat-plate PVT collectors can be sub-categorized into unglazed (e.g. similar aesthetics to PV modules, but without front glass cover) and glazed (e.g. similar in design to PV modules, with an additional front glass cover to decrease heat loss) PVT collectors.

Moreover, concentrating PVT collectors can be labelled due to their concentration ratio, such as low, medium and high concentration factors. Typically, low concentration PVT collectors are used as stationary (fixed collector tilt angle) solar systems. On the other hand, high concentration requires variable collector tilt angles and thus entails one or two-axis tracking systems.

A balanced operating fluid temperature is critical to reach higher electrical and thermal efficiencies. Therefore, the generality of the PVT water collectors and ST collectors can be divided into their range of applications:

- Low-temperature applications ($\sim 27\text{-}35^\circ\text{C}$) including swimming pool heating or spas, while operating temperatures up to 50°C are required for space heating. Typically found in unglazed PVT collectors (low thermal insulation);
- Medium-temperature applications for temperatures up to 80°C (e.g. glazed or evacuated tube collectors);
- High-temperature applications for temperatures higher than 80°C (e.g. high-efficiency flat-plate or concentrator collectors).

The temperatures of a specific system depend on the requirements of the heat supply system for DHW and space heating. Therefore, Lämmle et al. (2020) allocated (in a schematic view, Figure 3) each PVT technology and applications per operating temperature.

Figure 3. Map of PVT technologies and applications per operating temperature (Lämmle et al., 2020).

2.6. PVT and CPVT solar collectors: Advantages and Disadvantages

Due to the newest commercial interest in PVT solar collectors, it is important to compare the properties of PVT with standard ST and PV solar collectors.

The main benefits of PVT collectors, when compared to PV and ST, are (1) the possibility of increasing cell efficiency by reducing the cell operating temperature (Kazem et al., 2020), when heat is extracted at low temperatures. Therefore, it is fundamental that the panel design is able to transfer the heat from the cells to the HTF efficiently as well as homogeneously; (2) the production of one unit of PVT uses fewer raw materials than an equivalent area of ST and PV panels, which is expected to enable a lower production cost in €/kWh of annually produced heat power; (3) reduction of the installation area, which enables the deployment of more installed capacity per roof area.

On the other hand, the main disadvantages of PVT technologies are the higher complexity in both production and installation, and the reduced market share since it requires customers that need both heat and electricity (George et al., 2019).

The PVT-collector has higher heat losses than a high-efficiency ST collector, since the module surface has a high thermal emittance.

Some PVT manufacturers combine the concept of concentration to reduce the usage of PV cells and thermal absorber material. Concentration results in extra reflection losses from the reflector and a worse IAM profile. It reduces the heat losses (Cabral and Karlsson, 2018) and the number of expensive components (solar cells, receiver with selective surface).

In the end, it is a trade between the positive effect of lowering the collector cost and the negative effect of lowering output per square meter of aperture area (Tian et al., 2018).

Concentration also reduces the heat losses by means of less absorber area (Lämmle et al., 2016). This way, concentration allows higher thermal efficiency at high temperatures to be achieved, although it will reduce the efficiency of the solar cells (Lämmle et al., 2018).

Some of the disadvantages of concentration are the bulkier appearance, higher stagnation temperatures which lead to more expensive components, and lower power density. Factors such as simplicity or aesthetics are important for solar customers; however, the most important parameter remains the cost per kWh of heat and electricity produced. The water temperatures obtained in PVT hybrid systems are often moderate to keep the PV cell at low temperatures due to the voltage drop with an increased temperature. If the hybrid system is to be operated at low temperatures for maximizing the electricity production, the warm water produced can be useful for floor heating and pre-heating tap water. The optical efficiency is a key to the electrical and thermal performance of a CPVT hybrid system and consequently its importance has been assessed.

2.7. Current State of PVT Technology⁴

The past years showed that the PVT market is gaining momentum, especially in European countries, where the highest share of installed capacity of PVT collectors is located.

⁴ The data presented in this chapter has been acquired from the Solar Heat Worldwide report (2018, 2019 and 2020).

Recently, the exponentially growing number of specialized PVT manufacturers that entered the European market, increased the awareness and interest in this technology, which led it to be included in the market survey developed by the Solar Heat Worldwide consortium. The report presented in both 2018 and 2019 included data from the work developed by experts in both PV and T technologies, who are enthusiastic and share a common passion for this emerging solar technology. A market survey has been carried out under the works made by the IEA SHC Task 60 participants on “Application of PVT collectors.”

By the beginning of 2019 (relative to 2018), a cornerstone had been reached of more than 1 million square meters of PVT collectors installed, in more than 25 countries.

The report developed by Weiss and Spörk-Dür (2020) presents the global market developments and trends in 2019 of PVT solar collectors, in which the total area installed is around $1.167 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^2$ (e.g. $675 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^2$ in Europe, $281 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^2$ in Asia, $134 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^2$ in China and $70 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^2$ for the rest of the world). Overall, it accounted for $606 \text{ MW}_{\text{th}}$, $208 \text{ MW}_{\text{peak}}$ of the total installed capacity, which was provided by 31 PVT collector manufacturers and PVT system suppliers from 12 different countries.

Within the countries with the highest capacity installed, France has around 42%, South Korea has 24%, China around 11% and Germany with roughly 10% of installed PVT systems. The market for PVT collectors registered a significant global growth of +9% on average in 2018 and 2019. This trend was also observed in the European market with a slightly higher growth rate of +14%, which corresponds to an increase of the annually new installed thermal and electrical capacity of $41 \text{ MW}_{\text{th}}$ and $13 \text{ MW}_{\text{peak}}$, respectively.

Unglazed (also known as uncovered) water collectors are the most disseminated PVT technology with its largest market share of around 55% followed by air collectors (43%) and covered water collectors (2%). Evacuated tube collectors and low concentrator PVT play only a minor role in the total number of PVT installed capacity.

PVT technology suppliers commissioned at least 2800 new PVT systems worldwide in 2019. The number of PVT systems in operation at the end of 2019 was 25823, of which 3296 unglazed PVT collectors were in operation, corresponding to a gross area of $667 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^2$. Out of these systems, 86% of the PVT installations were focused on solar air (pre)heating of buildings followed by 7% for DHW for single-family households and the remaining 7% for solar combi-systems (e.g. for DHW and space heating), as well as for DHW for multifamily houses, hotels, hospitals, swimming pools and district heating.

In a global context, solar air systems (i.e., including PVT air collectors) have the highest share of the PVT market, with the majority of the installations being located in the French market.

2.8. PVT Collectors State of Art

In section 2.5, PVT collectors have been classified according to their design, either as flat or concentrating PVT collectors. Since the focus of this PhD thesis

is on a glazed concentrating liquid-based PVT collector with c-Si PV cells, a more detailed assessment of concentrating PVT collectors and their optical properties is addressed to avoid lengthiness and repetition. Therefore, the literature overview in the following chapter is strongly focused on the optical properties of a PVT solar collector.

As the research topic in question derives from the need to address the new meridians' emerging markets, this thesis focuses on the perspective of the main concentrating (CPVT) manufacturer Solarus Sunpower AB (addressed in this thesis as Solarus), which is to develop a new reflector geometry to couple with their developed bifacial PVT receiver. This PVT receiver has monocrystalline silicon (c-Si) PV cell strings in its core, featuring a high level of reliability and a high solar absorption coefficient, which can be enhanced if coupled with an adequate reflector geometry.

Glazed liquid-based HTF PVT collectors aim at replacing conventional ST collectors given the similarity between systems and operating temperature range. Zondag et al. (2008) expect these types of PVT collectors to overcome the challenge of temperature stability reaching higher shares of the solar market. Moreover, Zondag et al. (2008) expected that researchers would focus on temperature-protected PVT collectors with overheating protection, which was the aim of the PhD thesis developed by Lämmle (2018).

There are several commercially available concentrating PVT collectors, such as the stationary low concentrating PVT from Solarus and the line focusing PVT that was introduced by Absolicon AB and SunOyster Systems GmbH.

The motivation behind liquid-based concentrating PVT collectors is to replace the conventional thermal absorbers and at the same time decrease the amount of active PV area by applying cheaper reflectors. The reduced active PV cell area decreases the overall radiative heat losses due to the reduced hot surfaces. Stationary low concentration factor solar collectors (typically below 10 suns) do not reach temperatures higher than 120 °C (Lämmle et al., 2020), as they do not need the use of tracking systems due to their relatively high acceptance angles (Reichl et al., 2013).

Lämmle (2018) made a direct comparison between (“the best PVT collectors in the market”) unglazed (from MeyerBurger) and glazed (from EndeF) flat-plate PVT, low concentration (from Solarus) PVT, and a standard PV and ST module, to assess the current state of both thermal and electrical performance of the available PVT collectors.

Figure 4. Comparison of the electrical and thermal efficiency of best of market unglazed, glazed, and low-concentrating PVT collectors. Efficiency related to aperture area (provided by Manuel Lämmle and presented in Lämmle, 2018).

The thermal peak efficiencies range from 48% (for unglazed PVT) up to 53% (for the CPVT). These values fall below the 80% for standard flat plate ST collectors due to simultaneous electrical generation (i.e., the fraction of incident solar radiation is directly converted into electricity), lower absorptance and higher emittance of the receivers (i.e., higher optical (e.g. reflection, transmittance) and geometrical losses), in most cases, a higher thermal resistance between the PV cells and the HTF.

On the other hand, both unglazed and glazed PVT collectors can compete with thin-film PV modules, but not with the high-efficiency mono-Si modules that reach around 22%.

The LCPVT (from Solarus) can reach electrical efficiencies as high as 9.7%, which falls short of the 11.2% that the work developed on this thesis achieved and which is presented in the following chapters. Regarding the thermal efficiency, a thermal efficiency of 56.8% has been achieved, which is roughly +2% higher than the results presented in Figure 4.

Overall and as stated previously, a higher electrical efficiency leads to a lower thermal efficiency, which reinforces the educated “rule of thumb” that PVT collectors can either be optimized for high electrical or thermal performance.

2.9. Fundamentals of Optics in Solar Collectors

The main role and drive of solar energy systems is to convert the sun’s radiation to either electricity (through PV modules) or heat (via thermal collectors). However, the efficiency (i.e., relative low density of the solar flux) of such conversion still requires a thorough development, especially in PV module efficiency.

To meet the energy demands of densely populated zones, ideally the installation of large fields of solar collectors should cover massive areas, which involves the use of a significant amount of materials (e.g. production and installation) and resources (e.g. services). Moreover, it raises questions regarding the economic viability of these systems, and thus initiates the need for an increased sunlight conversion efficiency or a higher input flux. While the first is

subject to intensive research and innovation (e.g., developing new types of PV materials, etc.), the latter option can be accomplished by the addition of cheap mirrors/reflectors to the solar systems, which will concentrate the incoming radiation into an absorber (where the conversion will be done).

The following section presents the concepts behind the engineering of sunlight concentration and discusses the most common and well-developed optical geometries typically used in utility-scale solar collectors.

2.9.1. Concentrator Collector Overview

Solar concentration is achieved by using an optical device (typically a mirror/reflector) between the source of radiation (typically the sun) and the energy-absorbing surface, thus decreasing the effective area of the absorber and associated radiative energy losses at the same absorber temperature as a flat-plate collector.

Solar collectors are devices that can be coupled with reflectors to collect irradiation from a large reflective area to focus onto an absorber (either PV, thermal or a combination of both as PVT), which generates thermal energy at higher temperatures (higher potential value/efficiency) over ranges of wide incidence angles.

On the other hand, it leads to higher stagnation temperatures and worse incidence angle modifier (IAM) profiles, as it increases optical (e.g. reflection, transmittance) and geometrical losses, and the shading effect from the collector box edges. The core disadvantage typically relies on the dependence of direct normal irradiance, therefore, locations with regularly clear skies and high levels of direct radiation are critical for high conversion efficiencies.

Typically, concentrators can be characterized into reflectors (comprising mirrors) or refractors (i.e., lenses), surfaces or cylindrical of revolution, and also continuous or segmented (Duffie and Beckman, 2013). Depending on the type of concentration, concentrating collectors are typically categorized by the employed field technology, high or low concentration.

The low concentration is categorized in three different categories such as booster reflector, compound parabolic concentrator (CPC) and luminescent concentrator.

For high concentration, there are currently four main categories available as is schematically shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Four commonly used high concentration technologies for solar energy that attain high temperatures. Linear concentrators: a) parabolic trough and b) Fresnel reflectors. Punctual concentrators: c) central tower CSP and d) parabolic dish.

Linear concentrators comprise parabolic trough collector and linear Fresnel reflector technologies:

- Parabolic trough collector (Figure 5.a): the relative position between the mirror and the receiver does not change (the geometry remains constant), having single axis tracking system. It concentrates the solar radiation onto a receiver running the length of the trough, where the absorbed solar radiation heats the working fluid (up to 400 °C) that flows inside the receiver.
- Linear Fresnel reflector (Figure 5.b): the mirrors are moved to redirect the sunrays into a fixed linear receiver.

Punctual concentrators comprise the central tower CSP and parabolic dish technologies:

- Central tower CSP (Figure 5.c): the heliostats have two-axis tracking systems to keep the sun's image reflected onto the central point (receiver) that is placed at the top of a tower, which can reach up to 1000 °C.
- Parabolic dish (Figure 5.d): the relative position between the receiver and the mirror does not change during the day. It concentrates the incoming solar radiation to a point (receiver, reaching up to 650 °C), where the heat is transferred to a gas. This system needs a two-axis tracking system to work properly.

2.9.2. Concentration Ratio

Concentration ratio C_i is scientifically known as the ratio between the effective aperture area A_a and the receiver/absorber surface area A_r , which is the factor by which the radiation flux on the energy-absorbing surface is increased.

Moreover, a concentration ratio can also be characterized by its flux intensity, which comprises the flux and a local flux concentration ratio. A flux concentration ratio is commonly described as the average energy flux that strikes the receiver core over a given A_a . The latter can be defined as the ratio of energy flux (over a range of possible positions throughout the entire receiver area).

These ratios can vary over several hundreds of suns (unit that quantifies the concentration factor) and can be defined as follows.

$$C_i = \frac{A_a}{A_r} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

Depending on the concentration employed, this ratio can have an upper limit. This limit has different values if the concentration is either two-dimensional 2D (linear) concentrators (e.g. cylindrical parabolic concentrators) or three-dimensional 3D (circular) concentrators such as paraboloids. This limit, which has been introduced by Rabl (1976a), is based on the second law of thermodynamics applied to radiative heat exchange between sun and receiver.

Considering an ideal concentrator (i.e., free from imperfections), the radiation from the sun is considered as the fraction of emitted radiation that passes over a given aperture. For an ideal optical system, the luminance (i.e., a photometric measure of the luminous intensity per unit area of light travelling in a given direction, which describes the amount of light that passes through, is emitted from, or is reflected from a certain area, and falls within a given incidence angle) at the output is the same as the input luminance.

Assuming (for analysis simplification) that the sun is a perfect blackbody, T_s can be considered as the blackbody temperature (i.e., source, sun).

$$Q_{source \rightarrow receiver} = A_a \cdot \frac{r^2}{R^2} \cdot \sigma \cdot T_{source}^4 \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

Where the sun radius r is at a distance R from the receiver. Theoretically, a receiver with blackbody characteristics radiates energy equal to $A_r \cdot \sigma \cdot T_{receiver}^4$ (Duffie and Beckman, 2013), and a fraction $E_{receiver \rightarrow source}$ reaches the sun as

$$Q_{receiver \rightarrow source} = A_r \cdot \sigma \cdot T_{receiver}^4 \cdot E_{receiver \rightarrow source} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

The maximum temperature T_r can reach is T_s . Then the source and the receiver are in equilibrium. When T_s and T_r are equivalent, the second law of thermodynamics requires $Q_{source \rightarrow receiver}$ to be equal to $Q_{receiver \rightarrow source}$, therefore

$$\frac{A_a}{A_r} = \frac{R^2}{r^2} \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

The maximum value of $E_{receiver \rightarrow source}$ is equal to the unit, which means that the receiver only 'sees the sun'. The maximum concentration ratio for a 3D concentrator is then given by (Duffie and Beckman, 2013),

$$C_i = \frac{R^2}{r^2} = \frac{1}{\sin^2 \theta_s} \quad \text{where } \sin \theta_s = \frac{r}{R} \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

For an incident beam of solar radiation with a half-angular width (which is the maximum angle at which incoming sunlight can be captured by a solar concentrator) of 0.27° , the maximum concentration ratio for a three-dimensional

concentrator is around 45000. This value means that the maximum theoretical temperature allowed can never surpass the temperature of the source, which is 5740 K.

A real passive optical system has its output luminance as *at most* equal to the input luminance. For instance, if a lens is used to form an image that is smaller than the source object, the luminous power is therefore concentrated into a smaller area, thus a higher luminance is generated at the image. The light at the image plane, however, fills a larger solid angle so the luminance comes out to be the same assuming there is no loss at the lens, thus the image can never be “brighter” than the source.

By employing the same principle as for 3D concentrators, the concentration ratio for a 2D concentrator leads to

$$C_i = \frac{1}{\sin \theta_s} \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

Therefore, for an acceptance half-angle of 0.27° , the maximum concentration ratio for a 2D concentrator is of 212.

2.9.3. Non-imaging and Imaging Concentrators⁵

Due to the wide variety of concentrator designs, concentrator collectors are treated as non-imaging collectors for low concentration ratios and linear imaging collectors for higher concentration factors.

Non-imaging concentrators do not produce any optical image of the light source. Alternatively, this design is able to reflect all of the incident radiation into a receiver/absorber either beam or diffused, over a wide range of incidence angles. These systems are not precise since they typically do not require a tracking system; however, their flexibility is advantageous. The most commonly used non-imaging optic technology is identified as compound parabolic concentrator (CPC).

CPC collectors typically have low concentration ratios below 10 suns (i.e., low-temperature applications). However, non-imaging collectors’ flexibility concerning the use of non-beam radiation and more relaxed technical requirements to the positioning of concentrators, allows this technology to reach higher system performances at relatively low cost (i.e., attractive for investment), especially in regions where the solar resource is less than ideal (e.g. clear skies) for concentrating solar systems.

Stationary low concentration factor solar collectors (typically below 10 suns) do not reach temperatures higher than 120°C (Lämmle et al., 2020), as they do not need the use of tracking systems due to their relatively high acceptance angles (Reichl et al., 2013).

Linear imaging concentrators are typically used at high-temperature solar plants, by enabling a very large aperture area in relation to a reduced absorber

⁵ Based on the findings presented in both Duffie and Beckman (2013) and Winston et al. (2005).

area, which efficiently reduces thermal losses at high temperatures. These concentrators produce an optical image of the light source, even if it is usually of very low quality when compared with ordinary optical standards.

Ray-tracing software is a useful tool to thoroughly evaluate and develop concentrating collectors. By employing geometric reflections within a concentrating collector system, the distribution and angles of incidence of radiation on an imaging concentrator absorber can be determined. Imaging concentrators are known for a wider aperture and reduced reflectors when compared with non-imaging systems. The reflected incoming light onto a receiver produces an optical image; therefore, main parameters such as image size (i.e., width) and intensity of radiation have to be considered for precise energy analysis. Typically, the concentration ratio of these concentrators covers a range from 10 to 100 suns.

Parabolic (imaging concentrators) and CPC (non-imaging concentrators) trough solar collectors are currently the most studied (both analytically and experimentally), used, mature and commercially proven technologies (Achhari and El Fadar, 2020). By concentrating, the solar collectors reduce absorber/receiver area, enhancing annual thermal performance by decreasing the heat loss area and by reducing the material cost such as selective surface or PV cells (Lämmle et al., 2016). On the other hand, reflection and mismatching losses, as well as lateral shading on the edge cells (due to the collector box frame) arises, which reduces the electrical performance, particularly when PV cells are connected in series.

Several studies focusing on parabolic or CPC troughs have been presented, yielding high thermal and electrical efficiencies as shown by Bellos and Tziavidis (2019), Valizadeh et al. (2019) and Adam et al. (2019).

2.9.4. Parabolic Reflector Geometry

Parabolic reflector geometries, which are the basic optical systems for CSP technologies such as trough and dish collectors, are considered one of the most (if not the most) mature and commercially proven reflector geometries in the utility-scale CSP (Abbas et al, 2016). Therefore, CSP technologies rely on tracking systems to accurately produce an image of the sun on the surface of the receiver. The receiver must be sized accordingly to the produced sun's image, otherwise, the image will fall out of the receiver boundaries.

Theoretically, a parabola geometry is a curve comprising several points that lie on an equal distance between the directrix⁶ and the focus. The parabola axis intercepts the directrix and the focus, dividing the parabola into two symmetrical parts.

For each point of the parabola, the parallel light beams that strike the parabola aperture will be reflected towards the focal point, which can be also called focal length (Focus, Figure 6).

⁶ Perpendicular line to the axis of symmetry of a parabola and does not touch the parabola.

Figure 6. Profile view of a parabola geometry with the striking parallel rays being reflected towards the focal point.

Considering all sunlight beams as parallel, the ideal position of the receiver is found through the focal point location. Therefore, it is possible to calculate the maximum aperture (x) in function of the reflector height (z) and the focal length (f ; Figure 6).

$$x^2 = 4 \cdot f \cdot z \quad (\text{Eq. 7})$$

Equation 7 shows that the focal distance determines the curvature of the reflective surface of a parabola. Moreover, the height of the parabola of a finite parabola shape is characterized as the rim angle ϕ_r . For an increased ϕ_r (constant aperture), the parabola will be more curved (e.g. deeper reflector height) and f will be closer to the bottom centre of the parabola shape.

Figure 7. Beam reflection in a parabolic reflector geometry (imaging concentrator) for a given aperture a , and both circular and flat receiver shapes.

The receiver size must be designed accordingly with the diameter of the reflected beam at the focal point, hence Figure 7 illustrates the minimum cylindrical and flat receiver size for an incident beam angle of 0.27° .

Moreover, a parabolic (named Pure Parabola) trough geometry, that is further analyzed throughout this dissertation, based on section A (presented in section 2.8.5, Figure 9) has been developed and investigated. It is composed of a parabolic trough (section A) with a central vertical bifacial receiver and it is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Cross-section view of the PP geometry with a longer vertical bifacial (fin) receiver, composed by one full parabola (section A, from point 1 to 4).

The light rays that reach the collector aperture area at a positive angle of incidence will be reflected below the focus, therefore all incoming light with a negative incidence angle will be reflected above the focus, as described by Nilsson (2005).

2.9.5. Symmetrical Reflector Geometry Based on MaReCo Collector Geometry

Several studies on asymmetric concentrating solar collectors have been reported by Rabl (1976), Mills and Giutronich (1978), Welford and Winston (1989) and Tripanagnostopoulos et al. (2000). These studies led to a novel truncated geometry called Maximum Reflector Concentration (MaReCo) and a detailed development procedure of this geometry has been described by Adsten et al. (2005).

The reflector shape was designed with a circular section B (point 1 to 2, Figure 9) next to a bifacial receiver (point 1 to 5) and a parabola from point 2 to point 3 (truncated point, Figure 9). The circular section reflects the light beams directly to the receiver, replacing the receiver (represented by the dotted line) between point 2 and the focus (F , point 5). Figure 9 presents the basic sketch of a MaReCo design, divided into three sections A, B, and C.

Figure 9. Cross-section view of the basic MaReCo design, divided into 3 main sections: A (full parabola, from point 1 to 4), B (circular section, from point 1 to 2) and C (parabola section, from point 2 to 3). Depending on the truncation, the position of the cover glass will vary along the extended parabola. α is the aperture tilt.

This revision addresses, among other geometries, a CPC trough geometry based on section *B* and *C*, presented previously in Figure 9. The selected geometry is composed of a mirror-wise version of sections *B* and *C*, with a central vertical bifacial receiver as a mirror point, as shown in Figure 9. The receiver dimensions were set to fit this geometry (point 1 to 5, Figure 9) and vary in length depending on the applied geometry and concentration factor. Section *B* of the concentrator is composed of a 20° arc of a circle centred on the top edge of the vertical receiver and section *C* by a parabola with a focus on *f*.

Figure 10. Cross-section view of the simulated CPC geometry with a longer vertical bifacial (fin) receiver. The geometry is divided into 2 main sections: B (circular section, from point 1 to 2) and C (parabola section in black, from point 2 to 3).

2.9.6. The Compound Parabolic Concentrator

CPC concentrators (as mentioned previously) are non-imaging concentrators that do not require a tracking system due to the ability to reflect all available incident radiation, both beam and diffuse, into a receiver over a wide range of incidence angles. The boundary limits of these incidence angles are defined as the acceptance angle of a concentrator, where all the incoming incident radia-

tion, both beam and diffuse, that falls within this acceptance angle will be reflected into the receiver. A wide range of acceptance angles increases the attractiveness from the point of view of system simplicity, flexibility and cost-effectiveness of CPC reflector geometries.

It combines two parabolic reflectors, either symmetric or asymmetric, on each side. Each side of the parabola has its focus length (F , focus of the right-hand parabola in Figure 11) at the lower edge of the other parabola, shown in Figure 11. The distance from one end of the receiver to the focal point is given by the point where the parabola will reflect the incoming sunlight when the angle of incidence is lower or equivalent to the acceptance angle. The angle between the axis of the collector and the line connecting the focus of one of the parabolas with the opposite edge of the aperture is called acceptance half-angle θ_c . This angle is characterized by the maximum angle at which the incoming sunlight can be captured by the solar concentrator.

Figure 11. Cross-section of a symmetrical non-truncated CPC.

Typically, an ideal CPC is characterized by parallel surfaces at the upper-end points of both parabolas. The upper limits do not contribute meaningfully towards a higher radiation collection, therefore, the CPC geometry can be truncated with no real expense in performance.

Truncation is applied to increase optical efficiencies (i.e., decreasing the average number of reflections) and energy yields. On the other hand, this leads to higher heat losses per aperture area and thus lowers the amount of unnecessary shading (Carvalho et al., 1985; Adsten et al., 2005).

Moreover, limited truncation does not affect the acceptance half-angle, in contrast to the significant changes in concentration and height-to-aperture ratio, as well as in the average number of reflections (Winston and Hinterberger, 1975). Figure 12 presents the theoretical fraction of incident radiation for a given aperture at an angle θ that hits the absorber as a function of θ .

Figure 12. Acceptance angle function for a full (with and without surface errors) and truncated (with no surface errors) CPC.

Other useful expressions that describe the design of CPC concentrators are shown below in Eq. 8 and 9. The following equations relate the focal length of the side parabola to the acceptance half-angle (θ_c), receiver size (a'), and height of the collector (h), being f the focal length.

$$f = a'(1 + \sin\theta_c) \quad (\text{Eq.8})$$

$$h = \frac{f \cos\theta_c}{\sin^2\theta_c} \quad (\text{Eq.9})$$

These types of concentrators are built for each ray with an angle θ that comes into the CPC aperture with an angle smaller than θ_c to be reflected into the receiver. The ray will be reflected to the atmosphere if the angle θ is greater than θ_c .

2.9.7. The Edge-Ray Principle

For imaging concentrators to fully operate at their fullest potential requires tracking systems, which increases the overall cost of produced energy despite reaching higher temperatures and efficiencies. On the other hand, non-imaging concentrators such as the compound parabolic concentrators (CPC) are a good option to decrease costs and at the same time have some modularity (e.g. for building integration).

The CPC was first described by Winston (1974), which was followed by collaborations at Winston and Hinterberger (1975), and Rabl and Winston (1976). Later on, CPC reflector geometries for solar applications have been refined and presented by Duffie and Beckman (2013).

The development of CPC reflector geometries was based on a method presented in Winston et al. (2005), which was settled from a statement that implies that an imaging optical design derives from Fermat’s principle. Fermat’s principle states that the optical path length between object and image point is the same for all rays (Figure 13.a). By applying this principle to a “string” instead of rays, it gives the *Edge-Ray* algorithm of non-imaging optical designs (Figure 13.b).

Figure 13. Fermat’s principle for rays and strings. a) imaging concentrators; b) non-imaging concentrators.

One way to describe the edge-ray “string” principle, is that one end of a “string” is looped to a “rod” (Figure 14), in which section $A'C$ is characterized by a tilt angle θ and a length equal to the length of aperture section AA' . The opposite top edge end A , has been tied to the opposed bottom end of the edge B' .

To be able to trace out the reflector profile, section A' must be kept in place and section C must be moved away from A . Therefore, through a simple geometry calculation, the relation between sections can be given as

$BB' = AA' \cdot \sin\theta$, which translates the overall schematic of a 2D CPC reflector geometry.

Figure 14. String construction for planar absorbers.

Figure 15 presents a “string” construction for a tubular absorber, typically used for ST concentrators (Winston and Hinterberger, 1975).

Figure 15. “String” construction for tubular absorbers.

Moreover, the *Edge-Ray* principle generalization made in Figure 15 has been further developed in more detail. It has been assumed that all the incoming light that enters the aperture area with an angle θ shall be tangent to the convex absorber surface after one reflection bounce as shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Edge-Ray principle generalization for non-plane receivers.

Furthermore, section ED and EF section of the concentrator presented in Figure 16 are involutes of section EB and EC , respectively.

Following the same assumptions, an ideal concentrator design for a transverse fin absorber (horizontal) can be found and has been presented by Rabl (1976a) and schematized in the following Figure 17.

Figure 17. Ideal concentrator design for a transverse fin absorber.

- Section ED' and ED receive direct illumination, which are involutes of sections EB' and EB , respectively;
- ED' is an arc-circle with center in B' . $D'C'$ is a parabola with focus in B' and axis $D'A'$. $C'A$ is a parabola with focus in B and an axis parallel to $D'A'$;
- $C'A$ and CA' have their focus on B and B' , respectively;
- $C'D'$ and CD have their focus on B' and B , respectively.

The “string” principle allows for the possibility to assess the optimal involute shape for these concentrator collectors, where the center will be placed either on B' or B .

Moreover, this dissertation work, among other works, has developed and studied a truncated ideal concentrator solar collector for both electricity and heat generation (PVT), based on the principles described in section 2.8.7, more specifically from Figure 17.

2.9.8. Ideal Concentrator Design Concept

In this thesis work, an improved reflector geometry for a CPVT solar collector has been developed and presented. The aim was to improve the Solarus PC reflector geometry while having few raw materials, a lower concentration factor and a wider acceptance angle, as the Solarus PC has an asymmetric reflector geometry and is not suitable for lower latitudes that tend to have symmetry in their radiation profiles.

The development of the new reflector geometry followed the optical principles described in sections 2.8.6 and 2.8.7. However, it has been adapted for a bifacial PVT receiver with PV cell strings on both sides. A PVT absorber with eight elliptical flow channels has been selected for both thermal and electrical assessments made in this thesis work. The flow channels increase the heat transfer between the aluminum receiver core and the HTF, increasing in this way the HTF temperature while reducing the PV cell string temperature, which enhances the electrical efficiency.

Moreover, for an arbitrary standard ST absorber, no deviations are necessary. On the other hand, a thicker absorber (e.g. bifacial PVT receiver) entails some rework to the abovementioned optical principles, falling outside of the ideal concentrator tag.

The general form of the design concepts (Figure 18) was created with both circular and parabola sections with their optical axis defining the accepted radiation interval. The developed reflector concepts have been segmented into four main sections A, B, C and D which can vary in size depending on the design concept, employed.

CPC 1

CPC 2

CPC 3

CPC 4

Receiver width: 16.5 cm
 Receiver thickness: 1.45 cm
 Receiver length: 231 cm

Radius of circ.: 8 cm
 Reflector height: 12.8 cm

Aperture: 42.9 cm
 Concentration (bottom): 1.6
 Concentration factor: 1.3

Insulation (cover air) gap: 3.3 cm
 Reflector gap: 2.4 cm

Figure 18. Cross-section view of the general CPC 1, 2, 3 and 4 geometries.

The design concepts were truncated for a collector depth of around 128 ± 2 mm, as it was intended to have a short shadow length.

The radius of both sections A and B (Figure 18) was set to 80 ± 1 mm, slightly bigger than half of a full-size commercial PV cell width of 156 mm. This aims at minimizing the shadow effect, as well as to have the center of the circular section A slightly inside the edge of the PV cell, which was set at 2.5 mm for CPC 1 and 3, and 6 mm for CPC 2 and 4.

The circular sections A and B are set by the acceptance half-angle for a given reflector geometry. Both sections A and B (for all four reflector geometries concepts) have their focal points centered on the bottom edge of the receiver edge (2.5 and 6 mm towards the inside of the receiver). CPC 1 has a circular section A characterized by an arc angle of 90° and a radius of 80 ± 1 mm, while CPC 3 has an arc angle of 71° (section A). On the other hand, CPC 2 has a circular section with a total arc angle of 120° , while geometry CPC 4 has an arc angle of around 101° .

Regarding geometries CPC 3 and 4, a gap between the bottom receiver side and the mid reflector (middle of section A) was set to 24 ± 2 mm. This design allows the light rays to pass through the center of the collector (between the bottom receiver side and reflector) being collected on the opposite side of the bottom receiver, which distributes the light rays more evenly and at the same time reduces the conduction losses between the receiver and the reflector (as happens in both CPC 1 and 2). However, a downside is that this gap also allows some rays to escape (being reflected to the atmosphere), which reduces the optical efficiency at non-normal incidence angles.

A concentration factor on the bottom receiver side (receiver side facing the reflector) of 1.6 has been employed in all four of the geometry concepts. Furthermore, the PV cell string has a length of 2100 mm (comprising 12 full-size PV cells, encapsulated in a silicone gel from Wacker-Elastosil Solar 2205 with

a thickness of 3.5 mm), and a receiver core with a length of 2310 mm, 165 mm of width and thickness (r) of around 14.5 mm.

The receiver placement has a gap between the top of the receiver and the glass of 33 ± 2 mm, which reduces convection losses (Duffie and Beckman, 2013). The collector and reflector length was set to 2310 mm, to cope with the shadow created by the lack of reflector in the longitudinal direction. A low iron solar glass and a PMMA side gable protection with a thickness of 4 mm have been added to the collector design concept.

Table 1 presents a more detailed assessment of the main parameters of each geometry.

Table 1. Summary of the main parameters for each geometry design concept.

	CPC 1	CPC 2	CPC 3	CPC 4
Bottom concentration factor (C_i)		1.6		
Reflector depth (z) [mm]		128 \pm 2		
Receiver dimensions (L/W/T) [mm]		2310/165/14.5		
Aperture [mm]		429 \pm 2		
Cover air gap ⁷ [mm]		33 \pm 2		
Reflector gap ⁸ [mm]	-			24 \pm 2
Radius [mm]		80 \pm 1		
Theoretical acceptance half-angle (θ_c) [°]		30		
Circular section arc-angles [°]	90°	120°	71°	101°

Carvalho et al. (1985) presented the number of bounces for a CPC where acceptance radiation angles from 0° to 90° (which comprises both geometries CPC 1 and 3) have an average number of reflections of around 0.785. On the other hand, for acceptance radiation angles from 0° to 120° (which comprises CPC 2 and 4), the average number of bounces is set between 0.15 and 1.0, for a given concentration factor and specific truncation point.

Moreover, while designing these concentrators, the thickness of the receiver is of most importance since a thicker receiver will create a shading profile (from its width), which ultimately leads to lower performance.

The shadow effect can be minimized by decreasing the depth of the reflector since the distance between the bottom receiver side and the bottom reflector will set the size of the shadow in the bottom solar cells. Furthermore, the relative shadow is set by the size of the PV cell, decreasing the losses in the remaining series-connected PV cells. Section C is characterized by a parabola section that limits the concentration factor as well as the insulation air gap.

⁷ Distance between top receiver side and glass cover.

⁸ Distance between bottom middle receiver side and circular intersections (section A).

2.10. Impact of Shading and Concentration in CPVT Collectors

Non-uniform illumination over a single surface of a solar cell or a series of connected PV cells leads to a decrease in efficiency.

Bunthof et al. (2016) reported lateral shading on the edge PV cells string, as the main cause for decreasing the energy yield of PV arrays. In reality, stationary concentrating solar collectors do not provide a uniform flux distribution, which leads to a disproportionate illumination on a specific area of the solar cell, thus creating higher electrical resistance losses as well as material stress. Moreover, real-life surfaces have optical errors in the reflection (i.e., non-uniformities in the slope of the reflector, or microscopic surface irregularities) which generate non-uniform reflections (i.e., optical errors distorting the reflected image).

Typically, non-uniform illumination profiles are created by positional interferences (such as clouds or buildings), structural issues (low-quality design) and material imperfections. To understand and avoid positional interferences, shading profile calculations were introduced by Rönnelid and Karlsson (1997), where a solar projection angle θ_p has been defined and schematically shown in the following Figure 19.

Figure 19. Solar radiation projection angle θ_p onto a vertical surface with surface normal n .

Pfeiffer and Bihler (1982) conducted a detailed indoor experimental testing, in which two types of non-uniform illumination in solar cells of concentrator systems were identified, such as excessive illumination on some region of the solar cells or a complete shadow effect occurring on one of the solar cells. In the first case, excessive illumination on the solar cells generates high currents, thus increasing the resistivity losses.

On the other hand, in the second case, a complete shadow effect occurring on one of the series-connected cells causes the whole string to stop supplying energy. Usually, solar cells are connected in series in linear concentrators, where the electrical current passing through each cell is assumed the same. In reality, the electric current generated by each cell depends upon the amount of

illumination, being linearly dependent on the incident light (Coventry, 2005). The current in a string of identical solar cells will be limited by the cell with the least illumination (Woyte et al., 2003; Kreft et al., 2021).

Non-uniform radiation arises due to three main reasons: *Structural*, which are related to specific characteristics of the chosen concentrator design (e.g. shape, size and acceptance half-angle); *Errors*, such as flaws in manufacturing processes (e.g. the reflector) or incorrect collector tilt; and *Positional*, such as the relative position between the solar cell and the sun, or the shadows (clouds, buildings, etc.).

PV modules are normally connected in series, where the electrical current generated in each cell is assumed to be identical and proportional to the amount of illumination. The electrical current in a PV cell string will be limited by the cell with the least illumination (Paul et al., 2015) which is often caused by shading from the collectors' box frame or due to a short reflector length (Cabral et al., 2019).

When placed under a concentrating system, solar cells are affected by reflection and mismatching losses, thus reducing the performance. In stationary concentrating solar systems, some portions of the solar cell get more exposure than others, which causes a non-uniform distribution of irradiation. Furthermore, real-life surfaces have optical errors in the reflection (i.e., non-uniformities in the slope of the reflector, or microscopic surface irregularities) which generate non-uniform reflections (i.e., optical errors distorting the reflected image).

Moreover, for a stationary concentrating solar system to be able to work at its full electrical potential (i.e., without shading), it is necessary to guarantee that the reflected image of the PV cells in the reflector stays in the reflector boundaries, to avoid a loss of power. Therefore, shading can be tackled by typically employing longer reflectors. Transversal shading (defined by the aperture area/acceptance angle) impacts a PV cell string in a more uniform pattern, meaning that the losses are fairly proportional to the shaded area.

Furthermore, a detailed assessment of the shading effect on PV solar cells has been developed from reflective geometries presented in section 2.9.

The following assessment was developed through a numerical ray-tracing model software (Tonatiuh) and a multi-paradigm numerical computing environment software (MATLAB), which are described in detail in section 3.2.

The study focused on the shading profile created by the transversal and longitudinal incidence angles on the bottom receiver side (i.e., the side facing the reflector) in which the transversal incidence angle was kept at 0° while the longitudinal was simulated for every 15° (from the normal of the solar collector to the cover glass) for Figure 20 and Figure 22. On the other hand, for Figure 21 and Figure 23 the longitudinal angle was kept at 0° while the transversal was simulated for every 15° (from the normal of the solar collector to the cover glass).

Figures 20 and 21 show the different transversal irradiation profile distribution on the bottom receiver side, for different incidence angles.

Figures 22 and 23 present the longitudinal profile distribution on the bottom receiver side for the highest intensity spot of the receiver, which is the focal line. For the transversal direction, 156 mm is considered the width of the majority of commercial PV cells available. As for the longitudinal direction, the cell string is characterized by a length of 2100 mm (corresponding to 12 PV cells (156 x 156 mm) with a gap of around 21 mm between each PV cell, a standard value for PV manufacturing).

Figure 20 shows that the irradiation distribution (for variable longitudinal and constant transversal incidence angles) has a similar profile in all four design concepts. CPC 3 presents a higher irradiation intensity, reaching focal line intensities of around +40% higher than the ones registered on the focal lines for CPC 1, 2 and 4. Figure 20 also shows that outside the focal lines, CPC 1 varies within smaller ranges, thus having a slightly more homogeneous irradiation profile, which should reduce the thermal stress on the monocrystalline silicon PV cells.

Figure 20. Irradiation profile distribution on the transversal direction for different incidence angles for 4 reflector geometries (i.e., variable longitudinal angle and constant transversal angle).

For constant longitudinal and variable transversal angles, Figure 21 shows that due to the particular central circular section A, CPC 3 has a significant decrease in intensity of the focal line with the increase of the angle of incidence (starting at 15° on the transversal direction), as the reflected light misses the bottom receiver side. This phenomenon does not take place in the remaining CPC 1, 2 or 4 due to the increased section B or closed circular section A, which allows the light rays to be reflected more efficiently into the bottom receiver side.

CPC 1 registers the highest irradiation peak of all geometries, at incident angles of around 30° (transversal direction), since the opposite side of the reflector (facing the sun directly) still can efficiently redirect the light rays towards the bottom receiver side, thus creating a situation that is more likely to form hotspots.

Figure 21. Irradiation profile distribution on the transversal direction for different incidence angles for 4 reflector geometries (i.e., constant longitudinal angle and variable transversal angle).

Figure 22 shows the influence of the longitudinal incidence angles on the shading of PV arrays. The first PV cell of the string is shown (in black) as the first “column bar” in Figure 22. It is possible to confirm that from 30° on the longitudinal direction (Figure 22), a significant drop in irradiation on the first cell string is verified (increasing the thermal stress in the PV cells and significantly reducing the output of the whole array), leading to a loss of current, making CPC 4 the least sensitive to this angle dependence, despite having lower base values. At 60° (longitudinal direction), the first cell almost completely stops working due to no light being reflected into the cell. This leads to the whole

string having a reduced output. As the electrical performance model does not take into account the effect presented in Figure 22 (regarding shading effect on the first cell in the PV array), the overall electrical yield should be affected negatively. However, Figure 22 shows that the design concepts can illuminate the “first” cell for a large range of angles, where the influence of the cosine effect is very significant (lower solar irradiation).

Despite having a similar irradiation profile as the other three geometries (Figure 22), CPC 3 achieves higher irradiation intensities with ratios of around 1.3.

CPC 4 shows better performance regarding shading effect, as the reflector geometry is able to illuminate the first bottom PV cell for a longer time than the remaining studied CPC geometries.

Figure 22. Irradiation profile distribution on the longitudinal direction for different incidence angles for 4 reflector geometries (i.e., variable longitudinal angle and constant transversal angle).

An increased circular section leads to higher concentrations for a transversal angle of 15°, as can be seen in Figure 23 for CPC 2 and 4. CPC 3 is more sensitive to transversal incidence angles, as the other geometries have higher intensities until transversal incidence angles of [45°, 0°], nevertheless, CPC 3 registers the highest radiation peak at [0°, 0°].

Furthermore, the non-uniform illumination on the bottom receiver side is clearly visible in Figure 23, as the high-intensity focal lines are mainly compressed between transversal angles between 0° and 30°, and the minimum values are very close to zero.

The average values are within a reasonable intensity range as the highest value is around 1500 W/m². The two highest intensities were achieved by CPC 3 at [0°, 0°] and CPC 2 at [15°, 0°], both at around 6200 W/m².

Figure 23. Average, minimum and maximum irradiation on the longitudinal direction for different transversal incidence angles for 4 reflector geometries (i.e., constant longitudinal angle and variable transversal angle).

3. Methodology

3.1. Assessment of PVT Solar Collector Technologies

Typically, the performance of a PVT solar collector technology can be assessed by its standardized efficiency parameters (e.g. electrical, thermal and optical efficiency parameters), and by its annual electrical and thermal energy yield (i.e., calculated via ScenoCalc, which is the chosen simulation tool by the certification body Solar Keymark Network to assess the solar collector annual yield for a constant HTF temperature and at a specific location).

Solar Keymark Network and IEC certification bodies, among others, require that the testing procedure guidelines for both flat-plate and PV modules must be followed, respectively. The increased investment in PVT technologies has not been met by the certification bodies, which were not able to develop a methodological and explicit standard for the testing of combined efficiency of PVT solar collectors. This leaves the PVT thermal performance characterization to be tested according to the international standard for ST collectors ISO 9806:2017 and the electrical performance according to IEC standards (Jonas et al., 2019).

The increasing interest in Building Integrated PV (BIPV) and Façade Integrated PV (FIPV), and the developments in heat pump technology are generating several alternative for PVT applications.

Therefore, and to tackle this issue (among others), in 2018, under the management of the International Energy Agency (IEA) Solar Heating and Cooling (SHC) program, a task force composed of several experts in PV, T and PVT technology was initiated under the IEA-SHC Task 60: “Application of PVT collectors.” The IEA-SHC task 60 focuses on the improvement of performance characterization and modelling of PVT collectors and systems (IEA-SHC, 2018).

3.1.1. Electrical Efficiency Parameters

Several IEC standards are available in the market such as the IEC 61853:2011 and IEC 61215:2016 for terrestrial PV modules. As this dissertation addresses concentrating PVT solar collectors, the author selected the standard IEC 62108:2016 which focuses on “Concentrator photovoltaic (CPV) modules and assemblies – Design qualification and type approval” which was considered the most adequate for the electrical testing procedure.

The main electrical parameters can be obtained by a simplified electrical performance model based on the work developed by Lämmle et al. (2017), which is presented in Eq. 10. The model takes into account the instantaneous performance ratio (PR) due to incidence angle losses, being expressed by Eq. 10 for θ greater than zero (Duffie and Beckman, 2013).

$$PR_{IAM} = 1 - b_0 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\cos \theta} - 1 \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 10})$$

For simplicity, the cell temperature $t_{cell, PVT}$ was replaced by the fluid mean temperature t_m due to lack of knowledge regarding the solar cell temperature behavior (in relation with the fluid temperature), thus the temperature dependence of the electrical efficiency is expressed by Eq. 11 (edited from Skoplaki and Palyvos (2009)).

$$PR_T = 1 - \beta \cdot (t_m - t_a) \quad (\text{Eq. 11})$$

However, they can be obtained from flash tests in which the module's electrical output is measured at two different temperatures for a given solar radiation flux. Due to the selected concentration factor, the low irradiance behavior PR_G presented by Heydenreich et al. (2008) was not considered, thus the instantaneous specific electrical power output P_{el} is given by the following Eq. 12 (Lämmle et al., 2017).

$$P_{el} = \eta_{el,STC} \cdot PR_{IAM} \cdot PR_T \cdot G \quad (\text{Eq. 12})$$

where the temperature coefficient of electrical power is expressed by β and the standard panel efficiency by $\eta_{el,STC}$.

3.1.2. Thermal Efficiency Parameters

Currently, ISO 9806:2017 is the most common and complete testing procedure to assess the thermal behavior of any ST collector. The standard allows the solar collector testing to be conducted either in SST conditions or through quasi-dynamic testing (QDT) methods, under natural weather conditions (e.g. outdoor testing procedures).

The thermal quasi-dynamic performance model presented in ISO 9806:2017 (version 6.0 from 2018) takes into account parameters such as dependence on direct and diffuse radiation, mean fluid temperature and incidence angle modifiers. Eq. 13 presents the energy balance equation (in W/m^2) for liquid heating collectors based on ISO 9806:2017.

$$Q_{th} = \eta_{0,b} \cdot (K_{\theta b}(\theta_L, \theta_T) \cdot G_b + K_{\theta d} \cdot G_d) - c_1 \cdot (t_m - t_a) - c_2 \cdot (t_m - t_a)^2 - c_3 \cdot u \cdot (t_m - t_a) + c_4 \cdot (E_L - \sigma \cdot t_a^4) - c_5 \cdot \frac{dt_m}{dt} - c_6 \cdot u \cdot G - c_7 \cdot u \cdot (E_L - \sigma \cdot t_a^4) - c_8 \cdot (t_m - t_a)^4 \quad (\text{Eq. 13})$$

The heat losses are given by the coefficients c_1 and c_2 concerning the difference between mean fluid temperature t_m and the ambient temperature t_a . The coefficient c_5 is the effective thermal capacity, which describes the dependency to the derivate in time of the mean fluid temperature $\frac{dt_m}{dt}$. This parameter has been removed, as the mean temperature is static (SST analysis). Coefficients c_3 , c_4 , c_6 and c_7 for a given glazed concentrator collector concept are set to zero, due

to negligible wind speed dependence (ISO 9806:2017). Coefficient c_8 for concentrator collectors is also set to zero (according to ISO 9806:2017).

Therefore, the thermal efficiency curve for any ST collector can also be written in a more simplified approach. Eq. 14 shows the simplified energy balance equation (in W/m^2) used to estimate the thermal yield.

$$Q_{th} = \eta_{0,b} \cdot (K_{\theta b}(\theta_L, \theta_T) \cdot G_b + K_{\theta d} \cdot G_d) - c_1 \cdot (t_m - t_a) - c_2 \cdot (t_m - t_a)^2 \quad (\text{Eq. 14})$$

PVT solar collectors can apply for the Solar Keymark Network certification with specific guidelines, where the thermal performance is performed with synchronous thermal and electrical generation under maximum power point conditions, as the heat and electricity influence each other.

3.1.3. PVT Efficiency Parameters

There are three different modes that a PVT solar collector can operate, either as a ST collector, a PV module or combining both technologies. The latter has a significant influence on the thermal performance if electricity is being generated simultaneously (i.e., working as a PVT) or not (working as a ST collector) (Hofmann et al., 2010).

In this dissertation, the electrical and thermal operations have been measured individually, as the electrical measurements were retrieved in milliseconds, which does not impact the thermal behavior of the CPVT solar collector under testing. Therefore, both thermal and electrical power are calculated independently from each other.

Solar radiation G (W/m^2) that reaches the module at a solar irradiance will immediately lose a fraction to the ambient as Q_{loss} and the remaining portion empowers the PV module (Q_{el}) with a given electric efficiency η_{el} . The accumulation of solar energy increases the temperature of the PV module and generates the thermal power of Q_{th} , depending on the HTF and module design, which is transferred to the thermal module through a heat transfer mechanism with a specific thermal efficiency η_{th} (Ramos et al., 2019).

Thus, the combined overall efficiency of a PVT solar collector can be defined as the following Eq. 15 (Shakouri et al., 2020).

$$\eta_{PVT} = \frac{Q_{el}}{G \cdot A} + \frac{Q_{th}}{G \cdot A} \quad (\text{Eq. 15})$$

3.1.4. Optical Efficiency Parameters

3.1.4.1. Theoretical Optical Efficiency

Optical efficiency is a key element to the electrical and thermal performance characterization of a CPVT collector, as the system efficiency is set by the optical properties of the cover glazing (transmittance, τ), the reflector material (reflectance, ρ) and the PV solar cell (absorptance, α). In this specific case, the cell absorptance is negligible, as it is the same for a reference system without concentrators and glazing.

Eq. 16, which describes the theoretical optical efficiency for electricity production for the specific design concept, has been refined from the one presented by Brogren et al. (2000), as it does not comprise specific individual influence of global and beam radiation factors for both A_{cell} and $A_{reflector}$, respectively.

$$\eta_{opt} = \frac{\tau \cdot (G_{global} \cdot A_{cell} + G_{beam} \cdot A_{reflector} \cdot \rho)}{A_{aperture} \cdot G_{global}} \quad (\text{Eq. 16})$$

3.1.4.2. Optical Efficiency from I_{sc} Measurements

As the short-circuit current I_{sc} of a PV module is proportional to the irradiance, at a constant temperature, the optical efficiency can thus be calculated from the I_{sc} with corrections for the geometrical concentration ratio C_i , and measured global irradiated intensity G . Eq. 17 presents the correction factors for obtaining the optical efficiency from I_{sc} measurements.

$$\eta_{opt} = \frac{I_{sc, \text{measured}}}{I_{sc, \text{standard module}}} \cdot \frac{G_{src}}{C_i \cdot G} \quad (\text{Eq. 17})$$

3.1.4.3. Optical Efficiency from Thermal Measurements

The average collector output power Q (presented in the following Eq. 18) can be obtained by measuring the solar radiation, flow rate and HTF temperature (Duffie and Beckman, 2013).

$$Q = \rho \cdot V \cdot c_p \cdot (t_{out} - t_{in}) / A_c \quad (\text{Eq. 18})$$

To describe the collector output power P , a simplified model has been applied, in which solar radiation, peak collector efficiency η_0 and the HTF temperature difference is used as input, as can be seen in the following Eq. 19 and simplified in Eq. 20 to access the overall heat loss coefficient U_1 and the optical efficiency from thermal measurements.

$$P = \eta_0 \cdot G - U_1 \cdot \Delta T \quad (\text{Eq. 19})$$

$$\eta = \eta_0 - U_1 \cdot \frac{\Delta T}{G} \quad (\text{Eq. 20})$$

3.1.5. CEPT Solar Collector Simulation Program for Energy Yield Assessment

The CEPT Solar Collector Simulator is an Excel-based simulation tool that allows the calculation of both electrical and thermal annual energy output that was developed by Solarus to assess the annual energy performance of asymmetric reflector geometries.

To guarantee a high level of precision in the simulations, the simulation tool was validated with a minor deviation of around 5 % in comparison with the Solar Collector Energy Output Calculator (ScenoCalc, version v3.10d: SKN 2011), which was developed by the Swedish Research Institute (RISE) and nowadays is available for free from the Solar Keymark Network website. Several weather data sets can be used as input data, such as Davos, Würzburg, Stockholm and Athens. The weather files are supported by hourly (time steps) meteorological data records from Meteonorm (Meteonorm, 2018).

The main basis of CEPT is the assessment of collector energy yields over a constant annual HTF temperature (i.e., theoretical maximum achievable collector yield if a constant annual HTF temperature is applied), which assumes an infinite storage capacity (i.e., any heat gain will be utilized).

3.2. Ray-tracing Simulation Approach

The complexity of optical systems can be mitigated by a suitable simulation tool, typically called ray-tracing simulation tools. Ray-tracing software is employed to compare different optical design options and evaluate the final performance of a given reflector geometry, which in this case are both parabolic and CPC trough solar collectors.

From a wide range of available software (either paid or not), the author focused his optical analysis on performance analysis codes, which were specifically developed for CSP applications and freely available to the community (Tonatiuh). Tonatiuh was chosen due to its widespread use among the CSP community (especially researchers) and its freeware status.

The following chapter describes the working principles of the software, as well as a simplified MATLAB script description, which estimates the optical parameters of the CPC and parabolic reflector shapes.

3.2.1. Ray-tracing Software: Tonatiuh

The large dimensions that characterize concentrating solar collectors, lead to undesirable testing difficulties. This way, theoretical and simulation studies can and should play a major role, since experimental studies are usually costly and time-consuming. To overcome these difficulties, Perers et al. (1994) defined and validated a model that estimates IAMs of large collectors through a ray-tracing software, and simulated its output power. Therefore, for the analysis and design of solar concentrating systems, an MCRT method is employed, where the optical efficiency of each geometry at each angle (both transversal and longitudinal IAM directions) is assessed and plotted.

Tonatiuh is an open-source free-to-use software, created and developed at Centro Nacional de Energías Renovables (CENER), which focuses on the optical design simulation of complex concentrating solar power (CSP) systems. It uses C++ programming language and is based on an MCRT method, providing a friendly and easy-to-use graphical user interface. The software has been experimentally validated by Blanco et al. (2009), through real data measurements from different CSP projects. The software presents some interesting features, such as the possibility to simulate complex systems by using a higher variety of materials, a calculator for irradiation flux distributions, and the capability to import CAD files (Jafrancesco et al., 2018).

Modelling concentrating systems in Tonatiuh requires the inclusion of several nodes and sub-nodes in a tree structure. For that, the software provides several material and node shapes to define the system surfaces. After modelling the system, it is necessary to define the sun by position and shape (either Pillbox or Buie), azimuth and elevation angles. A specified number of rays are launched and traced from the light source into the concentrating system. The ray intersection with the system surface is calculated by the generated light rays from a light source. In cases where the light ray intersects the node bounding box, the intersection is verified with that node sub-node. With this approach, the energy fluxes of interest can be easily computed as a function of the number of photons arriving at the surface, per unit area. The assumption of elastic collisions is implemented, thus each photon transfers its energy to the absorber structure only when it is absorbed (Blanco et al., 2005). Figure 24 presents the ray-tracing simulation steps performed in this study.

Figure 24. Ray-tracing simulation steps.

The analysis made via the ray-tracing software has been conducted assuming pure specular behaviour; nevertheless, the software can be forced to reproduce the pure diffuse behaviour, adjusting the optical error of the surfaces of interest.

To avoid a mismatch between the optical system sections, the different geometries were drawn in CAD software and then imported into Tonatiuh.

Monte Carlo-based methods (such as Tonatiuh) present inherent statistical fluctuations, thus the total power, irradiation flux, standard deviation and computational time presented in Table 2 correspond to the average values obtained from a set of five runs (for each angle of incidence).

Table 2. Relationship between the number of launched rays for normal incidence and average computational time (seconds), standard deviation and average flux (W/m^2), for a set of five runs.

Number of rays	Computational time [secs.]	Standard deviation	Flux [W/m^2]
10^8	220	0.001	946
10^7	25	0.003	947
10^6	3	0.012	949
10^5	2	0.026	945
10^4	1	0.030	917

As expected, the standard deviation and computational time decrease for higher numbers of launched rays (Jafrancesco et al., 2018). Nonetheless, in this study, the direct normal irradiation (DNI) was set at $10^3 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$. The number of rays launched was set at 10^5 for the IAM simulation (time-consuming simulation) and 10^7 for the incidence irradiation flux distribution study. The values presented in Table 2 are for a single incidence angle simulation, but as the IAM simulation requires several sets of incidence angles, the computational time increases significantly when the number of launched rays increases. For this reason, the value was set to 10^5 (with minor penalties of around 1% of accuracy). A Pillbox approximation has been selected with a value for θ_{max} of 4.65 mrad (or 0.27°) since the sun shape varies widely with terrestrial location, sky conditions, and time.

The optical analysis was based on principles of radiation transmission through glazing suggested by Fresnel (presented in Duffie and Beckman, 2013), to account for the unpolarized radiation reflectance and transmittance.

Once the ray-tracing simulations have been performed, the data is extracted by means of a MATLAB script and employed in an electrical and thermal performance model, to evaluate the electrical and thermal annual yield.

For the analysis of the irradiation profile on the bottom side of the PVT receiver, a built-in extension from Tonatiuh has been employed, where the sun position was varied constantly (for both transversal and longitudinal direction), with the number of rays launched to be set at 10^7 rays.

Moreover, the ray-tracing software used for the design and development of the optical systems presented in this dissertation requires a better understanding of both technical and practical limitations of the employed software to accurately assess the performance of the given reflector geometries. Therefore, some limitations were found while the simulations were being performed, such as:

- Tonatiuh simulates the rotation of the “sun” around the collector/or geometry as 360° in the longitudinal and transversal direction. This means

that, if not properly conditioned, software simulates with no difference between day and night, when in reality the collector can only produce during daylight. Due to this difficulty, the sunrise and sunset were set at 6 am to 6 pm, respectively. The sunset and sunrise differ from day to day around 30 minutes throughout the year (e.g. Mogadishu) as it can only store 24 cells (corresponding to 24 hours per day), therefore it was necessary to select by hours, leading to a minor inaccuracy.

- The software has no input for meteorological data, as it only works with beam radiation.
- In order to achieve higher precision, it is required to set the amount of launched rays to as high as possible, on the other hand, this requires more time to compute.
- The software does not take into account the cooling factor of solar cells from the working fluid (PV cell temperature dependence).
- PVT system losses and cell efficiency are not taken into account in Tonatiuh, therefore a MATLAB script has been developed to address these matters.

3.3. CPVT *Experimental* Field Measurement Approach

Experimental outdoor field measurements were conducted on different CPVT solar collectors, to characterize the optical, electrical, and thermal properties of the optical concentrating PVT system.

Both electrical and thermal field performance measurements were conducted at the University of Gävle (HiG) solar laboratory, Sweden.

The electrical parameters have been measured according to the IEC 62108:2007 standard. On the other hand, the thermal parameters were measured following the current standard ISO 9806:2017 (SST method) for ST collectors, by measuring the thermal power at different operating temperature conditions.

To accurately carry out these specific field testing procedures a new thermal test rig (Figure 25) has been designed to cope with the specifications of the Solar Keymark Network standards and an improved electrical measurement system to address the electrical parameters of any type of solar collectors.

Figure 25. Thermal test rig design to cope with the specifications of ISO 9806:2017 testing procedure with an auxiliary pump station.

The thermal rig is able to test, in parallel, under the same circumstances two ST collectors and four PV modules.

Moreover, an improved solar collector stand (Figure 26) has been developed especially for measuring solar collectors with large dimensions (e.g. stationary concentrating PVT solar collectors, which are typically wider and longer than standard PV modules or flat-plate solar collectors).

Figure 26. Improved solar collector stand that allows the measurement of any type of parameters such as incidence angle modifiers for concentrating solar collectors.

The solar collector test stand is critical for the assessment of incidence angle modifier (IAM) field measurements, as it is necessary to constantly change the collector azimuth and tilt if the measurements are not performed inside of the equinox's time frame.

For the development of this dissertation, and due to the specificity of the employed PVT receivers from Solarus Sunpower, the test rig was limited to two troughs (comprising one collector) in parallel, which comprises two receivers, each one with two PV cell strings, thus four PV cell strings in total.

3.3.1. Outdoor IAM Testing Procedure

Hertel et al. (2015) described an IAM as the variance in output performance of a solar collector as the angle of the sun changes in relation to the surface of the collector, with respect to irradiance under normal incidence. The longitudinal and transversal IAM can be obtained through the maximum efficiency, solar irradiation, efficiency at each angle and aperture area.

For both thermal and electrical performance diagrams, the CPVT system is east-west oriented, with fixed collector tilt throughout the day, which was adjusted to ensure that the incidence angle was optimal for Gävle (coordinates: 60.67°N, 17.14°E).

The effective solar height is shown in Figure 27 (i.e., the south projection angle θ_{NS}), which typically sets the optimum collector tilt angle facing south in the northern hemisphere or facing north in the southern hemisphere.

Figure 27. The solar position (vector 1) has been divided into an east-west direction (vector 2) and a north-south vertical P_{NS} plane (vector 3). The south projection angle θ_{NS} is the angle between the projection of the “sun position vector” into a north-south vertical plane and the south horizon. Where θ_z is the solar zenith angle, γ_s the solar azimuth angle (based on Rönnelid and Karlsson, 1997).

For a specific position of the sun (i.e., short time interval Δt), the average beam irradiance G_b can be projected into the north-south vertical plane P_{NS} , as shown in Figure 27.

During the equinoxes, the south projection angle is fairly constant (the sun’s path has a profile movement in an east-west plane) during the day, which will be in the normal plane of a glass cover tilted with an angle equal to the latitude.

The south projection angle has a daily minimum at noon during summertime when it overlaps with the conventional solar height. For the optimal collector tilt angle on a south-facing surface, the collector surface must be tilted with an angle of $(90 - \theta_{NS})^\circ$, therefore, the collector surface is placed with a tilt of $(90 - \theta_{NS})^\circ$ for the selected testing days. The testing procedure is conducted during the equinoxes as the projected solar altitude remains constant (negligible error of around 2°), as can be seen in Figure 32.

Figure 28. South projected angle for the equinoxes and solstices (summer and winter). Location: Gävle (Sweden, Latitude: 60.7° N).

To perform measurements on $IAM_{Transv.}$ (transversal direction), the collector is east-west oriented and tilted with an angle of $(90 - \theta_{NS})^\circ$. By employing this testing procedure, the angle between the collector and the sun can be constantly adjusted so that the longitudinal direction angle is 0° , which decreases the need for any correction factors, as the projected solar altitude will have a profile movement in an east-west plane.

For the longitudinal $IAM_{Long.}$ testing procedure, the previously described $IAM_{Transv.}$ procedure is replicated. However, the collector is placed in a south-north position (rotated 90° from the initial position).

For an optimal measurement of both transversal and longitudinal IAM, the measurements should be performed around the equinox's time frame. During the equinox the south projection angle is fairly constant, which does not require azimuth and tilt adjustments, and thus no correction factors. Therefore, the presented work retrieved measurements for each IAM during the equinox's time frame. This procedure is applicable for solar collector test stands that are not equipped with tracking systems.

3.3.2. Testing Equipment Description for Thermal and Electrical Measurements

Figure 29 shows the experimental schematic setup (technical drawing scheme) that has been used for both electrical and thermal measurements, which measures inlet, outlet and ambient temperature, pressure, flow rate, and global and diffuse solar radiation. A water-cooled hybrid CPVT solar collector has been evaluated, built and installed in the outdoor testing laboratory at Gävle University (Sweden) with a variable south-oriented collector tilt angle (β) depending on the nature of the tests.

The test setup apparatus consists of a solar collector closed loop and a domestic hot water open loop. Furthermore, the solar collector loop relates to the

HTF flowing between the collector and heat exchanger, supplied by a fixed flow rate. A mixture of 80% of pure water and 20% ethylene glycol (with a heat capacity of 2200 J/Kg.K) is used as HTF with an overall heat capacity of 3813 J/Kg.K.

Figure 29. Technical drawing of the hydraulic rig composed of several temperature and pressure sensors, a heat exchanger, a vacuum degasser, expansion vessel, mixing tank (for a more homogeneous temperature), as well as a heater for constant inlet temperature.

The test rig apparatus consists of a hydraulic and electric circuit designed for performance characterization (both electrical and thermal) of any kind of domestic solar collector. For thermal performance characterization, the inlet collector temperature was constant for each measurement period (to access the efficiency), and the outlet collector temperature was measured to characterize the thermal behavior of the collector (presented in sections 4.3 and 4.4).

The closed-loop is composed of the following components:

- Programmable logic controller: All regulation and control are done by an Abelko Webmaster Pro/Ultrabase PLC system, which allows for remote control of the system.
- Automated flow control: The flow is controlled through a proportional-integral-derivative (PID) regulator and a frequency-controlled pump, which allows the user to set the desired flow rate and automatically adjust to any pressure drop.
- Collector inlet temperature control: Incoming hot water from the solar collectors is first cooled by tap water (through a heat exchanger) to a temperature slightly below the desired collector inlet temperature. The water is stored in a 10L tank for buffering and then heated to the desired temperature with a 4.5 kW heater from RELEK Produktion AB.
- Temperature measurement/thermal performance characterization: PT100s are used to measure the inlet and outlet temperatures of thermal collectors,

as well as ambient temperature. The inlet and outlet temperature sensors have been installed against the flow, thus creating turbulence within the pipe, and therefore yield more accurate measurements (Kalogirou, 2014).

- Vacuum degasser: For accurate measurement and results, the circuit must be completely free of air. Therefore, a degasser has been installed as it allows the flow to go through a chamber of lower pressure where air bubbles increase in size and are subsequently removed. Water that is free of air will naturally absorb any incoming air from the circuit and therefore the system eventually will be completely air-free (theoretically), even in places where the flow is too low to physically move trapped air bubbles.
- Insulated stainless steel piping: All piping in the test rig is made out of stainless steel pipes which decreases the pressure drop and reduces significantly the possibility of corrosion (Coker, 2007).

For the electrical performance characterization, an IV tracer (which applies a variable load) is used to measure and plot the IV diagrams.

Furthermore, on the solar loop system, several types of measurement equipment have been installed to measure the system operation, such as KippZonen CMP3 and CMP6 pyranometers to measure the diffuse and global radiation, respectively. Both pyranometers are installed in the same plane as the solar collector, which makes them move together with the solar collector. Furthermore, all sensors, such as ambient and HTF temperature sensors, pyranometers and flowmeters, are connected to a data acquisition system that monitors, records and processes the data through a CR1000 data logger from Campbell Scientific (with time-step record measurements of 30 sec per measurement).

Stagnation temperatures in flat-plate ST collectors often exceed 200 °C, which means it is imperative that the collector materials/structure withstand these temperatures (especially in solar concentrator collectors). Currently, the stagnation temperatures in stationary low concentration PVT collectors are 180 °C, such as the Solarus PC (Solarus, 2018). The high stagnation temperatures of PVT collectors impose new challenges for the employed materials and components, as well as for the design and construction of PVT collectors. Two major causes for failure are observed for PVT collectors as a result of excessive temperatures: thermo-mechanical stress and the exceedance of critical material temperatures (Lämmle et al., 2018). Furthermore, apart from the challenges of high stagnation temperatures that stationary CPVT solar collectors face, the focal line produced by the reflection of solar radiation into the PV cells increases the importance of specific and methodical material selection for these types of solar technologies.

Moreover, the electrical performance of the CPVT collector was characterized according to IEC 62108:2007 and the thermal performance according to ISO 9806:2017 by using the SST testing method.

Additionally, and to comply with the Solar Keymark guidelines for testing PVT collectors (SKN 2015), the thermal performance was measured with synchronous electrical measurements (at maximum power-point). Furthermore, the ISO 9806:2017 standard for the SST method states that concentrating collectors with transparent cover and with concentration ratio C_i lower than 3 suns

are treated as standard glazed collectors and that wind speed dependency can be neglected.

Table 3 shows the test condition limits for the SS methods presented in ISO 9806:2017 and the deviation from the performed testing presented in section 3.3.

Table 3. Test conditions and maximum allowed deviation for SST method, according to the international standard for ST collectors ISO 9806-2017 for thermal measurements. For electrical measurements, the test conditions and maximum allowed deviations are presented according to the IEC 62108:2017 standard.

	SST method ISO 9806:2017			IEC 62108:2007	
	Required value	Allowed deviation	Measured values during testing	Required value	Allowed deviation
Global radiation, G [W/m^2]	> 700	± 50	> 900	> 700	< 2 %
Incidence angle, θ_i [°]	< 20	-	< 7	-	-
Diffuse radiation, G_d/G [%]	< 30	-	< 14	-	-
Mass flow rate, \dot{m} [$\text{kg}/\text{s}\cdot\text{m}^2$]	0.02	$\pm 1\%$	0.03	-	< 1 °C per 5 min.
Inlet temperature, t_m [K]	-	± 0.1	± 0.1	-	-
Ambient temperature, t_a [K]	-	± 1.5	± 1.5	-	< 2 °C per min.

The standard for ST collectors ISO 9806-2017 has been followed apart from the mass flow rate \dot{m} , which has been set to $0.03 \text{ kg}/\text{s}\cdot\text{m}^2$ to achieve a lower ΔT (between T_{out} and T_{in}).

The solar collector test facility is composed of a hydraulic and electric circuit designed for domestic solar collector thermal and electrical performance characterization. For both electrical and thermal performance characterization, several types of testing measurement equipment have been used, such as two KippZonen (CMP3 for diffuse and CMP6 for global radiation) pyranometers (installed in the same plane as the solar collector), IV tracer, ambient and HTF temperature sensors, and flowmeters.

Table 4 presents both the thermal and electrical measurement equipment accuracy.

Table 4. Thermal and electrical measurement equipment and respective accuracy deviation according to manufacturer datasheets.

		Value	Deviation
<i>Thermal measurement equipment</i>	Flow rate \dot{m} [L/m]	0.5-10	± 1.5 %
	Temperature interval ΔT [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	0-90	± 0.04 %
	Pressure interval ΔP [Bar]	< 6	± 1.5 %
	Heater [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	10-90	± 0.04 %
	Pressure transmitter [Bar]	6	± 1 %
<i>Electrical measurement equipment</i>	Pyranometer CMP3 [W/m^2]	< 2000	± 1.5 %
	Pyranometer CMP6 [W/m^2]	< 2000	± 1 %
	IV Tracer [I] [V]	-	0.1 %

The testing equipment is connected to a CR1000 data logger from Campbell Scientific that monitors, records and processes the data with time-step measurements of 30 sec. All the measurements were then treated as 10-minute average data to compress and increase data accuracy.

4. Results and Discussion

Chapter 4 has been divided into 5 sections, in which section 4.1 and 4.2 relate to the reflector geometry development in a Monte Carlo ray-tracing (MCRTM) software with the support of a MATLAB script. Incidence angle modifiers have been assessed to assist the energy yield simulation tool, to determine the best overall symmetrical reflector geometry.

Moreover, in sections 4.3 and 4.4, two CPVT solar collectors have been built after the design development made in both Papers I and II (sections 4.1 and 4.2, respectively). Additionally, section 4.5 was developed to present the improvements made to the CPC solar collector presented in section 4.4 (Paper IV).

4.1. Paper I

Knowledge about the angular distribution of the annual solar radiation is required for the design stage of concentrating reflector geometries for solar collector technologies. Therefore, each reflective geometry shape has been drawn independently, thus ensuring a good connection between the elements. This way, a mismatch is avoided, as it is imperative to have a perfect connection between the different collector elements, to collect all the launched rays.

Perers (1993, 1997) and Rönnelid et al. (1996) defined different testing procedures based on a quasi-dynamic testing methodology for conventional solar collectors.

A symmetrically truncated PP reflector geometry (PP 1 and PP 2, Figure 30). The vertical receiver has a thickness of 5 mm and a width of 30 or 56 mm. Both receiver and reflector are 2310 mm long. The reflector height varied between 31 and 75 mm.

Figure 30. Cross-section view of PP geometries (with respective parameters). Left: PP 1 geometry; Right: PP 2 geometry.

A symmetrically truncated CPC reflector geometry (CPC 3 and CPC 4, Figure 31) composed of a circular section with an arc angle of 20° (each side), complemented by a truncated parabola section. The receiver dimensions, reflector height and length are in line with the ones presented above for the PP geometry.

Figure 31. Cross-section view of CPC geometries (with respective parameters), divided into 2 sections: B (circular mirror) and C (parabolic mirror). Left: CPC 3 geometry; Right: CPC 4 geometry.

The optical analysis was carried out based on the assumption that the reflecting surfaces are non-ideal and free from fabrication errors. Additionally, a thorough analysis of the different geometries was established in the following section 3. Table 5 presents a more detailed assessment regarding the main parameters of each geometry.

Table 5. Summary of the main parameters for each simulated geometry.

Geometry	Concentration factor (C_i)	Reflector height (z) [mm]	Receiver height (h) [mm]	Focal length (f) [mm]	Acceptance half-angle (θ_c) [°]
PP 1	1.6	75	56	27	-
PP 2		31	30	19	-
CPC 3	1.6	75	56	48	63
CPC 4		31	30	25	83

To assess the electrical IAMs, the selected reflector Almedco Vega SP195 has a spectral reflectivity in the visible range of $\rho = 92\%$, to cope with the spectral response of a silicon solar cell for wavelengths from 0.38 to around $0.78 \mu\text{m}$. On the other hand, for the assessment of thermal IAMs, the Almedco Vega SP195 reflector has a total solar reflectance of around 95% (including ultraviolet, visible and infrared wavelengths).

To carry out the analysis and design of solar concentrating systems, an MCRMTM was employed, where the efficiency of each geometry at each angle (IAM) has been assessed.

Moreover, a script has been developed and optimized, which comprises several lines of code to extract the data relative to the transversal and longitudinal IAM. The data was then fed into a multi-paradigm numerical computing software (MATLAB) to get the IAMs. Then, the IAMs have been employed in a thermal and electrical performance model described in section 3.1.5, to evaluate the annual electrical and thermal yield.

4.1.1. Incidence Angle Modifier Assessment

Incidence angle modifier (IAM) is known as the variance in output performance of a solar collector as the angle of the sun changes in relation to the surface of the collector, with respect to irradiance under normal incidence

(Hertel et al., 2015). The longitudinal and transversal IAM can be obtained through the maximum efficiency, solar irradiation, efficiency at each angle and aperture area.

This section presents an analysis of the results obtained for the transversal and longitudinal radiation IAM. Figures 32 to 35 show both transversal and longitudinal IAM (normalized for normal incidence) for each reflector geometry.

The international standard ISO 9806:2013 for ST collector testing methods states that the normal incidence (equal to zero) is usually used to define the incidence angles, however, other values can be used if applicable.

Both PP 1 and PP 2 geometries reached a peak efficiency of 90%. On the other hand, the CPC 3 geometry reached a peak efficiency of 74% or 6%_{rel} below the highest efficiency value of CPC 4.

For a concentration factor of 1.6, the PP 1 geometry achieved a peak efficiency of 18%_{rel} higher than the one obtained for the CPC 3. Additionally, the PP 2 geometry reached a value 12%_{rel} higher than the efficiency obtained for the CPC 4.

A higher receiver will allow the collector to collect more sunlight directly into the receiver before the reflector starts to work, thus working like a PV module until the sun rays reach the acceptance incidence angle. On the other hand, the height of the receiver shadows the receiver side that is not facing the sun, leading to only one side of the receiver working until the sunlight hits the opposite reflector. Nevertheless, a higher receiver will allow the geometry to collect the sunlight, both directly and through reflections.

As expected, the whole set of simulated concept geometries have symmetrical IAMs, in both transversal and longitudinal directions. The longitudinal direction has a constant profile throughout the different simulations, as expected.

Regarding the transversal IAMs, acceptance half-angles between 46° and 83° characterize the CPC geometries. Note that regardless of the geometry or the receiver height, the acceptance half-angle does not change since the focal point is fixed and sets the acceptance half-angle.

Figure 32. Normalized IAM for normal incidence (PP 1 geometry). Left: Longitudinal IAM; Right: Transversal IAM.

Figure 33. Normalized IAM for normal incidence (PP 2 geometry). Left: Longitudinal IAM; Right: Transversal IAM.

Figure 34. Normalized IAM for normal incidence (CPC 3 geometry). Left: Longitudinal IAM; Right: Transversal IAM.

Figure 35. Normalized IAM for normal incidence (CPC 4 geometry). Left: Longitudinal IAM; Right: Transversal IAM.

As can be seen in Figures 32 to 35 the transversal IAMs do not “start” or “end” at the acceptance half-angles. This phenomenon occurs due to the receiver being longer than the focal length, thus increasing the collected solar irradiance. This phenomenon is presented by Collares-Pereira et al. (1978), where it shows the increased solar irradiance that reached the absorber outside of the acceptance-half angle.

4.1.2. Electrical and Thermal Energy Yield Assessment

The evaluation of the thermal level of heating energy was focused on heating energy for DHW/SFH, for temperatures between $T_{in} = 40\text{ °C}$ and $T_{out} = 65\text{ °C}$. The concentration factor is an indicator of energy yield, which can be used to assess the performance of C-PVT collectors (since lower concentration factors lead to lower optical (e.g. reflection, transmittance) and geometrical losses,

thus higher energy yields). The energy yields of the investigated C-PVT collectors vary between 460 and 528 kWh/m²/year depending on the employed geometry.

Figure 36. Annual specific electrical (bottom, blue) and thermal (top, red) energy yield for a DHW/SFH system.

For an arbitrary mean fluid temperature of 53 °C, the CPC geometry achieved higher annual energy yields than the PP geometry, despite having lower peak efficiencies. Nevertheless, it should be noted that the geometry with the highest annual energy yield has the lowest half-acceptance angle (presented in Figures 32 and 33) of all of the simulated geometries and thus leading to lower overall annual energy yields.

The PP 2 geometry achieved an annual specific yield of 460 kWh/m² or 13%_{rel} below the yield obtained for CPC 4. A specific annual yield of 467 kWh/m²/year was achieved for PP 1, being 8.5%_{rel} below the highest energy yield for CPC 3.

In addition, the annually received energy profile of the simulated geometries (daily average power) is in line with the average seasonal variation of the daily extraterrestrial solar radiation for horizontal surfaces.

4.2. Paper II

The design concepts were truncated for a collector depth of around 128 mm, with the general form of the design concepts (Figure 18) being created with both circular and parabola sections with their optical axis defining the accepted radiation interval. The reflector consists of three sections A, B and C, which can vary in size depending on the design concept employed. The radius of both sections A and B (Figure 18) was set to 80 mm, slightly bigger than half of a full-size commercial PV cell width of 156 mm. This aims at minimizing the

shadow effect, as well as to have the center of the circular section A slightly inside the edge of the PV cell. The shadow effect can be minimized by decreasing the depth of the reflector since the distance between the bottom receiver side and the bottom reflector will set the size of the shadow in the bottom solar cells.

Furthermore, the relative shadow is set by the size of the PV cell, decreasing the losses in the remaining series-connected PV cells. Section C is characterized by a parabola section that limits the concentration factor as well as the insulation air gap.

A concentration factor on the bottom receiver side (receiver side facing the reflector) of 1.6 has been employed in all four of the geometry concepts, to have a very similar concentration factor as the LCPVT collector tested by Koronaki and Nitsas (2018).

Furthermore, the PV cell string (presented in Figure 37) has a length of 2100 mm (comprising 12 full-size PV cells, encapsulated in a silicone gel from Wacker-Elastosil Solar 2205 with a thickness of 3.5 mm), and a receiver core with a length of 2310 mm, 165 mm of width and thickness (r) of around 14.5 mm.

Figure 37. Bifacial PVT receiver used in the ray-tracing simulations.

The receiver placement has been kept constant with a gap between the top of the receiver and the glass of 33 mm (Figure 18). This gap has been implemented to reduce convection losses (Duffie and Beckman, 2013). The collector and reflector length was set to 2310 mm, to cope with the shadow created by the lack of reflector in the longitudinal direction, as can be seen in section 4.3. A low-iron solar glass and a PMMA side gable protection with a thickness of 4 mm have been added to the collector design concept.

4.2.1. Incidence Angle Modifier Assessment

This section presents an analysis of the results obtained for the transversal and longitudinal IAM for the reflector geometries presented in section 2.8.8 (Figure 18). Figures 38 to 41 show both transversal and longitudinal IAM for both the top and bottom receiver side (for a reflector depth z of 128 mm and a receiver thickness r of 14.5 mm).

As the main difference between geometries lies in the transversal direction, this evaluation focuses on the transversal IAMs. CPC 1 and 2 reached +7%_{rel} and +2%_{rel} higher optical efficiencies than CPC 3 and 4 reflector geometries, respectively. The transversal IAM for the bottom receiver side is clearly better for CPC 1 and CPC 2 as it has a closed circular section A which does not allow the rays to pass through and exit on the opposite side. Furthermore, the IAMs for the bottom receiver side of CPC 3 and CPC 4 have a higher decrease at lower incidence angles in comparison with CPC 1 and CPC 2.

The transversal IAM for CPC 2 is slightly better than for CPC 1 from 16° to 25°, nonetheless, CPC 2 displays a very steep decrease from 25° to 30°. This difference between CPC 1 and CPC 2 should be due to the inclusion of section B in CPC 2, which allows CPC 2 to have a more even transversal IAM on the bottom receiver side, for lower incidence angles (until 25°). This explanation is supported by the observation that both CPC 2 and CPC 4 register a significant drop in efficiency at 25°, even if CPC 2 appears to be more efficient than CPC 4 at lower incidence angles. When comparing CPC 2 and CPC 4 it is possible to visualize that CPC 2 appears to be more efficient at lower incidence angles than CPC 4, even though both register a significant drop in efficiency at around 25°.

For the top receiver side, it is expected that transversal IAMs for these geometries would be similar to the longitudinal IAMs since the top receiver side works as a normal flat PV module. As the receiver is placed 33 mm below the glass cover level, the IAM factor increases around 25° and 40°, due to the combination between direct light and the reflected light by the top reflector section (top part of section C). The IAM factor will increase differently from geometry to geometry, as the difference lies in section B.

Generally, the transversal IAM shapes obtained for the bottom receiver side are in line with the general transversal IAM for a CPC solar collector, resembling the one presented by Rabl (1976b).

As expected, the longitudinal IAMs for both receiver sides follow the typical pattern for solar collectors, as they have a constant decrease from lower incidence angles (closer to the normal of the solar collector) to higher incidence angles, due to the cosine effect.

Figure 38. CPC 1 normalized longitudinal (solid line) and transversal (dashed line) IAM.

Figure 39. CPC 2 normalized longitudinal (solid line) and transversal (dashed line) IAM.

Figure 40. CPC 3 normalized longitudinal (solid line) and transversal (dashed line) IAM.

Figure 41. CPC 4 normalized longitudinal (solid line) and transversal (dashed line) IAM.

The closed section A shows to be an advantage at low incidence solar angles (where the highest solar irradiation is achieved). This shows that section A in CPC 3 and 4 partially allows the light rays to pass under the receiver, both to be collected on the opposite edge of the bottom receiver side, as well as to allow some of the rays to escape to the exterior (at lower angles). This fact can be seen in both Figure 40 and Figure 41, where the transversal IAM (for the bottom receiver side) is very sensitive to the higher receiver placement, allowing some light to pass under the receiver and be reflected to the exterior. For all CPCs, the longitudinal profile is very similar for top and bottom. However, the top shows a considerably better transversal IAM than the bottom.

4.2.2. Electrical and Thermal Energy Yield Assessment

The evaluation focused on the thermal level of heating DHW for single-family houses (SFH) in Cairo (Egypt), for a range of temperatures between $T_{in} = 40$ °C and $T_{out} = 65$ °C. Several tilts have been simulated and the highest annual energy yield output has been obtained for a 25° tilt, which, as expected, is slightly below the 29° of latitude for Cairo (Egypt).

Annual energy yields between 420 and 452 kWh/m²/year were achieved (for a reflector depth of 128 mm and a receiver thickness of 14.5 mm), depending on the design concept. This means a variation of 32 kWh/m²/year or around +8% in the annual energy yield between the design concepts, which represents a significant improvement.

CPC 1 and 2 achieved annual specific yields of 452 and 451 kWh/m²/year, respectively, or around +3%_{rel} above the annual total yield obtained for CPC 3. On the other hand, CPC 4 achieved 7%_{rel} below the highest energy yield obtained for the given design concepts.

Generally, CPC 3 and 4 achieved lower annual total yields, showing that the gap between the reflector (section A) and the bottom of the receiver does lead to a reduction in output. However, it is important to point out that the benefit from an increase in light uniformity over the receiver is not accounted in these simulations, due to the lack of literature to estimate the performance decrease associated with the increase of the non-uniformity of light in PV cells. Additionally, the increased circular section B demonstrated no significant contribution to improve the annual energy yield. Since it is neutral from an output perspective, the likely criteria for including section B in the design should be ease of manufacturing/product cost. A potential manufacturer of this design could select either design from an output perspective.

The values of the electric annual yield can be partially explained by the high operating temperature range of the system, as the electric side of the collector is sensitive to high mean temperature fluids, as the temperature coefficient of electrical power β was 0.4%/K. To increase the electrical annual yield, lower operating temperatures should be applied. Another relevant point is that the data shows that the variation in electrical output of the four designs above is around 2% while the thermal output varies by 11%, showing that the electrical output is less sensitive than the thermal output since the study does not take into account the partial shading on the PV array. This effect is expected to influence the results as the annual electrical yield is expected to vary more than the thermal yield.

Furthermore, a parallel study has been conducted, where a full detailed assessment of the electrical and thermal yields is presented in Table 6, assessing the influence of the reflector depth in the overall annual energy total yield. For this study, the reflector depth (z) has been increased from the previous 128 mm to 256 mm, with a receiver thickness r of 14.5 mm, where the annual energy yields significantly increased, for CPC 2 and 4, enhancing the annual energy yields by +4 and +7%, respectively. CPC 1 had an increment of around +2%, whereas CPC 3 increased by +3%.

Winston and Hinterberger (1975), Rabl (1976a), Collares-Pereira et al. (1978), Rabl et al. (1980), and Carvalho et al. (1985) based their studies on reflective geometries with thin thermal receivers. PVT technologies require thicker receivers, thus it is necessary to reconsider the previous studies done for pure thermal collectors.

Due to this reason, an analysis regarding the thickness of the PVT receiver has been done, where higher annual energy yields of 1.6%_{rel.}, 3.2%_{rel.}, 1.9%_{rel.}, and 3.1%_{rel.}, for CPC 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively, have been achieved (for z of 128 mm and r of 1 mm). For a reflector geometry with a depth (z) of 256 mm and a receiver thickness (r) of 1 mm, CPC 2 did not register any change in energy yield (when compared with z of 256 mm and r of 14.5 mm), whereas the other design concepts registered growth between 4 and 14 kWh/m²/year. Generally, a thinner receiver can increase the overall annual energy yield from +1% up to +4%, depending on the employed reflector height.

Table 6. Summary of the annual thermal (kWh_{th}/m²/year) and electrical (kWh_{elect}/m²/year) energy yield results obtained for a DHW/SFH system, for different design configurations.

		z (128 mm) r (14.5 mm)	z (128 mm) r (1 mm)	z (256 mm) r (14.5 mm)	z (256 mm) r (1 mm)
CPC 1	Thermal yield	304	308	308	311
	Electrical yield	148	152	153	154
CPC 2	Thermal yield	299	311	311	314
	Electrical yield	152	154	156	154
CPC 3	Thermal yield	293	299	303	316
	Electrical yield	148	150	152	153
CPC 4	Thermal yield	274	285	298	311
	Electrical yield	146	148	150	154

A thicker receiver will create a bigger shading on the bottom receiver side, which means a decrease in the operating time of the reflector since the reflector will stop working sooner. For this reason, it is beneficial to have a receiver as thin as possible to maximize the reflector working hours (i.e., higher amount of direct radiation reaching the bottom receiver side).

Furthermore, a deeper collector shows that the increment verified for the thermal yield will be higher than the one registered for the electrical yield.

4.3. Paper III

A wedge PVT receiver shape has been designed to accommodate 24 quarter-size monocrystalline PV cells connected in series (hand-soldered), on each receiver side. The receiver has been placed 41 mm above the center section of the parabolic reflector geometry and makes an angle of 20° between the two receiver copper plates. The solar collector trough is characterized by an aperture of 323 mm and a parabolic reflector depth of 144 mm, as shown in the following Figure 42.

Figure 42. Cross-section (with dimensions in millimeters and degrees) view of the parabolic trough solar collector with a wedge PVT receiver.

The tilt angle that each receiver copper plate has (10° from the normal), aims at increasing (in the transversal direction) the amount of radiation received directly onto the PV cells and also to lower the electrical peak power to which the solar cells are exposed at normal incidence. For simplicity, each side of the PVT receiver has been named “receiver side 1-bottom and 2-top” for south or north orientation, respectively.

Cabral et al. (2019) showed that the longitudinal incident radiation has the biggest impact on the performance of LCPVT solar collectors, therefore, the design concept collector box has been limited to 170 by 2440 mm. Both receiver copper plates are connected by a 12 mm diameter black copper pipe with a wall thickness of 1 mm, where the HTF flows. The receiver has an outer width of 82 mm (inner width of 80 mm) and a length of 2000 mm, where a silicone gel from Wacker (Elastosil Solar 2205) with a thermal conductivity of $0.2 \text{ W/m } ^\circ\text{C}$ and light transmittance of around 97% has been used to encapsulate the PV cells. Additionally, a reflector plate (Almeco Vega 295SP) with 92% of reflectance has been selected. Moreover, the main characteristics of the PV cells from Big Sun Energy are presented in the following Table 7.

Table 7. Summary of the main parameters that characterize the PV cells.

Efficiency [%]	P_{mpp} [W]	V_{mpp} [V]	I_{mpp} [A]	V_{oc} [V]	I_{sc} [A]	Dimension [mm]
20.1	1.1	0.5	2.2	0.6	2.4	78x78

Furthermore, a low-iron solar glass (from Scheuten Glas) and a PMMA side gable protection with a thickness of 4 mm has been selected. The main parameters that characterize both side gables and the collector glass cover are presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Summary of the main parameters that characterize the low iron solar glass and the PMMA side gables.

	Cover, Solar glass	Gable, PMMA
Emissivity [%]	84	94
Thickness [mm]	4	4
Thermal conductivity [W/m.°C]	1	0.2
Transmittance ⁹ [%]	91 [+/- 0.5]	92 [+/- 1]

The nominal electrical peak power per square meter of aperture (for a module temperature of 25 °C at normal incidence) is around 80 $W_{p,el}$ for a concentration ratio (C_i) of 2.

Furthermore, the CPVT thermal peak power per square meter of aperture (while electricity is generated at $[(\Delta T/2)-T_{amb}]/I_{tot} = 0$ °C.m²/W) is 503 $W_{p,th}$. Each trough is characterized by an effective area of around 0.79 m² and the main characteristics of the receiver and reflector geometry are presented in the following Table 9.

Table 9. Summary of the main parameters of the receiver and reflector geometry design concept.

Geometry	Parabola
Concentration factor (C_i)	2
Reflector depth [mm]	144
Receiver dimensions (L/W/T) [mm]	2000/82/3.4
Air gap ¹⁰ [mm]	22
Gap ¹¹ [mm]	41
Receiver tilt angle [°]	10
Aperture [mm]	323

4.3.1. Daily Electrical Diagrams

Two days, one at the end of July and another in August, have been selected to provide a better understanding of the daily performance of the LCPVT solar collector for the two troughs (1-bottom and 2-top) and receiver sides (1 and 2), as well as the importance of the collector tilt angle in the overall performance of the CPVT solar collector. Therefore, Figure 43 presents a profile view of

⁹ Reference to ISO 9050. Restricted to wavelengths from 0.3 to 1.2 μ m.

¹⁰ Distance between top receiver side and glass cover, aiming to reduce convection losses (Duffie and Beckman, 2013).

¹¹ Distance between bottom receiver side and reflector plate.

the wedge PVT receiver in regards to the solar radiation incidence angle for a collector tilt of 42° for the 28th July (A) and the 27th August (B) at noon.

Figure 43. Solar radiation incidence angle for a collector tilt of 42° for the 28th of July (A) and the 27th of August (B) at noon.

As the solar altitude varies throughout the year, it was intended to study the electrical performance of the collector at different solar altitudes and therefore to have a displacement between the theoretical optimum collector tilt angle (i.e., projected solar altitude) and the actual solar collector tilt angle of 42° . Both days registered very similar solar radiation patterns, therefore, only the radiation pattern on the 28th of July is presented. Both global and diffuse solar radiation have been collected between 7:40 am and 4:55 pm and have been presented in the following Figure 44.

Figure 44. Global and diffuse radiation pattern for a typical clear sky day on the 28th of July. The pyranometers are south oriented and placed in the collector plane of 42° , between 7:40 am and 4:55 pm.

As the flow rate, HTF and ambient temperature influence the thermal and electrical efficiency, it is important to follow and understand their pattern. The flow

was set to a mean value of 3.4 L/min (time-step of 10 minutes) for July and is shown in Figure 45.

Figure 45. Outlet and inlet HTF temperatures (left Y-axis), and ambient temperature (right Y-axis) registered for trough 1 and 2 in a clear sky day on the 28th of July, for a collector tilt of 42° and a mean flow rate of 3.4 L/min (time-step of 10 minutes).

In the morning and afternoon, the ΔT is lower than 1 °C. On the other hand, as the ambient temperature and solar radiation rise, the ΔT also rises to around 2 °C, between 11 am and 3 pm. Furthermore, the inlet and outlet HTF temperature presented in Figure 45 displays a similar pattern from trough 1 to trough 2, which shows a good agreement between both troughs.

Figure 46 shows the instantaneous electrical power per unit of area registered for receiver sides 1 and 2 on a clear sky day on the 28th of July, with a mean flow rate of 3.4 L/min for a collector tilt angle of 42°.

Figure 46. Electrical power registered for receiver side 1-bottom and 2 (both troughs 1-bottom and 2-top) in a clear sky day on the 28th of July, for a collector tilt of 42° and a mean flow rate of 3.4 L/min and a temperature of around 54 °C.

The electrical power pattern presented in Figure 46 for receiver side 1 (trough 1-bottom) is in agreement with Figure 44, as the projected solar altitude is higher in the mornings/afternoon and lower at midday, thus a higher output during midday and lower output in the morning/afternoon. The sun will not see the bottom absorber during morning and afternoon due to the specific orientation of the receiver side 1-bottom (trough 1-bottom). From the electrical power pattern of receiver side 1-bottom (trough 1-bottom), it is also possible to acknowledge that the collector was not fully south-oriented as the peak power-point is not located at around 12:23 pm (as in Figure 44) but 12:08 pm. We can assume that the collector had a minor deviation of around 3° towards the east, as one hour typically compresses 15°.

On the other hand, this misalignment can be explained by a possible mismatch between the collector and the pyranometers' orientation. The electrical power pattern for receiver side 1-bottom follows the solar radiation pattern, due to the tilted receiver side of 10°, which helps to get a similar pattern as the one presented in Figure 44, reaching an electrical peak power of around 47 W/m². Due to the misalignment, the electrical power pattern for receiver side 2-top (for trough 1 and 2) will have only one electrical peak power in the afternoon (around 3:22 pm), and not two as expected (morning and afternoon). Additionally, both receiver side 2 (for trough 1 and 2) reached an electrical peak power of around 48 W/m².

A time interval between 9:24 am and 4:24 pm on a clear sky day on the 27th of August has been selected for a mean flow rate of 2.5 L/min (time-step of 10 minutes). Figure 47 presents the ambient, inlet and outlet (HTF) temperature patterns for this day.

Figure 47. Outlet and inlet temperature (time-step of 10 minutes, mean values) registered for trough 1 and 2 on a clear sky day on the 27th of August, for a collector tilt of 42° and a mean flow rate of 2.5 L/min.

The collector ΔT progressively increases from 0.5 °C to a maximum ΔT of 2.2 °C, from 9:24 am until 2:04 pm, where it slightly decreases. Additionally, Figure 48 shows the electrical power registered for receiver side 1 and 2 (both troughs 1 and 2) for a mean flow rate of 2.5 L/min and a collector tilt angle of 42°.

Figure 48. Electrical power register registered for receiver side 1-bottom and receiver side 2 (both troughs 1-bottom and 2-top) a clear sky day on the 27th of August (from 10:15 am and 2:53 pm), for a collector tilt of 42° and a mean flow rate of 2.5 L/min.

To maximize the annual electrical yield, it is important to adjust the collector tilt, which for this case should have been 52° (i.e., the optimal collector tilt angle is given by $90^\circ - \theta_{NS}^\circ$, with $\theta_{NS} = 38^\circ$ at noon), if the electrical peak power was the goal. However, the goal of this test intended to study the influence of the solar altitude on the electrical peak power.

Figure 48 shows a higher electrical peak power for receiver side 1-bottom (trough 1-bottom) since the angle between the receiver and the collector normal is of 10°, which allows receiver side 1-bottom to get direct radiation from the sun while having lower optical (e.g. reflection, transmittance) and geometrical losses, thus a peak power of 72 W/m² (35%_{rel} higher than in Figure 46). Moreover, the lower HTF temperature allows the monocrystalline Si solar cells to have higher efficiencies, thus a higher electrical peak power.

Concerning receiver side 2 (both trough 1-bottom and 2-top), it can be seen that the electrical peak power is fairly low and constant up to around 2:45 pm, where it increases to around 35 W/m² (27%_{rel} lower than in Figure 45). The difference between Figure 46 and Figure 48 lies on a lower solar altitude for August, which favors the receiver side 1-bottom.

4.3.2. Electrical Peak Efficiency

One of the most important parameters in a CPVT solar collector is the real electrical efficiency, therefore, Figure 49 presents the experimental electrical efficiency (per aperture area) for trough 1.

Figure 49. Experimental electrical efficiency per module temperature¹² for trough 1.

Figure 49 shows an electrical peak efficiency (i.e., nominal efficiency) for trough 1 of 8% ($R^2=0.996$) at 25 °C and 4.8% at 57 °C. This means a decrease of around 1.25%/°C, which is higher than expected as the silicon solar cells have an average temperature coefficient of around 0.4%/°C. The temperature has been monitored at the HTF level. PV cells have a higher temperature than the HTF and this difference is expected to be higher at 25 °C than at 57 °C since more heat is transferred from the PV cell to the HTF at 25 °C. As the temperature measurements were done at the HTF level and since the electrical efficiency is dependent on the cell temperature, a higher nominal efficiency is expected since the electrical peak efficiency presented previously is for an HTF temperature of 25 °C and not for a PV cell temperature of 25 °C.

Moreover, the monocrystalline solar cell temperature and illumination can be non-uniform, especially due to the “focal line” created by the reflector, which enhances this phenomenon. The highest temperature spot (commonly known as “hot spot”) on the PV cell will set the voltage and efficiency. Furthermore, a possible misalignment in the receiver placement, the PV cell string being hand-soldered (i.e., lower cell efficiency) and due to a portion of the light being reflected to the receiver backside contributes to lower efficiencies.

Additionally, by having only one receiver side electrically operational (leading to higher temperatures), trough 2-top reached an electrical peak efficiency -4.0%_{rel} lower than trough 1-bottom.

4.3.3. Optical Efficiency from I_{sc} Measurements

At high irradiation (around noon) on a clear day, it was possible to measure the short circuit current $I_{sc}=2.7$ A and solar irradiance $G=916$ W/m². As the full-size c-Si cell has been cut into four quarters and then series-connected, it is

¹² The module temperature is taken as the HTF fluid temperature since the cell temperature has not been measured.

expected to have a lower short circuit current. The manufacturer states that the I_{sc} is 9.6 A, at standard test condition STC (where G is 1000 W/m² for a temperature of 25 °C and an air mass of 1.5).

Moreover, the following Table 10 presents the measured optical efficiency according to Eq. (18) and the theoretical optical efficiency from I_{sc} measurements for different incidence angles according to Eq. (19).

Table 10. Measured optical efficiency per angle of incidence between 11:50 am and 2:30 pm.

Angle of incidence [°]	Theoretical opt. efficiency [%]	Measured opt. efficiency [%]
0 [+/- 1]	72	63
5 [+/- 1]	71	61
10 [+/- 1]	70	60
15 [+/- 1]	69	59
20 [+/- 1]	67	58
25 [+/- 1]	64	56
30 [+/- 1]	61	55
35 [+/- 1]	57	53
40 [+/- 1]	53	51

The presented measured optical efficiency (at 0° with a value of 63%) for normal incidence differs around -12 %_{rel} from the theoretical optical efficiency (at normal incidence), which can be explained by losses in the hand soldering of the PV cells as well as optical imperfections in the reflector geometry (i.e., optical losses).

4.3.4. Optical Efficiency from Thermal Measurements

The optical efficiency from thermal measurements is dependent on the geometry, transmittance of the glazing, reflectance of the reflector and absorptance of the PV cells. Figure 50 shows the measured instantaneous daily thermal efficiency, relative to the global radiation for two similar troughs, for time-steps of 10 minutes.

Figure 50. Instantaneous thermal efficiency diagram of the CPVT hybrid system from thermal measurements for a collector tilt of 42° . The collector is south oriented and placed in the east-west direction, between 8:24 am and 4:44 pm for an HTF temperature of 56°C on the 27th of August.

The misalignment displayed in Figure 50 (from trough 1 with $\eta_{max}= 45\%$ and 2 with $\eta_{max}= 48\%$) can be explained since the cable from receiver side 1 (trough 2) was unattached from the PV cell string and no electric power was generated. This will lead to higher thermal efficiencies. The measurements were taken for an HTF overall temperature of 56°C , which increases the losses. On the other hand, as no electric power is generated the thermal production will be higher.

The effective projected solar height determines the optimum tilt angle of a surface facing south for the given time of the year, which is illustrated in Figure 28. The effective solar height for the 27th of August is fairly constant between 11:44 am and 1:44 pm, which explains the fairly constant thermal efficiency around noon, in Figure 50.

Additionally, from the instantaneous thermal efficiency diagrams with a fairly constant irradiation pattern (between 850 and 982 W/m^2), it is possible to attain the thermal optical efficiency diagram from experimental data, which is presented in the following Figure 51, for both troughs 1 and 2.

Figure 51. Experimental efficiency for trough 1-bottom (solid blue line) and 2-top (dashed orange line).

From the slope of the linear regression diagram shown in Figure 51, it is possible to extract the first-order heat loss coefficient U_l ($\text{W}/\text{m}^2 \cdot ^\circ\text{C}$), which reached values of 4.1 and 4.0 $\text{W}/\text{m}^2 \cdot ^\circ\text{C}$ ($R^2 = 0.996$) for both trough 1-bottom and 2-top, respectively. Moreover, a thermal optical efficiency of 58.3% has been achieved for through 1-bottom, which leads to a thermal peak efficiency of around 50.3% if electricity is being produced. Additionally, a thermal optical efficiency of 59.9% (i.e., thermal peak efficiency of 52.2% if electricity is generated) is achieved for trough 2-top. As previously stated, only receiver side 2 is electrically operational, therefore it is comprehensible that trough 2-top achieved a slightly higher optical efficiency of around +2.7%_{rel} than trough 1.

4.3.5. Electrical Incidence Angle Modifier

This section presents an analysis of the results obtained for the longitudinal and transversal electrical IAM, where the testing procedure has been described in section 3.3.1.

The electrical IAM has been obtained from the incidence angle, global irradiation (W/m^2) during clear weather and electrical power per unit of area (W/m^2). Figure 52 presents the normalized experimental electrical IAM for the longitudinal direction.

Figure 52. Normalized experimental electrical IAM (combined receiver side 1-bottom and 2-top, from trough 1-bottom), longitudinal direction.

Furthermore, Figure 53 presents the normalized experimental electrical transversal IAM diagram for both receiver sides 1-bottom and 2-top (trough 1-bottom). It has a maximum deviation of 9.2% between both receiver sides and it can be explained due to a possible misalignment of the PVT receiver, which automatically leads to a minor deviation.

Figure 53. Normalized experimental electrical IAM (receiver side 1-bottom, 2-top and the combined trough 1-bottom) in the transversal direction.

As expected, the transversal IAM is more sensitive than the longitudinal IAM, which can be explained due to the narrow acceptance angle of around 10° (outside of which the drop in efficiency is more pronounced). Additionally, Figure 53 also shows that the electrical peak efficiency is not reached at normal incidence (typically at 0°), as in a standard flat PVT module, but between $5\text{-}10^\circ$

due to the tilt angle between the two receiver sides. This shows that around 8% is lost at normal incidence due to the large angle of incidence at the absorber.

Furthermore, the findings presented in this section are in line with the study presented by Koronaki and Nitsas (2018) which states that low-concentrator solar collectors are highly sensitive to high incident angles.

4.4. Paper IV

Two reflector geometry concepts, CPC 2 and 4, presented in section 2.8.8 (Figure 18) have been selected for further analysis. CPC 2 and 4 are further named CPC 1 and 2 and are based on the CPC geometry, coupled with a bifacial PVT receiver from Solarus.

First, an ideal CPC reflector geometry concept has been adjusted to have a detachment between the horizontal aluminum PVT absorber and where the reflector material is introduced. Secondly, an ideal CPC reflector geometry with a gap between the horizontal PVT receiver (comprising cooling fluid channels inside the aluminum core of the PVT absorber) and the reflector geometry is presented. Both design concepts are based on and a follow-up of the reference work made by Cabral et al. (2019).

CPC Reflector Design

The general form of the design concept (presented in Figure 54) was based on an ideal CPC geometry (ideal for flat absorbers), which is composed of circular and parabola sections with their optical axis defining the accepted radiation interval.

Figure 54. CPC 2 geometry cross-section view. Circular section A and B comprise an 80 mm radius and an insulation air gap of 33 mm (Cabral et al., 2019).

For both geometries, the reflector section can be divided into three main sections A, B and C, and their main parameters are described in Table 11. The main difference between CPC 2 and CPC 1 lies in a gap of 24 mm in section A (Figure 55).

Figure 55. CPC 1 geometry cross-section view, which comprises a 71° circular section A, a 30° circular section B and a parabola section C. An insulation air gap of 33 mm and a gap between the bottom middle receiver side and circular intersections (section A) of 24 mm are also schematized (Cabral et al., 2019).

A reflector from Almeco (Solar Vega SP295f) with a spectral reflectivity in the visible range of $\rho = 95\%$, a specular reflectance of $\geq 91\%$ and a total solar reflectance of 92% has been selected. The receiver has a length of around 2350 mm.

An insulation air gap of around 33 mm between the PV cells and glass cover has been added on both CPC geometries to reduce convection losses. Table 11 presents a more detailed assessment of the main parameters of each geometry.

Table 11. Summary of the main parameters for each geometry design concept.

Geometry	CPC 1	CPC 2
Bottom concentration factor (C_{i_bottom})	1.6	
Overall concentration factor (C_i)	1.3	
Reflector length [mm]	2350	
Reflector depth [mm]	128	
Air gap ¹³ [mm]	33	
Gap ¹⁴ [mm]	24	-
Radius [mm]	80	
Theoretical acceptance half-angle (θ_c) [°]	30	
Circular section arc-angles [°]	101	120
Aperture area [m ²]	1.07	
Gross area [m ²]	1.15	

Solarus PowerCollector Geometry

As previously stated, the goal of this paper is to introduce a refined CPC geometry for a PVT technology that can outperform the Solarus PC (Figure 56), which is based on the asymmetric roof-integrated Maximum Reflector Concentration (MaReCo) geometry presented in Adsten et al. (2005).

¹³ Distance between top receiver side and glass cover.

¹⁴ Distance between the bottom receiver side and the mid reflector (middle of section A).

Figure 56. General cross-section view of the Solarus collector with a MaReCo geometry (optical axis of 90° from the cover glass).

The irradiation from low solar altitudes during the winter time is very low during this period. This results in a relatively narrow annual irradiation distribution in the north south plane, meaning that a CPC-collector with a small acceptance angle can be designed. This is the basics behind the MaReCo design which has a small acceptance angle, a long bottom edge reflector for summer irradiation and a short over edge reflector for winter irradiation. The Solarus PC has no over edge reflector at all, which has been not adapted for low latitudes where the radiation is high throughout the year. Moreover, an improved reflector geometry is imperative to increase the market share of concentrating PVT solar collectors.

Collector Materials and Bifacial PVT Description

Both design concepts as well as the Solarus PC use the same bifacial PVT absorber design with identical PV cell technology and dimensions. The Solarus Sunpower bifacial PVT receiver has a receiver core with 2310 mm of length, a width of 165 mm and a thickness of 14.5 mm (Figure 57).

Figure 57. CPVT collector comprising two geometries (CPC 1 and 2) with identical PVT receivers (PV cell string configuration of 8-11-11-8 PV cells).

The cell string layout has a length of 2100 mm which comprises 38 one-third-size PV cells (to lower the amount of current in each cell) divided into four sub-strings (each one with one diode) of 8-11-11-8 PV cells. The PV cells are encapsulated in a silicone gel from Wacker-Elastosil Solar 2205 with a total thickness of 3.5 mm (Figure 58), with a reported thermal conductivity of 0.2 W/m.K and light transmittance of 97%.

Figure 58. Solarus bifacial PVT receiver: (1) receiver end cap; (2) PVT receiver; (3) 1st layer of Wacker-Elastosil Solar 2205; (4) monocrystalline PV cell string (8-11-11-8 connected in series); (5) 2nd layer of Wacker-Elastosil Solar 2205; (6) aluminum receiver end; (7) flow restrictor and (8) aluminum receiver core.

The PVT absorber has eight elliptical channels to increase the heat transfer between the aluminum receiver core and the HTF, increasing in this way the HTF temperature and thereby enhancing the electrical efficiency. The selected PV cells from Lightway Solar are characterized by an electrical efficiency of 20.1% and the main cell characteristics are presented in Table 12.

Table 12. Summary of the main parameters that characterize the one-third PV cells.

Efficiency [%]	P_{mpp} [W]	V_{mpp} [V]	I_{mpp} [A]	V_{oc} [V]	I_{sc} [A]	Temperature coefficient [%/°C]
20.1	1.57	0.53	2.96	0.63	3.13	-0.37

The electrical power output of PV modules can be improved by employing smaller sized silicon solar cells as this can effectively reduce the series resistance loss due to lower cell-to-module losses (Haedrich et al., 2014). Additionally, by having one-third-size PV cells, the theoretical maximum output power P_{mpp} and short-circuit current I_{sc} should be equal to one-third of the corresponding full-size cells, whereas the open-circuit voltage V_{oc} should remain the same.

Furthermore, a low-iron solar glass (from Scheuten Glas) and a Plexiglas side gable protection with a thickness of 4 mm has been added to the collector design concept.

It is important to note that the PVT receiver, the solar glass cover and the reflector material are the same materials used in the Solarus PC and have been donated by Solarus Sunpower. This way the differences are only in the reflector geometry which will lead to more accurate results when comparing both geometry designs.

Moreover, the developed work performed in both CPC reflector geometry solar collectors allowed a decrease of -15% in gross area and -38% in the total solar collector height, which leads to a direct cost reduction.

4.4.1. Daily Electrical Power

For both thermal and electrical performance testing procedures, the hybrid CPVT solar collector has been east-west oriented, with different collector tilts set by the south projected angle for a given day. This tilt was however adjusted to ensure that the incidence angle was optimal for Gävle (Sweden: 60.7°N, 17.1°E) at midday, as can be seen in Figure 59.

Figure 59. CPVT solar collector test apparatus (orientation: east-west direction) for different testing procedures with both pyranometers for global (KippZonen CMP6) and diffuse (KippZonen CMP3) radiation measurement.

The electrical performance of the CPVT collector was characterized according to IEC 62108 (2007) while the thermal performance was characterized according to ISO 9806:2017 (by SST testing methods). The glazed PVT collectors are not classified as wind and infrared-sensitive collectors (WISC). Therefore,

the additional thermal losses due to wind convection and infrared radiation are not considered.

The following section presents different sets of results, such as electrical instantaneous peak power, optical efficiency from I_{sc} and thermal measurements, day and dark first-order heat losses, and both transversal and longitudinal electrical IAM diagrams. Figure 60 presents the placement of both geometries CPC 1 and 2 in the test stand.

Figure 60. Schematic of the two different troughs (1 and 2) and receiver sides (1 and 2).

A clear sky day in June has been selected to provide a better understanding of the daily electrical performance profile of the CPVT solar collector for both CPC 1 and 2 receiver sides (bottom and top).

The data has been collected for the whole day of the 25th of June for a collector tilt of 38° and a constant HTF temperature of 24 °C is presented in the following Figure 61.

Figure 61. Electrical power registered for the bottom receiver side of CPC 1 and 2, and top receiver side for CPC 1 on a clear sky day on the 25th of June.

The ambient temperature reached as high as 32 °C. As expected, the CPC 1 top receiver side presents a typical pattern for a flat PV module, as it follows the solar radiation pattern reaching an electrical peak power of 48 W. The bottom receiver side from CPC 2 showed a slight increment of around +1.7 % when compared to CPC 1.

Furthermore, the pattern for both bottom receiver sides follow the solar radiation profile until 10:30 am and after 3 pm, which is explained by the bypass diode operation which shuts down one sub-string. From 10:30 am to 3 pm, which comprises roughly one-quarter of the total measured electrical power, the PVT system was able to operate at its maximum power as the diode is no longer operating (since no significant side shading *is* registered), thus increasing significantly the electrical peak power during mid-day. This phenomenon can be seen by analysing the V_{mpp} of the bottom receiver side where an increase of 6 V was registered, from 15 V up to 21 V, at 10:30 am and a decrease within the same voltage at 3 pm.

Additionally, two different days have been selected to study the influence of the cooling system on the overall performance of the PV cells. For a solar radiation of 800 W/m², an ambient temperature of 15 °C and a PV cell temperature of around 53 °C, the electrical power increased 34 % after the cooling inlet temperature of 24 °C has been employed.

On the other hand, for radiation levels of around 1000 W/m², an ambient temperature of 25 °C and a PV cell temperature of around 85 °C the electrical power increased 53 % by adding an HTF inlet temperature of 34 °C to the system.

4.4.2. Electrical Peak Efficiency

By using active cooling and a new reflector geometry the performance of the PV cells is expected to improve, thus increasing the electrical peak efficiency. Therefore, Figure 62 shows the electrical peak efficiency diagram as a function of the module temperature for both CPC 1 and 2, where the influence of the HTF and ambient temperature in the electrical peak efficiency is registered.

Figure 62. Electrical efficiency trendline diagram per gross area of CPC 1 (solid orange line) and CPC 2 (dashed blue line).

An electrical peak efficiency of 10.6% ($R^2 = 0.999$) has been achieved for both CPC 1 and 2 for a module temperature of 25 °C. Figure 62 also shows a very steady electrical peak efficiency for higher temperatures, which gives a temperature dependence coefficient of around 0.47%/°C. Additionally, the temperature has been monitored at the HTF level, which is lower than the PV cell temperature.

A lower nominal efficiency is to be expected since the electrical peak efficiency is dependent on the cell temperature and the measurements were made at an HTF temperature of 25 °C and not for a PV cell temperature of 25 °C.

The electrical peak efficiency of CPC 1 and 2 showed an improvement of around 17%_{CPC1} and 16%_{CPC2} when compared with the Solarus PC.

After assembly, it is expected that the overall solar collector efficiency drops below the theoretical peak efficiency of a unique solar cell. This phenomenon can be explained due to reflection and absorption losses, as well as manufacturing tolerances (distance between cells) that lead to non-producing “dead” areas. Furthermore, the connections between cells introduce resistance losses and although all the cells are theoretically batched together into power bands, the cells are not perfectly matched and therefore the electrical peak performance of a cell string connected in series will be set by the lowest-performing cell.

By employing the following Eq. (21), it is possible to address the electrical efficiency of different PVT technologies available in the market by taking into

account the temperature coefficient of electrical power β , the standard panel efficiency $\eta_{el,STC}$ and the HTF temperature.

$$\eta_{col} = \eta_{el,STC} \cdot [1 - \beta \cdot (t_m - t_a)] \quad (\text{Eq. 21})$$

Therefore, a comprehensive theoretical comparison (based on Eq. 23) between several PVT technologies brands (e.g. DualSun, EndeF and Solarus PC) and the low concentrating CPC 1 has been performed and presented in Figure 63.

Figure 63. Comparison of the electrical efficiency of an arbitrary unglazed (e.g. DualSun), glazed (e.g. EndeF) and low-concentrating (e.g. both Solarus PC and CPC 1 reflector geometry developed in this dissertation) PVT collectors, and a PV module. Efficiency related to the gross area. The size of the coloured squares shows the lower and higher electrical efficiency range, which corresponds to the higher and lower temperature, respectively.

4.4.3. Optical Efficiency from I_{sc} Measurements

From the IAM testing procedure, the I_{sc} has been recorded and the optical efficiency has been calculated, as the irradiance on the PV cells is proportional to the I_{sc} . From Eq. (1) the theoretical optical efficiency has been calculated as a function of the transverse incidence angles from 0° (normal incidence) up to 40° . Fig. 13 presents the results from the measured and theoretical optical efficiency for the given transversal angle of incidence, which gives a theoretical optical efficiencies of 82 % at normal incidence.

Figure 64. Measured and theoretical optical efficiency as a function of transverse incidence angle calculated from measured I_{sc} current, for both CPC 1 and 2.

It is possible to visualize in Figure 64 that the measured efficiency (calculated from measurements) decreases with the increment of the incident angles. Up to the acceptance angle, which is 30° (where an abrupt decrease in efficiency is registered), the measured optical efficiencies have a fairly slow decrease in relation with the theoretical optical efficiency pattern. For incident angles higher than the acceptance angle the differences increase due to reflector imperfections (i.e., manufacturing problems and material scattering) and therefore imprecise reflections.

Furthermore, due to the fact that for different incidence angles the focal line shifts across the PVT receiver, the series resistance is not the same for all incidence angles as the busbars placed in the extremities of the cells will carry most of the generated electric current.

Moreover, the steep decrease presented between 20° and 30° for CPC 1 might be explained by the gap of 24 mm in section A, which will allow a portion of the reflected rays to miss the absorber, and therefore to lower the overall efficiency. Additionally, the thickness of the PVT receiver has an impact on the measured acceptance-angle, which led to a lower measured acceptance-angle.

Below the specific IV curves are presented at normal incidence for both bottom (Figure 65) and top receiver side of geometry CPC 1 and 2.

Figure 65. IV curve at normal incidence (0° with normal of the solar collector) for the bottom receiver side of geometry CPC 1 (top image) and CPC 2 (bottom image) at 1015 W/m^2 .

CPC 1 and 2 reached a P_{mpp} of 60 and 62 W (bottom receiver side), while their I_{sc} reached 3.4 and 3.5 A, respectively.

On the other hand, the top receiver side has a similar profile and electrical outputs as presented in the following Figure 66.

Figure 66. IV curve at normal incidence (0° with normal of the solar collector) for the top receiver side at 1015 W/m^2 .

A P_{mpp} of around 50 W and an I_{sc} of around 2.8 A have been registered for the top receiver side of both geometries, as it is not dependent on the geometry.

Figure 67. IV curve at 5° from normal incidence (transversal direction) for the bottom receiver side of geometry CPC 1 (top image) and CPC 2 (bottom image) at 1000 W/m^2 .

A transversal angle of incidence of 5° leads to a P_{mpp} of 58 and 60 W, and to an I_{sc} of 3.3 and 3.4 A for both CPC 1 and 2, respectively.

Figure 68. IV curve at 10° from normal incidence (transversal direction) for the bottom receiver side of geometry CPC 1 (top image) and CPC 2 (bottom image) at 983 W/m^2 .

A transversal angle of incidence of 10° leads to a P_{mpp} of 54 and 56 W, and to an I_{sc} of around 3 and 3.1 A for both CPC 1 and 2, respectively.

Figure 69. IV curve at 15° from normal incidence (transversal direction) for the bottom receiver side of geometry CPC 1 (top image) and CPC 2 (bottom image) at 953 W/m^2 .

A transversal angle of incidence of 15° leads to a P_{mpp} of 53 and 54 W, and to an I_{sc} of 3 A for both CPC 1 and 2, respectively.

Additionally, Figure 70 and 71 present the IV curve at 20° and 25° , respectively, from normal incidence (transversal direction) for the bottom receiver side, where it is possible to see the impact of the acceptance-angle in the PV cell string electrical performance.

Figure 70. IV curve at 20° from normal incidence (transversal direction) for the bottom receiver side of geometry CPC 1 (top image) and CPC 2 (bottom image) at 934 W/m^2 .

A transversal angle of incidence of 20° leads to a P_{mpp} of 44 and 46 W, and to an I_{sc} of around 2.6 and 2.7 A for both CPC 1 and 2, respectively.

Figure 71. IV curve at 25° from normal incidence (transversal direction) for the bottom receiver side of geometry CPC 1 (top image) and CPC 2 (bottom image) at 903 W/m^2 .

At 25° from normal incidence (transversal direction), the P_{mpp} further decreases to 31 and 27 W, and to an I_{sc} of 1.8 and 1.6 A for both CPC 1 and 2, respectively.

Figure 72. IV curve at 30° from normal incidence (transversal direction) for the bottom receiver side of geometry CPC 1 (top image) and CPC 2 (bottom image) at 865 W/m^2 .

A transversal angle of incidence of 30° leads to a P_{mpp} of 22 W and to an I_{sc} of 1.3 A for both CPC 1 and 2.

Figure 73. IV curve at 35° from normal incidence (transversal direction) for the bottom receiver side of geometry CPC 1 (top image) and CPC 2 (bottom image) at 831 W/m².

A P_{mpp} of 20 W and an I_{sc} of 1.2 A, for both CPC 1 and 2, has been achieved at a transversal angle of incidence of 35°.

At 25° (Figures 70 and 71), the I_{sc} drops around -45% as the reflector is no longer able to efficiently reflect the beam radiation. Nevertheless, the decrease in the I_{sc} is sharper in CPC 2 than in CPC 1, possibly due to the section A opening below the bottom receiver side in CPC 1.

4.4.4. Optical Efficiency and Heat Loss Coefficient

The main parameter of interest in a ST collector is the optical efficiency η_0 and the first order heat loss coefficient U_l , which have been plotted in the following Figure 74, as a function of both HTF and ambient temperature.

Figure 74. Experimental overall efficiency per gross area for CPC 1 (solid orange line) and CPC 2 (dashed blue line).

From the diagram shown in Figure 74 the heat loss coefficient U_l , reached 5.0 W/m².K for CPC 1. Regarding the optical efficiency η_0 , a value of 62.3% (divided in 51.7%_{th} and 10.6%_{elect}, $R^2 = 0.997$) has been obtained per gross area.

Furthermore, the heat loss coefficient U_l (W/m².K) for CPC 2 (which is given by the slope of the dashed blue line in Figure 74) reached 5.4 W/m².K. Regarding the optical efficiency, a value of 61.8% (divided in 51.2%_{th} and 10.6%_{elect}, $R^2 = 0.995$) has been obtained per gross area for CPC 2.

The measured efficiencies are considerably lower than the theoretical efficiencies in Figure 64, which can be explained by enhanced optical errors while building the collector, dead areas (e.g. space that is not actively contributing to the energy production) and effective reflectance (e.g. amount of bounces that are required for the light rays to reach the receiver).

Additionally, during night time, the dark U-value for each CPC geometry has been drawn, which is presented in the following Figure 75.

Figure 75. Experimental first order heat loss coefficient (dark U-value) per aperture area for CPC 1 (solid orange line) and CPC 2 (dashed blue line).

The HTF outlet temperature determines the quality of energy from the second law of the thermodynamic point of view (exergy), while primary energy saving determines the amount of the thermal and electrical power cogeneration of the collector from the first law of thermodynamics point of view (energy).

From the diagram shown in Figure 75, a dark U-value of 3.5 and 4.7 $W/m^2.K$ ($R^2=0.999$) has been obtained for both CPC 1 and 2, respectively. As expected, the dark U-value is lower than the U-value obtained from Figure 74. The differences between the heat loss coefficient from CPC 1 and 2 can be explained by the higher conduction losses between the bottom receiver side and the reflector material (section A). Typically, the dark U-value is lower than the day U-value as during darkness the HTF liquid is warmer than the fin absorber (e.g. lower ΔT between the fin and the ambient), thus decreasing the heat losses (i.e., dark U-value < U-value).

On the other hand, during illumination, the fin absorber is warmer than the HTF liquid (e.g. bigger ΔT between the fin and the ambient), which leads to higher heat losses (i.e., U-value > dark U-value). Additionally, it is important to state that for a very low Δt ($T_{col} - T_{amb}$) the uncertainty of the measurement increases, nevertheless, it is a good base point to compare both geometries as they have been tested simultaneously.

Overall, the CPC 1 geometry reached a higher optical efficiency (+0.5 %_{rel}) and at the same time a lower day heat loss coefficient of around -8%_{rel} (-0.4 $W/m^2.K$) than CPC 2. The Solarus PC optical efficiency (per gross area) is around 61.4% (divided in 52.3%_{th} + 9.1%_{elect}), which is 5.6% and 4.7% lower than CPC 1 and 2, respectively. Furthermore, the Solarus PC has a lower day U-value of 3.5 $W/m^2.K$ (Solarus, 2018) due to the higher concentration ratio.

Additionally, the difference between the theoretical and the measured optical efficiency lies in the incidence angle and on the silicone gel transmittance losses, which will be magnified for high incidence angles, where the difference between the theoretical and measured optical efficiency from I_{sc} measurements is higher.

A comprehensive comparison (based on Eq. 23) between several PVT technologies brands (e.g. DualSun, EndeF and Solarus) and an arbitrary flat-plate ST collectors (e.g. Schüco) has been done and presented in Figure 76.

Figure 76. Comparison of the thermal efficiency arbitrary unglazed (e.g. DualSun), glazed (e.g. EndeF) and low-concentrating (e.g. both Solarus PC and CPC 1 reflector geometry developed in this dissertation) PVT collectors, and flat-plate ST collectors. Efficiency related to the gross area, at 1000 W/m^2 .

By improving the insulation, the stagnation temperature of CPC 1 can be increases from $77 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to around $85 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which leads to higher energy yields at higher temperatures as the ones required by Domestic Hot Water (DHW) applications. The stagnation temperature of a solar collector is typically reached when the solar collector is not cooled. One way to decrease the problems that occur while operating the collector at high temperatures is to reduce the HTF temperature and thus reduce the absorber temperature. Moreover, façade integration allows solar collectors to effectively match the solar irradiance in the collector plane to the heat demand for winter, thus reduce the maximum irradiance.

4.4.5. Electrical Incidence Angle Modifier

From the test method described in section 3.3.1 for both transversal and longitudinal electrical IAM, the following section presents an analysis of the results obtained for the electrical $IAM_{Long.}$ and $IAM_{Transv.}$. The IAM factor has been acquired by the relation between several parameters, such as the angle of incidence, global irradiation and electrical power. Figure 77 presents the outdoor testing for both CPC geometries, as well as for the Solarus PC.

Figure 77. Normalized experimental electrical transversal IAM for the Solarus PC, CPC 1 and CPC 2.

The $IAM_{transv.}$ of the Solarus PC follows the asymmetry of the geometry, where the amount of incoming light into the receiver side facing the reflector decreases from -11° to $+37.5^\circ$ since it is designed to operate at high latitudes. From Figure 77 it can be seen that the decrease in efficiency is smoother in CPC 1 than in CPC 2, possibly due to the opening in CPC 1 that leads to a loss in some reflected rays back to the sky.

On the other hand, CPC 2 $IAM_{transv.}$ pattern presents a more pronounced decrease in efficiency at the acceptance angle than CPC 1. Furthermore, neither CPC 1 or 2 have to be dependent on the solar collector tilt angle, as it can be placed as a standard PV module. On the other hand, by having a peak efficiency at -10° the Solarus PC is limited when it comes to collector tilt angle placement.

Overall, the CPC geometries show a better performance over the range of the measured incidence angles from -7.5° until $+37.5^\circ$ as the IAM factor is considerably higher than the IAM factor of the Solarus PC.

Additionally, the $IAM_{Long.}$ has been measured and compared with the longitudinal electrical IAM of the Solarus PC, being presented in the following Figure 78.

Figure 78. Normalized experimental electrical longitudinal IAM for the Solarus PC, CPC 1 and CPC 2.

Figure 78 has been developed to present the incidence angles of the highest importance, therefore incidence angles from 0° until 35° in the longitudinal direction are shown. Due to a longer distance from the receiver to the reflector plate, the Solarus PC has a bigger shadow length, therefore leading to a poorer IAM_{Long} , than CPC 1 and 2.

Furthermore, it is possible to visualize the importance of the diode system and the PV cell string layout in the overall performance of a PV system. Figure 78 clearly shows at which angle of incidence the diode system kicks in, which is around 26° and 29° for CPC 1 and 2 (respectively), and the Solarus PC around 15° . The IAM_{Long} exposes the major weakness of the MaReCo geometry when it comes to shading profiles, as a result of the relatively high distance between the receiver and the reflector plate, which will set the length of the shadow in the bottom receiver side. One way to avoid the significant drop presented previously would be to have a longer reflector, but conversely, the collector will be bigger and not economically viable.

The electrical peak power has been drawn from the IAM measurement procedure, where the top receiver side (facing the sky) reached 52.5 W/m^2 and 51.5 W/m^2 for CPC 1 and 2, respectively. On the other hand, the bottom receiver side (facing the reflector) achieved 65.7 W/m^2 and 65.1 W/m^2 for CPC 1 and 2, respectively. In total, CPC 1 achieved an electrical peak power of 118.2 W/m^2 , while CPC 2 achieved 116.6 W/m^2 , which are $+8.1 \%_{CPC1}$ and $+6.6 \%_{CPC2}$ higher than the electrical peak power of the Solarus PC ($P_{el.} = 109.7 \text{ W/m}^2$).

Moreover, the Solarus collector electrical peak efficiency is acquired at a tilt angle of -11° (Figure 77) for an IAM factor of 1.09.

In addition, for the same concentration factor, a higher electrical peak power for the CPC geometries is expected as it “produces” two focal lines,

which allows the reflected rays to be distributed more evenly in the PV cell, thus decreasing the conduction losses in the PV cell “fingers.”

4.4.6. Thermal Incidence Angle Modifier

Additionally, the test method described in section 4.1 has been applied to access the longitudinal and transversal thermal IAM, which is presented in the following Figure 79.

Figure 79. Normalized longitudinal thermal incidence angle modifier for the CPC 1 and the Solarus PC solar collector.

Figure 79 presents a very steady thermal performance at high incidence angles for both solar collectors, which was expected since the geometry has a minor impact on the thermal IAM_{Long} performance when compared with the higher impact it has on the $IAM_{transv.}$, as can be seen in Figure 80.

Figure 80. Normalized transversal thermal incidence angle modifier for the CPC 1 and the Solarus PC solar collector.

As expected, the CPC 1 has a better IAM profile than the Solarus PC as the geometry has a high impact on the efficiency of the reflected rays into the bottom receiver side. The acceptance angle is well defined, especially for the CPC 1 reflector geometry. The angles of most importance are comprised between $\pm 45^\circ$, which shows that, as in the transversal electrical IAM, the CPC 1 has an improved reflector geometry and is not limited to specific tilt angles.

4.4.7. CPC 1 Annual Energy Yield Assessment

The estimation of the electrical and thermal yields was developed through an in-house simulation tool developed by Solarus that is called CEPT, which was further validated with a minor deviation of around 5 % through the Solar Collector Energy Output Calculator (ScenoCalc, version v3.10d: SKN 2011). CEPT is an Excel-based simulation tool that allows the calculation of both electrical and thermal annual energy output. The simulation tool allows the user to input several weather files, which has been supported by hourly (time steps) meteorological data records from Meteonorm (Meteonorm, 2018) and are presented in the following Table 13.

Table 13. Summary of the weather data used, such as global, direct and diffuse radiation in the horizontal plane, latitude, longitude, standard longitude, average annual ambient temperature and average annual wind speed for four different locations.

Parameters	Unit	Location			
		Cairo	Athens	Stockholm	Cape Town
Latitude	-	30° N	38° N	59° N	34° S
Longitude	-	31° E	23° E	18° E	18° E
Standard Longitude	-	30°	30°	15°	30°
Global Horizontal Irradiation	kWh/m ² /year	2107	1722	1001	1975
Direct Horizontal Irradiance	kWh/m ² /year	1488	1168	485	1430
Diffuse Horizontal Irradiance	kWh/m ² /year	619	554	516	545
Average ambient temperature	°C	22	18	9	17
Average wind speed	m/s	4	5	3	5

Input data related to the gross area of each solar collector is required, thus CPC 1, Solarus PC, flat-plate ST collector and PV module main parameters are introduced and presented in the following Table 14.

Table 14. Normalized electrical and thermal input parameters per gross area of each solar collector/module for energy yield assessment.

	CPC 1	Solarus PC	ST flat-plate	PV module	Unit
η_{th}	51.7	52.3	76.1	-	%
$\eta_{th_diff.}$	40	39	69	-	%
c_1	4.4	3.8	4.4	-	W/m ² K
c_2	0.029	0.014	0.022	-	W/m ² K ²
η_{elect}	10.6	9.1	-	19.2	%
$\eta_{elect_diff.}$	8.2	7	-	17.3	%
β	-0.37	-0.37	-	-0.35	%/°C

A comparison between the reflector geometry CPC 1 and the Solarus PC has been made, as well as with a TrinaSolar TallMax PV module and a Viessmann Vitosol 200FM ST flat-plate solar collector is presented in the following Figure 81 for an installation site located in Cairo.

The PV module electrical energy yield has been retrieved at 35, 50, 55, 60 °C for Stockholm, Cape Town, Athens and Cairo, respectively.

A PV+ST system and CPC 1 solar collector have been placed with a collector tilt of 25°, whereas the Solarus PC has been installed with a collector tilt of 5° due to its asymmetric reflector geometry and thus a more delicate collector tilt requirement.

Figure 81. Annual energy yield (kWh/m²/year) comparison per square meter for Cairo (30° N; 31° E), Egypt. PV+ST system composed of 0.5 m² of PV and 0.5 m² of flat-plate collector. PV module electrical energy yield has been retrieved at 60 °C.

Electrically, the CPC 1 system is able to outperform the PC technology for any HTF temperature range, whereas for the PV+ST system (which comprises 0.5 m² of a PV module and 0.5 m² of a ST flat-plate solar collector) it is able to keep the performance of the PV module. As the HTF temperature range increases, the CPC 1 thermal annual yield decreases, which falls short from the PV+ST system at temperatures higher than 55 °C.

As the presented data suggests, the CPC 1 solar collector clearly outperforms the Solarus PC in annual energy yield, being the electrical energy yield that registered the highest increase, therefore the following analysis comprises the required installation area of a PV+ST system to meet the annual energy yield of one square meter of CPC 1 solar collector (Figure 82).

Figure 82. Required installation area, in m², to meet the energy yield production (thermal and electrical) of one square meter of CPC 1 solar collector, for Cairo (30° N; 31° E), Egypt.

By combining PV and ST technologies for the same temperature ranges, the PV+ST system requires +0.09 m² (at 45 °C), +0.02 m² (at 55 °C) and -0.06 m² (at 65 °C) to meet both thermal and electrical annual energy yield as the CPC 1 solar collector. Figure 82 shows that low temperature ranges favours the CPVT technology, whereas at high temperatures this advantage in installation area disappears.

A wide variety of radiation profiles are known for different locations, therefore an assessment for different sites has been developed, for Athens, Stockholm and Cape Town.

In Athens, both the PV+ST system and CPC 1 solar collector have been placed at 35° tilt, whereas the Solarus PC has been installed at 15°. Figure 83 presents the annual energy yield (kWh/m²/year) comparison per square meter for Athens, Greece.

Figure 83. Annual energy yield (kWh/m²/year) comparison per square meter for Athens (38° N; 23° E), Greece. PV+ST system composed of 0.5 m² of PV and 0.5 m² of flat-plate collector. PV module electrical energy yield has been retrieved at 55 °C.

A CPC 1 collector system is not able to deliver a higher overall annual energy yield than both PV+ST for temperatures higher than 55 °C. On the other hand, the CPC 1 system is able to outperform the Solarus PC at all ranges of temperatures.

The electrical annual yield of a CPC 1 system is fairly similar to the PV+ST system and significantly above the Solarus PC system. Moreover, the required installation area of a PV+ST system to meet the annual energy yield of one square meter of CPC 1 solar collector is presented in Figure 84.

Figure 84. Required installation area, in m², to meet the energy yield production (thermal and electrical) of one square meter of CPC 1 solar collector, for Athens (38° N; 23° E), Greece.

For an installation site located in Athens, a PV+ST system requires +0.04 m² (at 45 °C), -0.03 m² (at 55 °C) and -0.11 m² (at 65 °C) than the CPC 1 solar collector to deliver the same annual energy yield, needing fewer square meters of each technology due to its higher efficiencies for 55 °C and 65 °C.

At high latitudes, as in Stockholm, a system with a higher collector tilt is required, therefore the PV+ST system and CPC 1 solar collector have been placed with a collector tilt of 45°, whereas the Solarus PC has been installed at 25°. The annual energy yields registered for Stockholm are shown in the following Figure 85.

Figure 85. Annual energy yield (kWh/m²/year) comparison per square meter for Stockholm (59° N; 18° E), Sweden. PV+ST system composed of 0.5 m² of PV and 0.5 m² of flat-plate collector. PV module electrical energy yield has been retrieved at 35 °C.

A CPC 1 collector system, regardless of the HTF temperature range, is able to deliver a higher overall annual energy yield than the Solarus PC, which decreases as the HTF temperature ranges increase.

As expected, the Solarus PC is able to deliver more thermal energy than the CPC 1 collector as its asymmetric reflector geometry copes with the asymmetry of the solar radiation profile at these high latitudes. On the other hand, the electrical production of a CPC 1 system matches the PV+ST system and is almost one-third higher than the Solarus PC system, which presents a good solution for any location. As seen in the previous results, the main difference between the CPC 1 and the PV+ST system lies in the heat conversion factor.

The required installation area of a PV+ST system to meet the annual energy yield of one square meter of CPC 1 solar collector is presented in the following Figure 86.

Figure 86. Required installation area, in m², to meet the energy yield production (thermal and electrical) of one square meter of CPC 1 solar collector, for Stockholm (59° N; 18° E), Sweden.

In Stockholm, a PV+ST system entails less than -0.08 m² (at 45 °C), -0.17 m² (at 55 °C) and -0.28 m² (at 65 °C) to reach the same thermal and electrical annual yield as the CPC 1 solar collector.

For a system located in Cape Town, a PV+ST system and CPC 1 solar collector were installed at 30°, whereas the Solarus PC has been placed at a collector tilt of 10°. The annual energy yields registered for Cape Town are shown in the following Figure 87.

Figure 87. Annual energy yield (kWh/m²/year) comparison per square meter for Cape Town (34° S; 18° E), South Africa. PV+ST system composed of 0.5 m² of PV and 0.5 m² of flat plate collector. PV module electrical energy yield has been retrieved at 50 °C.

A PV+ST system, at HTF temperatures higher than 45 °C, is able to deliver a higher overall annual energy yield than both CPC 1 and Solarus PC. On the other hand, the CPC 1 collector is able to deliver the same electrical energy as the PV+ST system, whereas the PV+ST system is able to achieve higher thermal energy yields, due to its higher heat conversion factor.

The required installation area of a PV+ST system to meet the annual energy yield of one square meter of CPC 1 solar collector for Cape Town is presented in the following Figure 88.

Figure 88. Required installation area, in m², to meet the energy yield production (thermal and electrical) of one square meter of CPC 1 solar collector, for Cape Town (34° S; 18° E), South Africa.

A PV+ST system requires +0.03 m² (at 45 °C), -0.05 m² (at 55 °C) and -0.14 m² (at 65 °C) to deliver the same annual energy yield as the CPC 1 solar system.

It is well established that different locations will provide different performance/area ratios between PV+ST and CPVT systems, which provides a good metric for the technology installation to better fit the required energy needs. It is clear that for the given locations the overall best option is a system that comprises both PV and ST technologies since these require fewer square meters of installed area than a CPVT system. The main difference lies in the heat production as the electrical annual yield is fairly similar for both CPC 1 and PV+ST systems.

Additionally, a concentrating PVT, such as CPC and Solarus PC, will generate a lot of electricity and heat per absorber area, but not per glazed area. A CPVT system requires almost one-fourth extra area compared to a PV+ST system, for HTF temperatures of 65 °C at the worst location (Stockholm), which are typically most relevant/valued temperature which are required temperatures for DHW systems.

4.4.8. Cost Analysis of CPVT Collectors versus PV+ST Systems

While sizing a solar system, the price tag of the solar collectors must be taken into account as it will determine if the system composed by a CPVT solar collector is viable, even if it requires less installation area.

Therefore, a market screening of available CPVT products has been developed, which was supported by Lämmle's (2018) market survey for PV, flat-plate and PVT collectors for the German market.

The average market selling price to customers per square meter for an asymmetric CPVT is 250 €/m², whereas a PVT-unglazed is around 417 €/m² and a PVT-glazed roughly around 455 €/m². A monocrystalline PV module price typically ranges from around 100 and 186 €/m², while a polycrystalline PV module is comprised of 80 and 120 €/m². A flat-plate solar collector usually has a cost of 271 €/m², while an evacuated tube thermal collector reaches around 463 €/m² (Lämmle, 2018)¹⁵. Surprisingly, the price of an unglazed PVT collector is given by the sum of an average mono-Si PV module and a flat-plate collector.

A size reduction per gross area of -14% has been achieved, while the height of the collector decreased by -23% (which leads to a decrease in the overall volume of around -33%), thus fewer raw materials are used by the CPC 1 solar collector. Therefore a lower price tag can be achieved through a material list breakdown and applying the required size reductions, which led to an estimated value of 223 €/m².

The following Table 15 presents the relation between the required installation area (presented in Figures 82, 84, 86 and 88) of a PV+ST system for different HTF temperature ranges and its individual costs. This trend sets the threshold for a competitive price tag of a CPVT solar collector for the specifics of this study.

Table 15. Threshold for a competitive price tag of a CPVT solar collector (CPC 1), in €/m², based on the required installation area of a conventional PV+ST, for different HTF temperature ranges.

	Cairo (30° N; 31° E)			Athens (38° N; 23° E)			Stockholm (59° N; 18° E)			Cape Town (34° S; 18° E)		
	45 °C	55 °C	65 °C	45 °C	55 °C	65 °C	45 °C	55 °C	65 °C	45 °C	55 °C	65 °C
	PV+ST	228	213	194	216	200	180	186	163	136	214	196

For simplicity, the value of heat and electricity has been assumed with the same relevance, even though this might be slightly dissimilar at different locations/regions, as each country might produce its energy via different methods and sources (e.g. coal, gas, oil, etc.).

Table 15 presents threshold for the required net list price for a PVT or CPVT solar collector to be competitive against PV+ST systems.

The bigger the PV module share in a PV+ST system, the bigger the gap between systems. In fact, the flat-plate installation share is the one that sets the PV+ST viability, as the PV module share is fairly constant for a wide range of HTF temperatures.

The higher the HTF temperature the bigger the cost gap between systems, which can reach up to +50%_{rel} for the worst case scenario for Stockholm. Therefore, a CPVT system must be further developed in terms of material costs, in which the bifacial PVT receiver is the most costly part of the CPVT solar collector.

¹⁵ The net list prices, which do not include taxes, are related to the primary energy collector yield.

4.5. RES4BUILD Project

Under grant agreement No. 814865 (RES4BUILD), the following research work has been supported with funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program.

The "Clean Energy for All Europeans" package, presented by the European Commission on 30th of November (2016), is guided by three main goals: prioritize energy efficiency, achieve global leadership in renewable energies, and provide a fair deal to consumers. The project aims at decarbonizing the energy consumption in buildings by developing integrated renewable energy-based solutions that are tailored to the needs and requirements of users and installers.

The author's main objective within the RES4BUILD project is to improve the performance and reduce the cost of the most innovative components of the RES4BUILD solutions, specifically a CPVT solar collector. The required developments focus on the reduction of the thermal losses and at the same time on the enhancement of heat harvesting from the PV cells to the thermal absorber, as well as adapt reflector geometries to suit a wide range of latitudes.

Therefore, a CPVT solar collector has been built and developed based on the findings of Paper IV. The CPVT has the same geometry as the CPC 1 reflector geometry of Paper IV, however, it has reflective gables instead of transparent gables, which was necessary to reduce the costs of the solar collector within the project.

The newly built RES4BUILD CPVT solar collector is presented in the following Figure 89.

Figure 89. CPVT solar collector test apparatus (orientation: east-west direction) for different testing procedures with both pyranometers for global (KippZonen CMP6) and diffuse (KippZonen CMP3) radiation measurement.

4.5.1. Test Results

The following section presents different sets of results, such as electrical daily (instantaneous) peak power, optical efficiency from thermal measurements, day and dark heat losses, and both transversal and longitudinal (electrical and thermal) IAM diagrams.

4.5.2. Electrical Peak Efficiency

For a clear sky day in September, a daily electrical performance profile of the LCPVT solar collector has been drawn. The data has been collected for the whole day of the 19th of September for a collector tilt of 61° (location: Gävle) and a constant HTF temperature of 20 °C, whereas the ambient temperature reached as high as 15 °C.

Figure 90 shows the electrical peak efficiency diagram as a function of the module temperature, where the influence of the HTF and ambient temperature in the electrical peak efficiency is registered.

Figure 90. Electrical efficiency trendline diagram per gross area.

Electrical peak efficiency of 10.83% ($R^2=0.999$) has been achieved for a module temperature of 25 °C, which is higher by +19 and +2% than the electrical peak efficiency of the Solarus PC and CPC 1 solar collectors, respectively.

4.5.3. Efficiency from Thermal Measurements

The overall η and U_l as a function of both HTF and ambient temperatures diagram is expressed in the following Figure 91.

Figure 91. Experimental overall efficiency trendline diagram per gross area.

The day heat loss coefficient U_l reached 4.4 W/m².K. Regarding the overall efficiency, a value of 63.1% (divided in 52.3%_{th} and 10.83%_{elect}, $R^2 = 0.995$) has been obtained. The heat losses decreased around -12%, whereas the electrical peak efficiency increased +2% in relation to the CPC 1 solar collector.

Figure 92 presents the experimental heat loss coefficient (dark U-value) per aperture area.

Figure 92. Experimental overall efficiency trendline diagram per gross area.

A dark U-value $1.9 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$ ($R^2 = 0.999$) has been obtained. As expected, the dark U-value is lower than the day U-value obtained from Figure 86.

Overall, the Solarus PC overall efficiency, per gross area, is -3% lower than the RES4BUILD solar collector. Furthermore, the Solarus PC has a lower day U-value of $3.5 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$ (Solarus, 2018) due to the higher concentration ratio.

Additionally, the difference between the theoretical and the measured optical efficiency lies in the incidence angle and on the silicone gel transmittance losses, which will be magnified for high incidence angles, where the difference between the theoretical and measured optical efficiency from I_{sc} measurements is higher.

4.5.4. Incidence Angle Modifier

From the test method previously described for both transversal and longitudinal electrical IAM, the following section presents an analysis of the results obtained for the electrical $IAM_{Long.}$ and $IAM_{Transv.}$. Figures 93 and 94 present the normalized transversal and longitudinal electrical/thermal incidence angle modifier for the RES4BUILD and Solarus PC solar collectors.

Figure 93. Electrical and thermal transversal incidence angle modifier for the RES4BUILD and Solarus PC solar collectors.

The decrease in efficiency is smoother in the RES4BUILD solar collector, due to the opening in section A of the CPC reflector geometry.

Moreover, the electrical peak power from the IAM measurement has been drawn, which achieved 122 W/m^2 , which is +11% higher than the electrical peak power of the Solarus PC ($P_{el.} = 109 \text{ W/m}^2$).

Figure 94. Electrical and thermal longitudinal incidence angle modifier for the RES4BUILD and Solarus PC solar collectors.

The importance of the diode system in the PV cell string layout in the overall performance of the RES4BUILD PV system is very well defined, as it kicks in at around 25° and 60°, which is significantly later than the PC solar collector at 15° and 50°, respectively.

The difference between the two solar collectors lies in the difference between the type of gables implemented on each CPVT solar collector, which is transparent in the Solarus PC and CPC 1, and reflective in the RES4BUILD solar collector. As expected, the reflective gables slightly decreased the longitudinal IAM since no light goes through at incident angles higher than +55°.

On the other hand, this penalty in performance will not significantly affect the performance at relevant incident angles between 0° and +55°. Moreover, adding transparent gables is expected to increase, to some extent, the annual energy yield of the RES4BUILD solar collector.

4.5.5. RES4BUILD Energy Yield Assessment

The estimation of the electrical and thermal yields was also performed through CEPT, to be able to compare the RES4BUILD solar collector and an arbitrary PV module (TrinaSolar AllMax Plus) and a flat-plate solar collector (Veissmann Vitosol 200FM-SV2F).

The main input parameters, per gross area, of the RES4BUILD solar collector, are presented in the following Table 16.

Table 16. Electrical and thermal input parameters per gross area for the RES4BUILD solar collector for an energy yield assessment, as well as for the previous simulated solar collectors.

	RES4BUILD	CPC 1	Solarus PC	ST flat-plate	PV module	Unit
η_{th}	52.3	51.7	52.3	76.1	-	%
$\eta_{th_diff.}$	40	40	39	69	-	%
c_1	3.9	4.8	3.8	4.4	-	W/m ² K
c_2	0.026	0.029	0.014	0.022	-	W/m ² K ²
η_{elect}	10.8	10.6	9.1	-	19.2	%
$\eta_{elect_diff.}$	8.3	8.2	7	-	17.3	%
β	-0.37	-0.37	-0.37	-	-0.35	%/°C

The RES4BUILD solar collector, due to its improved collector tightness and overall efficiencies, is expected to outperform the CPC 1 solar collector and therefore decrease the performance gap between a PV+ST system and a CPVT collector presented in section 4.5.

Moreover, the annual energy yield comparison between the RES4BUILD solar collector, a TrinaSolar AllMax Plus PV module and a Veissmann Vitosol 200FM-SV2F flat-plate solar collector is presented in the following Table 17.

Moreover, the abovementioned assessment has been updated to directly evaluate these systems with the Solarus PC. The annual energy yield has been assessed for different locations such as Cairo, Athens, Stockholm and Cape Town, where the same solar collector tilt angles as the ones presented in the previous section 4.4.7 have been applied.

Table 17. Annual energy yield (kWh/m²/year) comparison per square meter for Cairo, Athens, Stockholm and Cape Town. PV+ST system is composed of 0.5 m² of PV and 0.5 m² of ST flat-plate collector. The PV module electrical energy yield has been retrieved at 35, 50, 55, 60 °C for Stockholm, Cape Town, Athens and Cairo, respectively.

		PV+ST		RES4BUILD		Solarus PC	
		Th.	Elect.	Th.	Elect.	Th.	Elect.
Cairo (30° N; 31° E)	45 °C	639	177	761	189	699	131
	55 °C	550	177	625	181	576	125
	65 °C	463	177	488	174	458	119
Athens (38° N; 23° E)	45 °C	473	152	536	160	501	112
	55 °C	396	152	423	154	400	107
	65 °C	322	152	318	147	310	102
Stockholm (59° N; 18° E)	45 °C	200	97	197	98	190	72
	55 °C	150	97	132	94	134	69
	65 °C	108	97	80	90	87	66
Cape Town (34° S; 18° E)	45 °C	535	175	608	180	560	126
	55 °C	449	175	479	173	448	121
	65 °C	366	175	356	166	346	115

The lower heat losses allows the RES4BUILD collector to outperform the Solarus PC system at all HTF temperature ranges, for Cairo.

Moreover, improvements of around +16% (at 45 °C), +11% (at 55 °C) and +3% (at 65 °C) in the annual energy yield have been registered when compared with a PV+ST system, which will decrease the performance gap between PV+ST and CPVT systems. This improvement is mainly due to the increased thermal peak efficiency (+1.1%), which increased the thermal yield of the RES4BUILD solar collector by +5% (at 45 °C), +7% (at 55 °C) and +11% (at 65 °C).

For Athens, the RES4BUILD system is able to deliver an average of +29 kWh/m²/year of heat and roughly +2 kWh/m²/year of electricity than a ST collector and PV module, respectively for all ranges of temperatures.

The least effective site location is Stockholm as it requires a more controlled collector tilt angle due to the specificity of the reflector geometry. Nevertheless the improvements were shown to be significant as it was able to outperform the Solarus PC at any range of temperatures.

For the southern hemisphere, in Cape Town, improvements were seen of around +14% (at 45 °C), +5% (at 55 °C) and -4% (at 65 °C) in the annual energy yield in relation with the presented values of the PV+ST system.

Overall, the performance gap difference, on average, increased for the RES4BUILD solar collector for 45 °C and 55 °C by 10% and 2%, respectively. At temperature ranges of 65 °C the performance gap increased for the PV+ST system by 5%, meaning that for higher temperatures the CPVT is not competitive against a PV+ST solar system.

With the RES4BUILD solar collector being an improvement of CPC 1 solar collector, as presented in section 4.5, it was expected to outperform the Solarus PC and therefore after the validation of the results in Table 18, the following analysis was made in relation solely to a PV+ST system and the RES4BUILD solar collector.

Table 18. Required installation area, in m², to meet the energy yield production (thermal and electrical) of one square meter of the RES4BUILD solar collector, for Cairo, Athens, Stockholm and Cape Town. The PV module electrical energy yield has been retrieved at 35, 50, 55, 60 °C for Stockholm, Cape Town, Athens and Cairo, respectively.

		PV	ST	PV+ST
Cairo (30° N; 31° E)	45 °C	0.53	0.60	1.13
	55 °C	0.51	0.57	1.08
	65 °C	0.49	0.53	1.02
Athens (38° N; 23° E)	45 °C	0.53	0.57	1.10
	55 °C	0.51	0.53	1.04
	65 °C	0.49	0.49	0.98
Stockholm (59° N; 18° E)	45 °C	0.51	0.49	1.00
	55 °C	0.49	0.44	0.93
	65 °C	0.47	0.37	0.84
Cape Town (34° S; 18° E)	45 °C	0.51	0.57	1.08
	55 °C	0.49	0.53	1.02
	65 °C	0.47	0.49	0.96

In Cairo, Egypt, the new improvements presented in the RES4BUILD solar system lead to an increased installation area of the PV+ST system, which requires +0.13 m² (at 45 °C), +0.08 m² (at 55 °C) and +0.02 m² (at 65 °C) to reach the same annual energy yield as the RES4BUILD solar system.

The increased annual energy yield registered in Athens leads to a smaller installation area of a CPVT system on average of around -0.04 m². A PV+ST system requires +0.1 m² (at 45 °C), +0.04 m² (at 55 °C) and -0.02 m² (at 65 °C) of installed area than the RES4BUILD solar system.

For Stockholm, the installation area of a PV+ST system decreased on average by -11% (compared to Athens), which can be translated into -0.07 m² (at 55 °C) and -0.16 m² (at 65 °C).

On the other hand, Cape Town registered an increment in installation area of a PV+ST system similar to Athens, as +0.08 m² (at 45 °C), +0.02 m² (at 55 °C) and -0.04 m² (at 65 °C) is required to reach the annual energy yield of the RES4BUILD solar system.

As expected, the electrical installation share proved to be fairly constant, whereas the heat production as the HTF temperature rises requires fewer square meters of ST collectors.

4.5.6. Cost Analysis of the RES4BUILD Collector versus PV+ST Systems

The study performed for the CPC 1 in section 4.4.8 has been replicated for the RES4BUILD solar collector and presented below. The same ST and PV collector/module has been used, while the annual energy yield for the RES4BUILD collector has been updated to reflect the results presented in section 4.5.5.

Therefore, Table 19 presents the relation between the RES4BUILD collector price (223 €/m²) compared with the required installation area (presented in Table 18) of a PV+ST system for different HTF temperature ranges.

Table 19. Threshold for a competitive price tag of a CPVT solar collector (RES4BUILD), in €/m², based in the required installation area of a conventional PV+ST, for different HTF temperature ranges.

	Cairo (30° N; 31° E)			Athens (38° N; 23° E)			Stockholm (59° N; 18° E)			Cape Town (34° S; 18° E)		
	45 °C	55 °C	65 °C	45 °C	55 °C	65 °C	45 °C	55 °C	65 °C	45 °C	55 °C	65 °C
	PV+ST	238	227	213	229	217	203	206	188	167	228	215

The RES4BUILD solar collector, due to its improved performance (e.g. in relation with the CPC 1 collector), is able to decrease the €/m² gap between a CPVT and a system composed of PV and ST solar technologies. This can be translated by a higher installation area of the PV+ST system and therefore a required higher price than the one presented in Table 15.

At 45 °C, the CPVT system is able to be competitive for all medium and low latitudes. However, at high latitudes such as in Stockholm, the PV+ST system is more viable in costs. Despite being, performance-wise, very competitive at 55 °C, the high costs of the CPVT system do not pay off.

5. Conclusions and Outlook

The presented work has been divided into design and testing of a specific symmetric concentrating PVT solar collector for standing/vertical and horizontal receiver/absorber placement.

Paper I and II are related to the design concept of symmetrical reflector geometries, whereas Papers III, IV and the RES4BUILD project focus on the field testing measurements of the developed reflector geometries of Papers I and II.

The main focus of this thesis work is comprised of Papers II, IV and the RES4BUILD project as it presented the most promising and trustworthy results from all the Papers I-IV content.

In Paper I, a symmetrical reflector shape, either CPC or parabolic trough, has been coupled with vertical standing receivers with several widths and studied for its IAM and annual energy yield. Only the optical properties of the reflector material have been taken into account (i.e., no additional material optical properties are taken into account, such as glazing and PV cells).

A CPC reflector shape has been coupled with a triangular PVT receiver, in Paper III, where its IAM, and electrical and thermal efficiency have been assessed, which follows to some extent the work developed in Paper I.

Following the process presented above, the development of a CPC geometry based on an ideal concentrator has been presented in Paper II, in which four different reflector geometries have been analyzed. From the findings presented in Paper II, Paper IV presents the field outdoor measurements of two of the four CPC geometries studied in Paper II, which were further developed and outdoor tested in Paper IV. Additionally, the findings from Paper IV were further enhanced by the development of the RES4BUILD project, in which the CPC solar collector presented and tested in Paper IV was further improved, which led to increased efficiencies and therefore higher energy conversion factors.

5.1. Paper I

The design concepts aim to provide low-cost energy, by replacing partially the expensive receiver with cheap reflectors. A great part of the incoming available solar radiation will be collected without the need for tracking due to the use of reflectors and specific symmetric geometry.

Due to the symmetric reflector shape, both transversal and longitudinal IAM profiles are, as expected, symmetrical for each collector. The CPC geometry achieved higher annual energy yields due to their broader IAMs, which presents a better option than a pure parabolic trough collector. Therefore, further studies should focus on CPC reflector geometries.

5.2. Paper II

The use of a symmetric reflector geometry allows higher annual outputs worldwide, while a low concentration factor is necessary to avoid tracking and a

lower collector depth to reduce the shading, which is particularly important for the electrical part of any CPVT design concept.

CPC 1 and 2 achieved higher annual energy yields from +3 to +7%_{rel} than CPC 3 and 4, respectively. This is due to the 24 mm gap, which causes part of the incoming reflected light to miss the reflector, thus leading to lower energy yields. The study showed the electrical yield to be less sensitive than the thermal yield for the different design concept variations. This happens, as the partial shading on the PV cells has not been taken into account, otherwise, the electrical yield would be expected to be more sensitive than the thermal yield, as section A will more significantly influence CPC 1 and 2.

The transversal IAM (for the bottom receiver side) proves to be very sensitive to the higher receiver placement (opening in section A), allowing some light to pass under the receiver and be reflected to the exterior. Furthermore, the placement of the receiver also affects the transversal IAM for the top receiver side, as it can collect some reflected light from the reflector (top side of section C).

By having a thinner receiver and a deeper reflector the overall annual total yield will increase, regardless of the geometry concept employed. Increasing the reflector depth will only be profitable if the cost increment of materials is lower than the value of the annual energy gains. For this reason, the location of the installation is of critical importance as the price of heat and electricity varies significantly around the world and as the climate patterns also vary significantly.

Moreover, the study showed that the longitudinal direction is closely related to the shading effect, as partial shadowing increases more significantly from 30° onwards, making CPC 4 the reflector geometry that copes better with partial shadowing.

Nevertheless, and based on the findings, the author believes that CPC 2 was shown to be the most promising geometry due to the radiation profile on the bottom receiver side. Furthermore, CPC 1 and 2 display more uniform radiation distribution profiles than the remaining geometries, leading to lower maximum incident radiation, thus higher energy yields and lower level of cell stress, which ultimately means higher durability.

5.3. Paper III

The developed work has been funded by the Swedish Foundation for International Cooperation in Research and Higher Education, under grant number ME 2018-7559, therefore the receiver shape (i.e., triangular PVT receiver shape) has been locked to the project and not the desired flat bifacial receiver that has been implemented in Paper I.

The measurement results made on a low concentration PVT solar collector reached an overall electrical peak efficiency of 8% while the thermal optical efficiency reached 58.3% and 59.9% for trough 1 and 2, respectively.

Heat loss coefficients of 4.1 and 4.0 W/m².°C were attained for trough 1 and 2, respectively.

The electrical transversal IAM for each receiver side reached an electrical peak efficiency at 10° , which is in line with the half-acceptance angle of the reflector geometry.

In sum, the design concept has been successful in reducing the electrical peak power at normal incidence, and thus lowering the stress and high radiation intensity to which the solar cells are exposed at normal incidence.

5.4. Paper IV

As intended, the measurement results confirmed that both CPC 1 and 2 geometries (i.e., CPC 4 and 1 in Paper II, respectively) are an improvement from the MaReCo geometry of the Solarus PC. The electrical peak efficiency had an improvement of 17.7% and 17.3%, for CPC 1 and 2, respectively. Moreover, the electrical peak power improved by 8.1% and 6.6%, for CPC 1 and 2, respectively. On the other hand, the measured optical efficiency increased 5.6% for CPC 1 and 4.7% for CPC2, which can be translated to 3.5% and 2.5% in thermal peak power for CPC 1 and 2, respectively.

Furthermore, the heat loss coefficient for both CPC 1 and 2 increased due to the lower concentration factor, but on the other hand, the U-value can be lowered around $-15\%_{\text{CPC1}}$ up to $-24\%_{\text{CPC2}}$ by adding insulation on the back cover and by sealing the solar glass to the collector box.

Last but not least, the IAM profiles showed the biggest improvement of all the parameters that have been measured as CPC 1 and 2 were revealed to be less sensitive to high longitudinal incidence angles than the Solarus PC, and thus increasing the overall amount of working hours. The results of this study show that CPC 1 solar collector can deliver the same electrical energy yield making use of a smaller collector area than the Solarus PC, depending on the HTF temperature range employed.

Moreover, for studied locations, a PV+ST system requires less installation area than a CPC 1 and Solarus PC systems. Nevertheless, the improved CPVT collector strongly outperforms the Solarus PC in area usage, as it requires less -0.14 m^2 of installed area.

At all ranges of temperatures, the CPC 1 solar collector presented nearly the same electrical annual yield as the PV+ST system, while falling short in the thermal energy yield. At low operating HTF temperatures, CPC 1 solar collector is competitive. Nevertheless, the energy performance gap between both technologies decreased, mainly due to the improvements registered at the electrical side of the CPC 1.

The presented study reveals that a CPVT system must be further developed, especially in material costs, in which the bifacial PVT receiver is the most expensive component of the CPVT solar collector. Additionally, a bifacial PVT receiver comprising PV cells (high emitters) should be equipped with a selective surface to cover the non-producing areas, thus increasing the thermal energy yield by means of a higher thermal efficiency.

5.5. RES4BUILD Project

The insulation developments made to the CPC 1 solar collector from Paper IV revealed enhanced overall efficiencies and lower heat losses, which leads to higher annual energy yields.

Moreover, the developments showed that the RES4BUILD solar collector is not able to reach the required heat production of ST collectors at higher temperatures, whereas it is able to compete with a system composed by 0.5 m² of a PV module.

The trade-off between the higher cost of a PVT collector and PV or ST collectors must be balanced by the value of both heat and electricity produced. The heat can be delivered to a heating station or used directly by the system, or else it must be stored. On the other hand, electricity can be delivered to the grid, used directly (which enhances the savings and therefore enhances the return on investment (ROI) depending on the local electricity prices), as well as stored either in batteries or converted into heat.

Nevertheless, and as specified in section 5.4, this design concept requires further development in both cost and performance, which can be mitigated by the employment of new materials to enhance (especially) the thermal efficiency and bring down the costs.

5.6. Outlook

Due to the combination of both PV and ST technologies in the same gross area, PVT technologies employ the benefits of cooling the PV cells, thus increasing their overall efficiency, and thus using this excess heat to increase the HTF temperature of a ST system.

The asymmetry of the MaReCo geometry employed by Solarus in their CPVT, limits the performance of the PC in location sites at medium and low latitudes. At these locations, the solar radiation pattern is considered symmetric with higher solar altitudes (i.e., higher latitudes have lower solar altitudes, thus lower latitudes have higher solar altitudes) and thus not suitable for the specific asymmetric MaReCo reflector geometry that requires lower incidence angles to match the heat demand with the heat production. To accomplish a more balanced heat production, the asymmetry of the MaReCo geometry reflects away the solar radiation in the summer, whereas in the remaining months it is able to focus the incoming light towards the receiver.

The initial reflector geometry development required a Monte Carlo ray-tracing software with the support of a MATLAB script. The ray-tracing software proved to be an adequate tool for the thermal assessment of reflector geometries, whereas for the electrical assessment the software presents limitations that should be tackled in the future. Nevertheless, the ray-tracing software with the support of a MATLAB script is able to efficiently assess the incidence angle modifiers, as well as optical efficiencies (RQ-I).

Different symmetrical reflector trough shapes have been developed either with longer receiver widths or east-west/north-south placements. Amongst the simulated reflector geometries, CPC reflector shapes proved to be the most

efficient with +11%_{rel} higher annual energy yields than a parabolic trough collector.

The newly developed symmetric reflector geometry, based on an ideal CPC reflector geometry for ST collectors, aimed at maximizing the incoming solar radiation without the need to sacrifice the electrical production while being a stationary solar collector. At the same time, the reflector shape simultaneously reduces the non-uniform illumination on the bottom receiver side, which will decelerate the PV cell material degradation and increase the overall CPVT collector lifespan. The CPC geometry proved to be the best solution as it can outperform the asymmetry of the Solarus PC reflector geometry, and thus yield more energy at lower latitudes (RQ-II). Additionally, the use of a symmetric reflector geometry allows higher annual energy yields, matching the symmetric annual heat demand profile for low and medium latitudes (RQ-II and III).

To achieve higher annual energy yields the CPC geometry went through several modifications/versions in which different reflector layouts were experimented on and subsequently two of them were selected to be further analyzed through field measurements. The outdoor field measurements were performed according to the international standards ISO 9806:2017 (employing SST testing methods) and 61215:2016 in which several parameters were retrieved such as electrical and thermal IAM, electrical and thermal efficiencies, and heat loss coefficients. The real-life outdoor measurements showed significant improvements in all parameters, such as electrical and thermal IAM (RQ-IV), as well as overall peak efficiencies. The presented improvements increased the overall annual energy yield of CPVT solar collectors when placed side by side with an asymmetric reflector geometry such as the Solarus PC (RQ-III).

Moreover, an improved version (namely RES4BUILD) of the CPC reflector geometry, which consisted solely of a tighter collector box, allowed the RES4BUILD solar collector to further improve its electrical and thermal efficiency, as well as decrease its heat losses and thus reach higher annual energy yields than the CPC collector (RQ-III).

Furthermore, an assessment was made to find the real significance of the obtained results, in which a direct comparison with a PV+ST solar system has been made (Table 20).

Table 20. Annual energy yield (kWh/m²/year) comparison per square meter for four different site locations. A PV+ST system has been composed of 0.5 m² of PV modules and 0.5 m² of flat-plate collectors. The PV module electrical energy yield has been retrieved at 35, 50, 55, 60 °C for Stockholm, Cape Town, Athens and Cairo, respectively.

		PV+ST		CPC 1		RES4BUILD		Solarus PC	
		Th.	Elect.	Th.	Elect.	Th.	Elect.	Th.	Elect.
Cairo (30° N; 31° E)	45 °C	639	177	722	185	761	189	699	131
	55 °C	550	177	573	178	625	181	576	125
	65 °C	463	177	426	170	488	174	458	119
Athens (38° N; 23° E)	45 °C	473	152	497	157	536	160	501	112
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	65 °C	322	152	267	144	318	147	310	102
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	55 °C	150	97	105	92	132	94	134	69
	65 °C	108	97	56	88	80	90	87	66
Cape Town (34° S; 18° E)	45 °C	535	175	559	177	608	180	560	126
	55 °C	449	175	421	170	479	173	448	121
	65 °C	366	175	293	162	356	166	346	115

A symmetric reflector geometry (i.e., CPC and RES4BUILD) when placed side-by-side with an asymmetric reflector geometry (i.e., PC) presents higher annual energy yields when deployed in low or medium latitudes, as the winter solar radiation (and consequently the energy yield) increases.

CPVT technologies, at their current development, are not able to compete with mature technologies such as PV and ST at high temperatures, neither in overall performance nor in cost competitiveness, since a system competitiveness is extremely dependent on the type of collector, system and location.

Nevertheless, this thesis work presents significant upgrades to the current CPVT solar collector by means of an improved reflector geometry, which led to a performance gap reduction between technologies (RQ-V). Additionally, further developments in regards to the tightness of solar collectors can lead, to some extent, to improved overall efficiencies and therefore higher energy yields (RQ-VI). Furthermore, mass production must be in the horizon of PVT manufacturers to further reduce costs.

PVT technologies are potentially a viable solution to compete with isolated systems as PV and ST solar collectors if a significant reduction in manufacturing cost is achieved, coupled with an increased energy production performance. Therefore, its success is intensely linked to the capacity of the PVT industry/researchers to scale down its current system cost and complexity in a way that can shorten the cost/performance gap to both PV and ST technologies, which have several decades of constant development, especially the PV industry with an exponential performance increment and constant decrease in material costs.

Additionally, a bifacial PVT receiver comprising PV cells, which are high emitters, should be equipped with a selective surface to increase the thermal energy yield by means of a higher thermal efficiency.

For PVT systems to have a fair chance compared to PV systems, special high subsidy levels for PVT systems are suggested for the following years. It is estimated that these subsidies might generate a sustainable market for PVT and PV systems. Perers et al. (2021) suggests some principles for a subsidy scheme, such as:

- The subsidy is only paid as long as the system is working and according to how high the energy production is, in €/kWh, which will promote a sustainable after-market for repair and upgrade systems.
- The subsidy level is lowered on a yearly basis for new customers, according to the system cost development on the market.
- Early PVT investors get a contract with a high enough fixed subsidy (in €/kWh), stable over 10 years, to create a more predictable payback time, even when the reduction in system costs and subsidy reductions is fast for later customers.
- The energy meter should be located directly after the PVT inverter, to avoid economic uncertainties, due to local differences in self-consumption.
- If possible, add another energy meter on the thermal side, which can be used with a different lower subsidy level.
- These meter results can also be used to assure and compare system performance and provide assistance to companies.

From an environmental perspective, the overall production of Si-PV modules requires high intake of fossil fuels from countries such as China and Vietnam, which increases the dependency from non-renewable energy sources. Conversely, the production of CPC-PVT solar collectors, as a hybrid component, uses less electric energy and less coal power.

Other ways to increase useful thermal power at higher temperatures might rely on low-emissivity coatings either on top/bottom of solar glass covers or on top of the receiver core. Low-emissivity coatings for low concentrating PVT collectors can decrease the overall heat loss coefficient by $-36\%_{\text{rel}}$ and thus incrementally increase the useful thermal power of a CPVT solar collector (Lämmle, 2018). The application of low-emissivity coatings in either bottom of the glass cover or receiver core has the drawback of slightly decreasing the electrical peak power by $-8\%_{\text{rel}}$ (Lämmle, 2018), which might be acceptable since the useful thermal power significantly increases. However, further studies are required to reduce reflectance and absorptance losses in the coatings. On the other hand, limited suitable highly transparent low-emissivity coatings are commercially available, which might limit a wider deployment of low-emissivity coatings in CPVT collectors.

Furthermore, PVT technologies, in theory, allow the end-user to benefit from both feed-in tariffs and renewable heat incentives (RHI), due to the simultaneous production of electricity and heat. For DHW systems, in the UK, PVT technologies only benefit from the feed-in tariffs. However, for non-DHW systems, PVT technologies benefit from both incentives, which decreases the payback time.

In addition, the financial attractiveness concerning manufacturing and indirect costs can be improved by providing complete solar solutions with pre-configured packages of PVT collectors and auxiliary heating systems that facilitate the end-user's decision. Moreover, architectonic integration of PVT technologies into the building envelope offers a combined solution for both electricity and heat production while requiring less installation area.

As seen in Figures 81, 83, 85 and 87 the PVT system falls short in heat production, which produces its majority of heat for DHW in the summer months. Whereas, in the winter months, when the required amount of DHW is not met, a back-up system is required such as a heating component (i.e., boiler). This issue is also seen in ST systems, thus PVT technologies by also supplying electricity are on the verge of potentially being competitive, as PVTs are, at the core, ST collectors that are able to produce electricity from the same gross area, which makes the future of PVT technology strictly reliant on the future of ST technologies, which rely on energy efficiency, durability and reliability aspects of a collector development.

The current global transformation of energy systems based on fossil fuels to RE systems lies predominantly on a high share of electrical power generation. The aim of reaching the required share of heating and cooling via power generation by the end of this century seems unrealistic at today's progress, which will require sustainable solutions such as ST and therefore PVT collectors.

The electrical storage trend is already ongoing by means of electrical batteries, nonetheless heat tends to be easier, cheaper and environmentally friendlier to store than electricity, as it already gave real proof of its maturity and efficient reliability. In this way, PVT technologies have an opportunity to increase their market share, not neglecting permanent developments, both in terms of performance and in terms of cost reduction.

The high share of greenhouse gas emissions in the heat sector requires a severe and methodical decarbonization by a balanced technology mix, in which ST and PVT technologies must be considered, as it is crucial to achieve the already proposed goals in several environmental agreements.

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Papers

Associated papers have been removed in the electronic version of this thesis.

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